

**INVESTIGATING THE CHALLENGES AFFECTING THE CO-
EVOLUTION OF UNIVERSITIES IN A COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT:
THE CASE OF LEBANESE UNIVERSITIES**

A thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy

By

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to my family and friends. They supported and encouraged me unconditionally during my doctoral journey, giving me a chance to thrive. It would be hard to express my full gratitude to all who directly or indirectly contributed to this research.

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Declaration

This thesis is submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in support of my application for the doctoral degree. This is to certify that this thesis entitled “*Investigating the Challenges Affecting the Co-Evolution of Universities in a Competitive Environment: The Case of Lebanese Universities*” is the result of my own work and has not been previously submitted for any other degree from this or another university. I also declare that all information contained in this document has been produced by me and that the work contained herein is my own except where explicitly specified otherwise in the text. The work presented is in accordance with academic rules and ethical conduct recommended by the University of the West of Scotland.

Abstract

Interactions between organizations and their environments are central to organizational research and practice in a constantly changing environment. However, despite the significance of this topic in several fields and disciplines, there are few studies on how organizations can co-evolve with their environment. The present research seeks to examine this apparent theoretical and empirical deficiency by providing an extensive understanding and comprehensive analysis of the relationship between organizations and their environment. The research also identifies key factors limiting higher education institutions' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

The present research adopted qualitative research methodology, interpretive paradigm, and multiple case study approach to collect and analyze research data using semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection tool. The research data was collected mainly from higher education institutions in Lebanon. Through in-depth interviews, the researcher explored Lebanese universities managers' perceptions of Lebanese higher education field and knowledge of how Lebanese universities interact with their environment. Thirty-nine interviews were conducted with participants from twenty-six Lebanese universities. Interview data were analyzed using thematic analysis and presented in eight themes.

The empirical evidence revealed that six sets of factors influence Lebanese universities' co-evolution with their environment. The influencing factors are internal, external, managerial capabilities, capability-building processes, competition, and organizational outcome.

Theoretically, this research contributes to organizational and management research and extends the growing research on organizational co-evolution. The research provides a deeper understanding of the relationship between an organization and its environment through a co-evolutionary approach. The present research provides a comprehensive co-evolutionary

framework investigating the main internal and external factors affecting an organization's ability to co-evolve. From a practical perspective, the present research can help organizations and managers construct an apprehension of the relationship between organizations and their environment and managers' role in administering this relation, responding to external environmental conditions, leading change, and preparing organizations to better face altered environment conditions by adopting a new alternative approach. As a result of this research, a comprehensive view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment will be presented. This will help policymakers support local universities and enhance Lebanese higher education system.

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Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher presents a brief outline of the present research. This chapter includes eight sections. Section 1.1 introduces the first chapter of this research, while Section 1.2 provides the background of the research. In addition, this chapter provides an overview of the main challenges facing universities worldwide (Section 1.3) research problem (Section 1.4) research rationale (Section 1.5) research aim, objectives, and questions (Section 1.6) summary of research methodology (Section 1.7) and concludes with the thesis structure (Section 1.8).

1.2 Background

As organizations, universities do not operate dependently or externally to their environment (Musselin, 2018; Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021). Organizations regularly replicate their environment's characteristics, and in many situations, environmental conditions influence organizations that operate within or relate to a specific environment (Hillmann, J. and Guenther, 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021). Due to education globalization, universities are currently open to a broader international environment (Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; Cantwell et al., 2022). Universities are not just affected by local environments but also by the international higher education environment (Chankseliani and McCowan, 2021; Cantwell et al., 2022). Due to the rapid acceleration in technology, new education services and products emerged affecting the higher education landscape (Orr et al., 2020). This has led to increased external pressure on universities and created a competitive higher education landscape (Orr et al., 2020).

Higher education has evolved into a highly competitive environment in which universities are required to renew their capabilities and develop improved, more innovative services and programs to compete with their rivals (Orr et al., 2020). Universities started embracing flexibility and openness to innovative learning techniques and models to cope with new education trends and demands, challenging the traditional dominant characteristics of education (Cheung et al., 2021). Various products and services were developed in response to the changing environmental setting in higher education (Chankseliani et al., 2020; Zapp et al., 2021). Due to constant technological advancements and the broader globalization of education, the educational landscape has been transformed into an ever-changing and competitive medium (Varghese and Mandal, 2020; Li, 2020). A new shift has been created globally in higher education, which has changed education delivery methods, research activities, and traditional university processes (Jackson, 2019; Marcus, 2020; Govindarajan and Srivastava, 2020). In this rapidly evolving environment, universities have to reconsider their conventional education systems, offer new services and programs, and adopt new approaches to remain relevant to external changes and higher education development (Purcell et al., 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020; Govindarajan, 2020). This has resulted in a competitive environment where higher education institutions' survival is determined by adopting new adequate approaches that ensure rapid and continuous adaptation to new environmental changes and conditions (Chankseliani and McCowan, 2021). Choosing the right approach to respond to environmental changes can shape universities' ability to renovate their services and meet market demand to compete in a competitive environment (Barbato et al., 2020). Thus, universities should be able to develop or adopt new approaches to respond adequately to new environmental settings in the higher education field.

The topic of organizational and environmental mutual influence has been researched in different fields and disciplines in the last 40 years and led to traditional organizational adaptation being questioned (Stobierski, 2020; Oyibo and Gabriel, 2020; Duchek, 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Clauss et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021; Walter, 2021; Ruef, 2022). Instead of adapting to changing environmental conditions, organizations can influence or disrupt their environment, which affects the organizational landscape (Shatilo, 2020; Clauss et al., 2021). Co-evolutionary theory emerged to bridge the dichotomy between organizations and their environment, provide a deeper understanding of how organizations can respond to external conditions, and identify factors limiting these organizations to take better actions and co-evolve with their environment (Abatecola, 2020; Kompell et al., 2020). As a result of the altered environmental setting and the growing international competition in higher education, Lebanese universities are challenged with new competitive environment conditions that require an innovative approach to respond to environmental changes (Haidar, 2018; Nauffal and Nader, 2019). The new environmental conditions have shifted Lebanese higher education environment from stable to competitive (Khaddage-Soboh, 2021; Zgheib, 2021).

This research discusses co-evolutionary approach as an innovative and new approach for advancing the higher education field and helping Lebanese universities face external influencing factors. The co-evolutionary approach aims to construct a new view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and identify the factors limiting their abilities to co-evolve with their environment. The research results will benefit Lebanese higher education and academic communities.

1.3 Challenges Facing Higher Education Institutions

Continuous environmental effects on the global higher education setting are challenging universities worldwide's ability to compete and demand transformative changes to their traditional processes, research activities, and offered products and services (Purcell et al., 2019; Abad-Segura et al., 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020).

1. *Globalization.* Higher education's entry into the international free market has affected universities' structural forms and roles in the global higher education environment (Castro, 2019; Alexander et al., 2019). A global strategy is becoming essential for universities to compete globally; however, not all universities can integrate their resources internationally effectively with their local operations and processes (Reichert, 2019; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Tight, 2021).

2. *Rapid change rate.* The higher education field is challenged by rapid development, influencing the ability of universities to renovate their processes and offer new programs and services to meet new educational standards and emerging students' needs (Ehlers and Kellermann, 2019; Jackson, 2019). Universities are having difficulties coping with the pace of changes outside their organizations due to their limited abilities to develop their capabilities, processes, and offerings to adapt to the new norms (Ehlers and Kellermann, 2019; Oke and Fernandes, 2020).

3. *Technological factors.* Technology and digital innovation are becoming the norm in higher education as technology is integrated into teaching and research processes (Kopp et al., 2019). Digital technologies are utilized to innovate the learning and teaching experience and revolutionize research activities (Oke and Fernandes, 2020). Digital accessibility is one of the main capabilities that universities need to operate as a modern university that allows universities to offer remote solutions to international students worldwide (Henriksen et al., 2021). Due to growing global competition, science and technology are considered strategic and competitive resources for

universities, whereas their acquisition and utilization are both essential for universities' competitiveness and sustainability in the global market (Dwivedi et al., 2021;). Digital transformation in higher education is becoming a trend and a benchmark for universities worldwide (Benavides et al., 2020; Abad-Segura et al., 2020).

4. *Global ranking.* The global ranking system has affected universities' market position locally and internationally by presenting gaps between universities, which affects their reputation worldwide (Vidal and Ferreira, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021). Many universities' ranks are decreasing due to their inability to respond to new competitive conditions, which affects their competitiveness among rivals internationally (Vidal and Ferreira, 2020; Adaileh, 2022).

5. *Marketizing of the universities.* Many international universities are focusing on marketing strategies rather than academics to achieve competitiveness (Teo, 2019; Demin, 2019). The focus on image, reputation, and marketing strategies was given the term the 'marketizing of the universities, which made the higher education field competitive and let many universities divert their activities to win in a competitive landscape (Chatterji et al., 2022).

6. *The challenges of alternative education.* Universities are challenged by alternative education means resulting from advanced technology utilization, such as online and distance learning (Dozhdikov, 2020; Fernando, 2020). Distance learning has changed higher education institutions' collaborative research and knowledge production and their spread globally (Milicevic et al., 2021).

7. *Rising costs and shifting funding.* The cost of operating private and public higher education institutions is rising worldwide (Altbach et al., 2019; Verweij and Meerkerk, 2020). Several universities are challenged by decreased public expenditure to cover their essential processes and development expenses (Verweij and Meerkerk, 2020). Public universities would not be able to cover operational and development costs without adequate funding, which can affect their ability

to compete with other universities, especially private institutions (Rosinger et al., 2020; Kelchen et al., 2020).

8. *Rising student expectations.* The job market is becoming more competitive, and the costs of higher education are rising, which extorts additional pressure on universities to meet students' expectations to secure future jobs (Chankseliani, 2021; Ariffin et al., 2022; Tandika and Ndiujye, 2022).

9. *Sustainable research activities.* Many universities are focusing more on teaching practices rather than research activities (Bratianu et al., 2021; Ratten and Usmanij, 2021). Universities are challenged to offer higher education to a more significant number of students efficiently with the required skills and expertise needed in the workplace (Veluri et al., 2022; Alam, 2022; Erlangga et al., 2022). The incapability to perform research and teaching activities is challenging universities' competitiveness internationally, as research and teaching are becoming core functions of a university and valuable sources of knowledge and learning (Veluri et al., 2022; Alam, 2022; Erlangga et al., 2022).

10. *Recruiting the right people.* Universities' staff are responsible for delivering high-quality education, supporting students, developing the university's capabilities, and introducing new processes and activities. For that, universities should be able to attract highly skilled staff to achieve university objectives (Giang et al 2021, Tri et al., 2021). Universities are challenged to attract highly skilled staff in higher education, especially when the university is required to make radical changes to adopt an international strategy and compete globally (Giang et al 2021, Tri et al., 2021; Kant et al., 2021).

Thus, it is evident that global higher education is facing several challenges, influencing universities worldwide. In the following section, the researcher discusses the influences of the altered environmental setting on universities worldwide and in Lebanon in particular.

1.4 Research Relevance and Significance

The relationship between organizations and their environment is a significant topic that has captured the attention and interest of both researchers and practitioners in different fields and disciplines (Aldrich et al., 2020; Stobierski, 2020; Oyibo and Gabriel, 2020; Duchek, 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2020; Aronsson et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021; Walter, 2021). More than ever, environmental conditions are continually changing, making it difficult for organizations to adopt only adaptive responses to altered environmental states, especially in the presence of radical and disruptive changes happening within their environment (Chladek, 2019; Stobierski, 2021; Aronsson et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021; Walter, 2021). Prior studies emphasized an adaptive approach to face rising environmental challenges. Several researchers focused on one of both organization-environmental sides or on an organizational component, agent, or unit solely and then related it to the external environment and vice versa (Knardahl et al., 2019; Oyibo and Gabriel, 2020; Duchek, 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2021; Aronsson et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Although few studies have examined the relationship between organizations and their environments from both ends, they continue to be limited by not exploring the factors and binding mechanisms that affect an organization's internal and external environment (Duchek, 2020; Sima et al., 2020; Peters and Simaens, 2020; Doz et al., 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2021; Aronsson et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021).

Several authors (Sarta et al., 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2021; Aronsson et al., 2021; Walter, 2021; Verhoef et al., 2021) argued that organizations should be able to manage both their internal

and external environments by which organizations should maintain the ability to adapt to external and make necessary development to its core components to sustain their ability to continue their operations and development on the internal side. Likewise, Dewar et al. (2019) considered that a continuous feedback relation exists between organizations and their environment, which should be administered by decreasing the effect of environmental changes, increasing internal influences, or having a mutual influence. Organizational co-evolution is among the emerging research topics adopted to understand better the relationship between organizations and their environment (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021). Instead of adapting to new environmental conditions, co-evolutionary theory provides a new approach to bridge the dichotomy between organizations and their environment, offer a deeper understanding of the mutual influence of organizations and their environment, identify the mechanism that bounds this relationship, and identify the main internal and external factors affecting organizations' fitness, growth and ability to compete with rivals within a particular environment (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021). Co-evolutionary approaches help identify the main mechanisms that bind the relationship between organizations and their environments, the main factors that influence their ability to co-evolve with their environment (Fox, 2020; Robert et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Das et al., 2020; Eliakis et al., 2020). Co-evolutionary theory offers a continual understanding of the organization-environment relationship and continual organizational development to respond to environmental changes (Donaires and Martinelli, 2018; Fuertes et al., 2020; Uchida, 2020). Co-evolutionary theory helps in enhancing more comprehensive strategies,

improving organizational processes, and aiding in the development of new organizational forms and outcomes (Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Uchida, 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Ekonomika, 2020; Elbanna et al., 2020; Aronson, 2021; Ferreira et al., 2020; Dzhengiz, 2020). Co-evolutionary approach can foster innovative outcomes by offering a new perspective of administrating the organization-environment relationship by re-evaluating, re-combining, and integrating different organizational and environmental factors to develop enhanced and new organizational capabilities, processes, forms, outcomes, and dynamics (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021).

Due to its comprehensiveness and need to encompass several factors on the micro and macro level, past co-evolutionary research has studied a limited number of internal and external factors and didn't focus on the mechanisms that bound them together. Prior co-evolutionary research was limited to a few factors and studied the essential organizational components of the co-evolutionary approach, and didn't extend to study the co-evolution of organizations on an industry scale (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021). Past studies have examined various sets of external and internal factors that influence organizations' ability to maintain their fitness; however, they didn't offer a comprehensive approach that encompasses the main co-evolutionary approach components, such as management role, competition, capability building, organizational outcome, and new forms (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021). This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the relationship between

organizations and their environment and investigates the co-evolution of Lebanese universities with their environment. The present research proposes a new comprehensive co-evolutionary framework that encompasses several factors mentioned in prior studies but not integrated into one comprehensive framework, including environmental factors, organizational factors, management role, capability-building process, competitiveness, and outcome (Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Abatecola, 2020; Kompella, 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda 2021). By that, the main influencing factors can be identified, and a new view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and the environment can be constructed (Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Abatecola, 2020; Kompella, 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda 2021).

On the practical side, the present research provides a new approach for universities to manage their interaction with their environment and identify the factors limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Contributions to this research will extend the view of how a university can achieve fitness, sustainability, and competitiveness by adopting a co-evolutionary framework (Jackson, 2019; Moroz, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Lartey, 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Izumi et al. 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al. 2021). This research offers a new strategic approach for university managers, portraying their role in managing organizational-environment relationships in facing external challenges and the development of organizational capabilities through the lens of co-evolutionary theory (Jackson, 2019; Moroz, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Lartey 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Izumi et al. 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al. 2021). The new co-evolutionary framework offers new dynamics and mechanisms inside higher education for better capabilities, methods, and outcomes offered by universities, which will reflect positively on the overall higher education system and future generations in Lebanon (Jackson, 2019; Moroz, 2020; Chen et al.

2020; Lartey 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Izumi et al. 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al 2021). The results of this research can be applied to other universities, educational institutions, and organizations from different fields internationally. The developed co-evolutionary framework can be used as a base for future co-evolutionary approaches that extend its factors and components to increase its comprehensiveness for future understanding of relationship between organization and environment, organizational co-evolution, and offering a link between organizational evolution and revolution. In this regard, co-evolutionary approach will provide Lebanese policymakers with a new perspective on the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environments. As a result, current plans will be adjusted, and flexible policies will be set in order to effectively support local universities and enhance Lebanese higher education system.

1.5 Research Problem

The increasing external factors have transformed the higher education environment into a competitive landscape. The altered environmental conditions have influenced the ability of international universities to stay fit and compete within their environment (Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Cantwell et al., 2022). Higher education's global expansion and the emergence of new technologies have shifted higher education's stable status into a more competitive environment (Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; Cantwell et al., 2022; Orr et al., 2020). Due to this situation, higher education institutions are challenged to respond to external influences adequately, stay fit, and sustain their competitiveness among rivals within their environment (Varghese and Mandal, 2020; Li, 2020; Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Cantwell et al., 2022). Likewise, Lebanese universities are challenged by new environmental conditions (Tarhini et al., 2019; Chedrawi et al., 2019; Harb and Karami-Akkary, 2019; Ghosn-Chelala, 2020; Fawaz and Samaha, 2021). The new environmental setting has shifted the landscape

of Lebanese higher education from a stable to a competitive environment, exerting new pressures on Lebanese universities and affecting their competitiveness and fitness (Abourjeili and Harb, 2020). Several researchers (Saab et al., 2017; Baroudi, 2019; Hassen, 2020) studied the new characteristics of Lebanese higher education system and the challenges that emerged from new altered environmental conditions. However, there is a lack of research that studies the critical limiting factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to respond to new environmental changes adequately. At the same time, other international universities were able to respond to new environmental influences and sustain their competitiveness and position in the higher education field locally and globally. The current setting of Lebanese higher education and the fact that each higher education field has distinct characteristics and conditions provide further evidence that Lebanese universities need a new approach to face and respond adequately to environmental challenges.

1.6 Research Rationale

As mentioned in Section 1.2, organizations' ability to sustain their operations in the global and digital economy is becoming a significant challenge for many universities. Evidence suggests that globalization and technological advancements have transformed the landscape of education worldwide, making it difficult for many universities to cope with new environmental conditions (Skare and Soriano, 2021; Belousova et al., 2021). Several researchers (Varghese and Mandal, 2020; Li, 2020; Cheung et al., 2021; Anthonysamy and Hew, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021) suggested that universities' approach regarding their relationship with their environment shapes their interactions and perception of their environment. The perception-action relation determines how an institution analyzes its environment, its position inside it, and its actions to respond to environmental changes (Xu et al., 2019; Khaw et al., 2020; Mengu and Turk, 2021; Bode, 2022).

The inability to have a clear construct of the relationship between institutions and their environment, respond to external changes and dictate their position, rank, and fitness within their environment (Xu et al., 2019; Khaw et al., 2020; Mengu and Turk, 2021; Bode, 2022). Since each environment is unique and is affected by different external factors, organizations should continuously renew their approaches to understand their surrounding settings better and adequately respond to environmental changes (Fuertes et al., 2020; Duchek, 2020; Sarta et al., 2021; Walter, 2021; Ruef, 2022).

1.7 Research Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions

In this section, the researcher presents the aim of the research, its objectives, and research questions.

1.7.1 Research Aim

The research aims to investigate the challenges affecting Lebanese universities to co-evolve in a competitive environment.

1.7.2 Research Objectives

To pursue the aim of the present research, specific objectives were set, which are:

- To review and evaluate the literature, which leads to the identification of a literature gap.
- To explore the internal and external factors limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment.
- To explore the role of Lebanese universities' management in dealing with the changing environmental conditions.

- To develop a new co-evolutionary theoretical framework that addresses the relationship between universities and their environment.
- To address the implications of applying co-evolutionary theory in higher education.

1.7.3 Research Questions

To answer the research objectives, several sub-questions of this research need to be answered:

1. What is the relationship between universities and their environment?
2. What is the role of management in managing the relationship between universities and their environment?
3. What are the key organizational factors to develop a co-evolutionary framework?
4. What are the main factors limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment?
5. What are the critical factors for applying a co-evolutionary framework at Lebanese universities?

1.8 Summary of Research Methodology

In this section, the researcher discusses the adopted methodology for this research. The discussion of research methodology covers the several methods and techniques adopted in the research design and interpretation of its results (Sileyew et al., 2019). This research investigates the main factors limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. The researcher followed a qualitative method to achieve the aim of the research. The researcher adopted the inductive approach, which enables researchers to use specific observations to build an abstraction or construct an overview of the investigated phenomenon (Creswell and Creswell, 2019). A multiple case study strategy was applied to collect data from multiple resources, ensuring the outcome variety, richness, and reliability (Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021). The data collection for the case study was conducted in cooperation with universities in Lebanese higher

education system. Thirty-nine semi-structured interviews were conducted with managers from twenty-six Lebanese universities to collect data for this research. The data was then analyzed using thematic analysis technique to identify patterns and emerging themes.

1.9 Thesis Outline

This section presents the seven chapters which constitute this thesis.

Chapter 1 introduces the research, presenting the key challenges facing higher education institutions, the research aim, objectives, questions, and contributions. The chapter includes the research problem, research rationale, and summary of the research methodology and concludes with providing thesis outline.

Chapter 2 reviews existing literature on organizations' nature and relationship with their environment, the higher education system, and its emerging challenges. Also, the chapter includes an overview of Lebanese higher education system and the challenges facing Lebanese universities. The chapter includes a literature gap in the existing literature on the investigated topic.

Chapter 3 evaluates the existing organizational theories that study the relationship between organizations and their environment. The chapter illustrates the gaps in the existing theories and proposes a new framework to better comprehend the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and provide a new approach to face emerging challenges.

Chapter 4 discusses the adopted research methodology in this research, describes the research process, and explains methods selection. The chapter includes research design, data access, data collection, and analysis methods.

Chapter 5 reports the key findings from the qualitative collected data. The chapter includes the main factors influencing Lebanese universities' co-evolution with their environment.

Chapter 6 discusses the research findings reported in Chapter 5. In this chapter, the findings of this research are discussed and interpreted separately.

Chapter 7 presents the results of this research, its theoretical, practical contributions, policy implications, and suggestions for future research.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher reviews existing literature on the nature of organizations and their relationships with their environment. The chapter also discusses the current conditions of the higher education system and the nature of the relationship between universities and their environment. The chapter also provides a historical background of Lebanese higher education and presents its new setting. The discussion of empirical literature in this chapter will allow the researcher to identify gaps in existing research and provide a basis for future studies regarding the specific case of Lebanon.

2.2 The Nature of Organizations and the Environments

The present section discusses the nature of organizations, their interaction with their internal and external environments, and the main environmental factors influencing both environments.

2.2.1 The Nature of Organizations

An organization is considered to be a group of several people collaborating for a common goal (Fischer et al., 2020). Hillmann and Guenther (2021) considered that an organization is an assembly of a group of people congregated in a commonplace to contribute their efforts to achieve a specified aim or goal. According to Fuertes et al (2020) organizations are based on the concept of synergy, which allows groups of individuals to do more work than individuals who work alone. Organizations can be categorized as profit or non-profit organizations (Castane and Oliveira, 2020). Coule and Bain (2021) stated that organizations could be corporations, governmental and

non-governmental organizations, political organizations, international organizations, non-profit corporations or charities, and educational institutions. Laihonen and Huhtamaki (2020) considered that organizations could operate in the public and private sectors, performing public duties and developing commercial market activities. Researchers considered that organizations could not be separated from their environment and resemblance to its conditions. Shirokova et al. (2020) believed that organizations exist within environments that provide necessary resources, markets, opportunities, threats, or impose organizational limitations. Organizations are not static entities but continuously interact with several factors and influences imposed by their environment (Duchek, 2020; Valeri, 2021). Stobierski (2020) argued that each organizational environment has distinct characteristics, determines the organization's operations, and distinguishes an organization from other organizations.

Similarly, Hofmann and Jaeger-Erben (2020) believed that organizations are open systems constantly influenced by their external environment. Walter (2021) suggested that the organizational environment assembles different factors influencing organizations, that can shape organizational activities and operations. Likewise, De Medeiros et al (2022) argued that the organizational environment sets legal, technological, socio-cultural, and other organizational limitations. Thus, the environment of an organization influences its work dynamics and type of operations. Section 2.2.2 will better discuss the nature of the organizational environment to provide a better understanding of the relationship between organizations and their environment.

2.2.2 The Nature of Organization's Environment

Organizational environment refers to the set of organizations that have the same function, type, or industry with respect to a particular organization (Oyibo and Gabriel, 2020). Organizational environments comprise internal and external organizational environments (Shatilo, 2020).

Organizational internal environment consists of the main organizational factors that shape an organization's core, while external factors include external influences exerted from other altered environment settings or organizations from the same environment (Shatilo, 2020). Satyendra (2020) believed that the internal environment includes internal organizational components of a firm. According to Flodin and Lind (2020) the internal environment of an organization comprises its structure, human resources, value system or organization philosophy, and physical resources. Flodin and Jacobson et al. (2022) considered that organizations' mission and objectives, culture, financial and marketing resources, brand image, and technical capabilities belong to organizations' internal environment.

On the other hand, Menglong (2020) considered that the external environment could relate to an organization's general environment, including all external factors influencing an organization's capabilities, fitness, and competitiveness. Matovic (2020) believed that the external environment includes political factors, which refer to the extent of government interference in the economy and the influence of organizations within a specific industry. Economic factors can affect conditions that shift supply and demand in a particular economy, while social factors relate to changes in the socio-cultural market environment (Matovic, 2020; Koziol-Nadolna and Beyer, 2021). Technological factors shape innovation and development progress in a market or industry, speed up processes, or even help create new markets (Shabalov et al., 2021; Matovic, 2020; Yang and Gu, 2021). Environmental factors relate to ecological and environmental factors, which can affect an organization's ability to operate and meet consumer demands, while legal factors dictate the current legal restrictions within a given country (Matovic, 2020).

Therefore, organizations operate within both internal and external environments. Each environment has its own influencing factors and potential impact on the organization. However,

despite extensive literature on studying organizations' internal and external environments, there is a lack of investigation of the factors that administer this relation, whether it is managerial, organizational factors, or a combination of both. Although, in recent research, external and internal factors were investigated, with the advancement of technology and the open markets, new influencing factors should be added to study organizations' limiting factors comprehensively. The current relationship between organizations and their environment will be elaborated in Section 2.2.3.

2.2.3 Organization-Environment Relationship

Several authors (Sarta et al., 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2020; Aronsson et al., 2021; Walter, 2021) argued that organizations should be capable of managing both their internal and external environments to adapt to external changes as well as internal to make necessary development to its core components to sustain their ability to continue their operations and development. Kumar (2019) suggested that the internal environment of an organization is considered controllable, in contrast to the external organizational environment, which is characterized by ambiguity, uncertainty, and velocity, and since organizations are unable to have control over their external environment, it is difficult to be fully controlled. Likewise, Dewar et al. (2019) considered that there is a continuous feedback relation between organizations and the environment, which should be administered by decreasing or increasing the effect of environmental changes, internal influences, or mutual influences. Aronsson et al. (2021) stated that organizational environments are subject to frequent changes, for that, organizations should be able to respond adequately to relevant environmental changes. Similarly, Hillmann and Guenther (2021) considered that each organization should develop its capabilities and have a suitable response system to face environmental challenges. Hanelt et al. (2021) argued that organizational environment research

became important when studying organizations, especially under altered environmental conditions.

Scholars (Hillmann and Guenther, 2021; Lee et al., 2022; Zhou, 2022) considered that globalization and technological advancement are the main factors altering the conditions of organizations' environments. Globalization and other external factors dramatically affect organizations' operations, products, and offered value (Sima et al., 2020). Globalization and technological advancement have changed the nature of organizational environments, impacting how organizations operate and respond to new environmental changes (Teece, 2020; Majeed et al., 2022). Doz et al. (2020) considered that globalization had expanded narrow environments into broader and more diverse markets. According to Popkova et al. (2022) globalization has embraced international integration strategies, integrating environments into a global context. Other researchers (Sarta et al., 2020; Gupta, 2022) suggested that as organizations became interdependent, several trade barriers were loosened, which allowed new rivals to enter and operate in different environments; the reason is that organizations have to engage with local and new external rivals from different environments, which can disrupt or alter the environmental conditions of a particular environment. Ever-increasing competition and unbridled globalization are forcing organizations to provide better solutions and meet customer needs, especially through technological assistance (Vilhjalmsson and Wikman, 2021; Hoang, 2021). The need for global dynamism is increasing as organizational environment conditions change, forcing organizations to adapt or move to an international approach to stay competitive (Do et al., 2022). In addition, technological advancement and new technological forms have increased organizational challenges and required organizations to adopt new ways to deal with altering external conditions and demands for new capabilities and performance (Mikalef et al., 2021).

Several authors (Dwivedi et al., 2020; Dzwigol, 2020 Verhoef et al., 2021) suggested that technological advancements have changed the conditions of different environments. Technological advancements that exist outside an organization and are not typically fully acquired or used by many organizations can limit organizations' ability to adapt or limit their ability to offer higher value or their international integration capability (Dwivedi et al., 2020; Dzwigol, 2020 Verhoef et al., 2021). In addition, new technologies have affected an organization's ability to engage or be a part of an environment or an industry (Dwivedi et al., 2020; Dzwigol, 2020 Verhoef et al., 2021).

Several authors (Ahlstrom et al., 2020; Buchholz et al., 2020; Benito et al., 2022) agreed that the new setting imposed by globalization and technology, and other external forces created altered organizational environment characteristics and helped the development of new forms of organization and offerings. Many organizations could capitalize on the new technologies and features the global environment can offer (Ahlstrom et al., 2020; Buchholz et al., 2020; Benito et al., 2022). The new organizational forms act as additional global players, increasing global landscape competitiveness (Smailhodzic and Soltanifar, 2021; Moccia et al., 2020). In a competitive environment, firms are renovated by the flow and need to develop new competencies to maintain their competitiveness (McDonald et al., 2021; Ferreira, J. and Coelho, 2020). As organizations are becoming digitalized, they face a growing imperative to reinvent themselves, move quicker, adapt more rapidly, promote accelerated learning, and embrace a dynamic culture within their organizations (Verhoef et al., 2020; Fonseca and Picoto, 2020; Mosteanu, 2020). However, leading companies are moving beyond the design process and are developing better and new organizations for the future or even offering a new form in the market (Peter et al., 2020). Designing organizations of the future may be difficult for some organizations due to the nature of

the processes an organization should go through to reach this state; however, designing organizations of the future is a continuous and never-ending process (Peter et al., 2020; Witell et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021). Organizations that rise to the challenge need to adopt a new way to deal with altering external conditions and demands for new capabilities and performance (Hidma et al., 2020).

In contrast to the past, organizations have typically been built for efficiency and effectiveness; however, in competitive environments, it is not enough to achieve efficiency and effectiveness to operate in an ever-changing environment (Peter et al., 2020). Instead, organizations need to be designed for speed, agility, and adaptability to compete with other organizations in a globally competitive environment (Munteanu et al., 2020; Walter, 2021). Thus, new factors should be investigated to develop new approaches to face organizational environmental changes and challenges.

2.3 Higher Education Institutions

In this section, the researcher provides an overview of the nature of universities and their relation to the higher education environment. This section addresses the main environmental factors affecting higher education worldwide: globalization, technology, e-learning, and the rise of new educational forms.

2.3.1 The Nature of Higher Education Institutions

Universities are organizations that operate in a diverse and ever-changing environment that could directly or indirectly influence their operations, role, and competitiveness (Zalite and Zvirbule, 2020; Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020). The higher education environment is considered the

main source of various resources, which higher education institutions use as input in their operations and processes, including information, financial, essential material, and resources (Vykydal et al., 2020; Geng and Zhao, 2020). Tomlinson (2018) considered that environments could be a source of higher education institutions' consumers of the institutions' outputs, such as academic degrees and other educational services. Other scholars (Hinds, 2019; Jahnke and Liebscher, 2020; Risen and Goldstei, 2021) believed that the higher education environment allows higher education institutions to attract students and human resources, like staff or faculty members. Risen and Goldstein (2021) suggested that the nature and extent of interactions of higher education institutions with their environment determine whether they adopt an open or closed system. Thus, higher education institutions and environments are reciprocally interdependent and bound by continuous mutual interaction.

Several scholars (Recio and Colella, 2020; Jandric et al., 2020; Bergan et al., 2020) believed that the external pressures exerted by the higher education environments have permeated virtually all facets of academic and non-academic work, resulting in many new roles, activities, and responsibilities for administrators, staff, and faculty. External pressures from the higher education environment require redesigning departmental, college, and unit assignments and reporting relationships (Recio and Colella, 2020; Jandric et al., 2020; Bergan et al., 2020). Higher education operates as any organization operates within internal and external environment (Cox, 2021). Chankseliani et al. (2021) considered that higher education's general environment consists of several factors influencing higher institutions' operations. Other scholars (Alareeni et al., 2021; Bin et al., 2020) considered that higher education's external environment consists of an assembly of organizations that may directly affect higher education institutions' operations and ability to compete. Valk and Kratovits (2021) considered that higher education leaders must be able to

manage complex relationships among other external entities and acknowledge dynamic interactions with other institutions. For a better understating of the higher education institutions' relationship with their environment, the following section discusses the nature of the higher education system.

2.3.2 The Setting of Higher Education System

Degang (2021) considered that universities face numerous challenges to survive, including competitiveness. As higher education institutions face global challenges, they need to adapt their internal and external resources and capabilities to operate and compete in a highly turbulent and uncertain environment (Chankseliani et al., 2020; Fumasoli, 2021). Lee and Han (2021) believed that the higher education landscape is changing and becoming more competitive, especially with increased educational institutions and new forms of education. The openness of global higher education markets, along with technological development, has increased the influence of new external rivals, as well as the rise of new forms of education, which makes the higher education landscape competitive (Tully and Sidin, 2019; Zapp et al., 2021; Degang, 2021).

2.3.2.1 Globalization

Higher education is witnessing the rise of private international universities and student mobility as education demand grows (Beall, 2020). It was noted by Chankseliani et al. (2021) that knowledge is regarded as a strategic asset used by firms in order to compete in the knowledge economy. According to Kaur (2020) competition between different hierarchical and unequal international universities is becoming the norm in higher education and determining their international rank. In addition, Zapp and Lerch (2020) concluded that higher education competition could take many

forms and take place locally, regionally, and internationally. Other researchers (Salmi, 2020; Bergan et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020) outlined that global higher education today faces fierce global rivalry, affecting local higher education to compete or enter new markets.

Similarly, other researchers (Garcia-Morales et al., 2020; Mitchell et al., 2020; Williamson, 2021) considered that international universities need to adapt or develop new models for teaching, generating valuable contributions, learning, and integrating them with new technologies. Zajda and Rust (2020) proposed that the new higher education landscape demands higher quality standards and advanced technological tools to compete and provide better outcomes. University capabilities should be re-innovated to meet global competition and guarantee higher education levels (Mathivanan et al., 2020; Czerniewicz, 2020). In addition, the decline in public financial support and rise in operations costs have forced global universities to explore new means to increase access and grow additional learning and revenue opportunities in the global market to cover their overheads and main financial flexibility (Bolton and Hubble, 2021; Komljenovic, 2020). Govindarajan and Srivastava (2020) argued that universities worldwide are swiftly leaving traditional on-campus teaching and entering a virtual education model environment, forcing them to rethink their mission and goals.

2.3.2.2 Technology

Technology has aided the higher education sector, making global higher education more competitive and uncertain (Teras et al., 2020; Jilke, 2021). The new higher education system conditions pressure higher education institutions to develop or acquire new technologies to help them become more flexible, adaptive, and able to compete (Bergan and Matei, 2020; Rapanta et al., 2020). Effective integration of new technologies can enhance organizational capabilities,

reduce costs, and grow and expand their market share, decreasing organizational vulnerability and enhancing adaptability (Obrenovic et al., 2020). Muller and Mildenerger (2021) asserted that new technologies entail enormous acquisition costs associated with reduced regression risk. Universities' leaders have difficulty predicting how to control and utilize new technologies that can affect their abilities and disrupt the higher education field (Scully et al., 2021). International competition requires universities to have access to advanced technological capabilities to compete with other universities worldwide (Farrell and Sugrue, 2021).

2.3.2.3 E-Learning and New Forms

Online and distance learning were introduced as new forms of teaching in the global market (Gourlay et al., 2021). Historically, universities offered a passive experience for the learner; however, e-learning requires building skills that can be usefully applied (Borup et al., 2020; Rios et al., 2021). However, students request a degree that provides skills needed for employment more than education (Rios et al., 2021). The changing preference of students for education delivery has allowed new ways and techniques to emerge in the global higher education landscape (Rakowski, 2020; Miranda et al., 2020). Universities started initiating new forms of delivering education and updating their programs to offer flexible programs to local and international students using new technologies (Ramírez-Montoya et al., 2021). New educational forms, whether e-learning or distance learning, offer additional educational opportunities to international learners who prefer or need alternative education methods (Valverde-Berrocoso et al., 2020). E-learning embraces the shift to virtual learning and represents the future of borderless global education (Govindarajan and Srivastava, 2020). Due to the alleviated growth of online education provision and disruption in the

field, universities face new pressures, which require universities to make necessary changes to respond to these changes (Morris et al., 2020; Abel-Jr, 2020).

2.4 Lebanese Higher Education

In this section, the researcher provides a historical background of Lebanese higher education system.

2.4.1 Overview of Lebanese Higher Education

Lebanese higher education sector is considered the oldest higher education sector in the Middle East region (Nauffal, 2019; Mekdach, 2020; AUB, 2022). The first Lebanese educational institution was established in 1866 (Nauffal, 2019; Mekdach, 2020). The first institution then became the American University in Beirut (Mekdach, 2020; AUB, 2022). Lebanese higher education field consists of private universities and one public university founded in 1951 (UL, 2020). Private Lebanese universities operate mainly in Lebanon and are recognized by Lebanese government. The number of private universities since the 1990s has increased, expanding Lebanese higher education system (USAID, 2020).

According to Antoun et al. (2022) Lebanon was considered an education hub among other regional countries besides its long educational history in the Middle East. Lebanese universities attract international students from different countries international and regional countries (Hassen, 2020). Arabic is the country's spoken language (MEHE, 2023). Universities in Lebanon use English and French as the main teaching languages, with a few universities offering Arabic for certain programs (MEHE, 2023). Each university freely chooses a language, but English is the most used language, and many universities that use French as the main teaching language are converting it

into English (USAID, 2020; MEHE, 2023). Lebanese universities follow the American semester-based course completion system. Depending on the year of education, students can be classified into three categories: junior level, sophomore level, and senior students. The academic year consists of two main semesters: one in Fall, the second in Spring, and a third shorter summer semester (AACARO, 2020).

Lebanese constitution grants freedom for Lebanese universities to improve and develop new programs, processes, services, and offerings (MEHE, 2023). In Lebanon, tertiary education has two parts; the first is tertiary vocational and higher education, and the second is general or non-vocational education (AACARO, 2020; MEHE, 2023). Lebanese education system, mainly tertiary, includes technical and vocational institutions. Lebanon has only one public university and fifty private higher education institutions (MEHE, 2023; LBHE-Plan, 2023). Lebanese Ministry of Higher Education outlined in its Higher Education Plan 2023-2027 that in Lebanon, thirty-six higher institutions are considered universities, nine are considered universities-colleges, three are considered universities for theological studies, and two other licensed institutions that didn't operate yet, in Lebanon (MEHE, 2023; LBHE-Plan, 2023).

In Lebanon, a 'Directorate-General for Higher Education' was developed in 2002 to organize and manage private education's operations, outcomes, and processes (MEHE, 2023). On the contrary, the 'Directorate General of Technical and Vocational Education' is responsible for organizing the operations of Lebanese technical institutions and vocational organizations (MEHE, 2023). Lebanese higher education institutions are classified into three types: universities, college colleges, and higher vocational institutions (MEHE, 2023). A higher education institution with a minimum of three schools and the ability to offer a minimum of nine bachelor's degree majors is considered a university; however, any higher education institution with one or two academic fields is

considered a college in Lebanon. A higher institution specializing in at least one technical field or more or teaching middle cadres is considered a higher vocational institute. In Lebanon, universities have the ability and legitimacy to teach, conduct research, and do community services (Saab et al., 2017; MEHE, 2023). Lebanese higher education system grants the right to undergo such activities (Mershad, 2020; MEHE, 2023). In addition, Lebanese government adopts indirect expenditures, such as educational allowances, to cover education tuition for public employees' children (Baroudi, 2019; Mershad, 2020). Lebanese private university is responsible for covering its expenditures and is expected to have its own budget, as there is no public funding from the government (Baroudi, 2019). Universities depend on their capital without government spending or benefits (Baroudi, 2019). Lebanese universities do not follow a standard model for their governance (MERIC, 2019). Each university has its own model for governing its operations. Lebanese public university is administered by a council that constitutes the president and deans elected by the minister's council (MERIC, 2019).

On the other hand, the board of trustees governs private universities, which can be the universities' stakeholders or owners, who can elect the university's deans and their president. The authoritative power of the private university in Lebanon is in the hands of its university's council (MERIC, 2019). The private Lebanese universities sector has more enrolled students than the public sector (MEHE, 2023). Lebanon participates in many international agreements and memberships, such as Tempus, Erasmus projects, EU (FP6, FP7) USAID, CEDRE program, and others (MERIC, 2019; USAID, 2020). In the following section, the researcher reviewed the characteristics of Lebanese Higher education.

2.4.2 The Role of Lebanese Universities Managers

Lebanese university managers share similar roles with managers from different organizations. Lebanese university management teams are responsible for administering the university's everyday tasks, coordinating, organizing, setting plans, and controlling internal processes and activities happening inside the university (Khattab, 2019; Mekdach, 2020; Al-Khoury and Khatib 2020; Al Jardali et al., 2021). In addition, the university manager's role in Lebanon is focused internally and is limited to the external environment or surroundings (Ballatore et al., 2021; Khalil, 2020). In Lebanon, a university manager may represent the university, collaborate with external parties, or prepare for external social or academic events (Khattab, 2019; Mekdach, 2020; Khalil, 2020). Lebanese university managers decide future courses of action, adjust the university's plan and objectives, and coordinate with staff members, academics, and students (Mershad et al., 2019; Khattab, 2019; Al-Khoury and Khatib, 2020; Mekdach, 2020). Lebanese managers are considered the contact point between Lebanese Ministry of Education and the university which the manager represents (Khattab, 2019; Sadq et al., 2020; Mekdach, 2020; Khaddage-Soboh et al., 2021). Lebanese managers work with and through the university's academics and coordinate with universities' faculties and departments to improve and enhance the teaching and research process and ensure high-standard outcomes (Mershad et al., 2019; Khattab, 2019; Sadq et al., 2020; Mekdach, 2020) The typical manager at a Lebanese university is responsible for the university's financial matters, tangible and non-tangible assets, and human resources (Mekdach, 2020; Sadq et al., 2020; Khaddage-Soboh et al., 2021).

2.4.3 The Setting of Lebanese Higher Education

Lebanese higher education sector is considered an advanced sector with a good reputation in the region and worldwide; however, it is losing its prominence within its surroundings and competitiveness (Abourjeili and Harb, 2020). According to Chedrawi (2019) the landscape of Lebanese higher education is dramatically changing and becoming competitive. Haidar (2021) believed that Lebanese higher education field operates within the international higher education system and is similarly affected by altered conditions and rapid developments in higher education worldwide. Mershad et al (2020) considered that the new environmental changes have directly affected how Lebanese universities operate, rank, and interact with higher education institutions (Ballatore et al., 2021). Similarly, Sadq et al. (2019) argued that Lebanese higher education institutions face new pressures in implementing effective measures and finding their way in a changing landscape. With open markets and globalization, Lebanese higher education system has become very competitive (Mackoul, 2019; Mershad et al., 2020). The new competitive conditions have intensified competition between Lebanese higher education institutions (Mackoul, 2019). The competition between Lebanese universities is considered a significant challenge that should be understood since it affects the university's strategies, position, and offered value (Sadq et al., 2019; Tarhini et al., 2020; Haider, 2021). However, Lebanese higher education environment has changed from a stable to a competitive environment, limiting Lebanese universities' ability to achieve sustainability in their environments (Nauffal, 2019; Abourjeili and Harb, 2020; Haider et al., 2021). Thus, competition between Lebanese universities is becoming fierce to provide a better offering and capture a new niche in Lebanese market (Ballatore et al., 2021). As Tarhini et al (2019) considered that technological advancement and use by international universities have disrupted the global education landscape and Lebanese higher education institutions.

Additionally, Sritharan (2020) considered that the utilization of technology by major international universities disrupted Lebanese market by offering online degrees and distance learning methods. Assaf and Nehmeh (2022) suggested that online learning was able to enter Lebanese market and influence traditional campus education. According to Abourjeili and Harb (2020) distance learning can compete with existing Lebanese universities and add new players to Lebanese market. Distance learning methods allow students to gain new degrees not offered by Lebanese universities (Abourjeili and Harb, 2020). Due to altered environmental conditions, Lebanese higher education institutions' ranking has lowered internationally (Zgheib et al., 2019). International students at Lebanese universities have decreased in the last few years (Gajderowicz, and Jakubowski, 2022). In addition, Khaddage et al (2020) concluded that local Lebanese students are traveling to other countries, offering higher programs that can meet market demands and future trends. Lebanese higher education institutions' survival depends entirely on their ability to retain and increase the number of enrolled students, as it is essential for continuity with a higher standard of education (Khaddage et al., 2020; Younis e al., 2021). Several researchers (Mershad et al., 2019; Abourjeili and Harb, 2020; Khaddage et al., 2020; Younis e al., 2021) agreed that the current Lebanese higher education status needs new strategies, and a view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment should be developed. Likewise, Lebanese universities are affected by several external influences in the international higher education landscape (Mershad et al., 2019; Hamze, 2020; Khaddage et al., 2020; Younis e al., 2021). Existing literature lacks research investigating the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and offers a comprehensive approach that helps identify the main factors limiting Lebanese higher education institutions co-evolve with their environment.

2.5 Literature Gap

After reviewing relevant research on the relationship between organizations and their environment, the researcher identified that there is a lack of investigation of the factors affecting the relationship between organizations and their environment on the micro and macro levels (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2021). Past research studied a limited number of internal and external factors and didn't provide a comprehensive overview of the relationship between organizations and their environments. Despite their main aim to investigate internal and external factors, several researchers (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021) adopted co-evolutionary approach in their research; however, their research was limited by investigating a limited number of factors and disregarding essential organizational components of co-evolutionary approach. Moreover, previous studies have not extended the study of organizational co-evolution on an industrial scale (Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020). Few studies have examined various sets of external and internal factors that influence organizations' ability to maintain their fitness, competitiveness, and ability to co-evolve with their environment; however, they did not offer a comprehensive approach that encompasses the main co-evolutionary approach components, such as management role, competition, capability building, and new organizational outcome and forms (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021).

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no research has investigated these factors simultaneously in the context of co-evolutionary approach. Thus, the current understanding of the

relationship between organizations and their environments and the factors limiting their ability to co-evolve is still quite limited.

Moreover, limited number of studies focused on the management role in administrating the relationship between organizations and their environments and co-evolutionary process adoption. Several authors (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021; Kaipainen, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020) considered that prior studies did not integrate management roles and capabilities and emphasized future research on management roles and capabilities, which is the midpoint and link between internal and external organizational environments (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). Managerial roles should extend from the internal organizational functions to the external environment (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). This includes managing or organizing the interrelated processes between organizations and their environments (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). Management can thus act as a managing force for the internal and external organizational environment, an integral part of organizations' co-evolution processes, and a leading force for change (Kaipainen, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020). The study of management's roles and capabilities was disregarded from past research when examining the relationship between an organization and its environment, providing a limited understanding of management's role in the organization-environment relationship and its potential to make better decisions and future development (Stewart, 2019; Khattak and Shah, 2020; Harsch and Festing, 2020; Walter, 2021; Gomes et al., 2022). In addition, past studies didn't include management's role in adopting new approaches and their implementation inside an organization (Stewart, 2019; Khattak and Shah, 2020; Harsch and Festing, 2020).

While there has been considerable research into the relationship between organizations and their environments, few studies have investigated the relationship between universities and their environments and the factors affecting this relationship (Reichert, 2019; Abuhassna et al., 2020; Garcia-Morales et al., 2021; Turnbull et al., 2021; Rapanta et al., 2021; Oliveira et al., 2021; Neuwirth et al., 2021). There is a need for extensive studies that explore how universities adapt and interact with their environment and the main factors that limit universities' ability to interact with their environment, particularly on an industrial level (Turnbull et al., 2021; Rapanta et al., 2021; Oliveira et al., 2021; Neuwirth et al., 2021). Research on an industrial level can provide a better construct of the overall industry's situation and each organization's position within a specific sector or field (Farquhar et al., 2020; Wut, 2021; Tortorella et al., 2020; Sedyastuti et al., 2021). Moreover, there is a need to explore new factors, especially in higher education, since environments are continuously changing (Reichert, 2019; Abuhassna et al., 2020; García-Morales et al., 2021; Turnbull et al., 2021; Rapanta et al., 2021; Oliveira et al., 2021; Neuwirth et al., 2021). Furthermore, despite the existing studies in the literature relating to the relationship between organizations and their environments, there is limited research conducted in countries outside the Western Hemisphere. There have been relatively few studies on this topic in the Middle East region, specifically Lebanon. Several researchers (Mershad et al., 2019; Tarhini et al., 2020; Ballatore et al., 2021; Assaf and Nehmeh, 2022) agreed that the current Lebanese higher education status needs new strategies and a view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment should be developed.

In response to the deficiencies mentioned above, this study provides a new construct of the relationship between universities and their environment and identifies the factors influencing universities to be involved in their environment in Lebanon.

2.6 Conclusion

To better understand the relationship between universities and their environments, the research focused on existing literature that studies the relationship between organizations and their environments. Higher education institutions as organizations operate within environments bounded by continuous interaction. The literature shows how the higher education landscape has become competitive due to altered environmental conditions, mainly globalization, technological advancement, and the emergence of new international learning methods and forms offered by different higher education institutions. The literature review includes a historical background of Lebanese higher education sector and its current setting. Referring to the academic research discussed in this chapter, the researcher identified and presented several gaps in Section 2.5. The following chapter reviews existing organizational theories and frameworks investigating the relationship between organizations and their environment to develop a comprehensive framework for the present research.

Chapter Three: Theoretical Framework Development

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher reviews additional literature based on the need to understand better the relationship between organizations and their environment presented in Chapter 2. The researcher reviewed existing organizational theories, frameworks, and literature gap to develop a comprehensive theoretical framework.

3.2 Organizational Theories Review

In this section, the researcher discusses the origins and development of organizational theories, organizational and environmental analysis, postmodern co-evolutionary theories.

3.2.1 Organizational Analysis Theories

In the early 1900s, organizational science emerged in response to modern life's rules and laws (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). Early research focused on organizational legitimacy and governance (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). Organizations were considered institutions pursuing specific goals and having relatively formal social structures (Isomura, 2020). According to Fligstein (2020) organizational theory explains how organizations operate to better understand and appreciate organizations as entities. Scott and Davis (2017) argued that organizational theory relates to interconnected concepts that describe organizational members' and groups' behavior when performing joint tasks to achieve a common goal. Post et al. (2020) believed that organizational theory draws on different knowledge bodies and disciplines. Classical, neoclassical,

contingency, and hierarchical structures are considered organizational theories (Bueno, 2021; Valeri, 2021). Organizational theory variations are built on multiple contemporary and post-modern views (Bueno, 2021; Valeri, 2021). According to Valeri (2021) organizations were perceived to be closed systems, separated and operate independently of their environment through the lens of traditional theories. Clementino and Perkins (2020) considered that several researchers had adopted an open-system view of organizations, acknowledging that conventional theory had neglected to incorporate many environmental factors influencing organizations' operations. Rational, natural, and open system approaches are considered key theoretical perspectives on organizations in which the historical development and nature of an organization can be evaluated (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018; Alikulov and Rizaev et al., 2020; Maclean et al., 2021).

3.2.1.1 Rational Systems Theories

Rational systems theory emphasizes the formalization and specificity of organizations' goals, which are essential aspects of an organization from the theory's point of view (Fligstein, 2021). Moreover, rational system theory considers that actions inside an organization are essential to studying rationality inside an organization. According to Hatch (2018) several researchers have invested significant time in analyzing internal activities, organizational structure, and its effect on its members, which led to the development of different schools of thought that consider organizations rational systems. These schools include scientific management, administrative, decision-making, and bureaucracy theories.

Scientific management. Frederick Taylor founded scientific management theory in 1911 (Scott and Davis, 2017; Cappelli, 2020). Frederick Taylor aimed to measure and develop a more effective work process through systematic frameworks (Bulturbayevich and Ikromjonovich, 2021). From his research at Bethlehem Steel, Taylor concluded that managerial roles are critical to increasing

production productivity (Scott and Davis, 2017; Nicotera, 2019; Braverman, 2020). Scientific management theory highlights the importance of cooperation between management and workers inside organizations to ensure that workers follow existing procedures and share work and responsibilities (Braverman, 2020).

Administrative theory. In contrast to scientific management theory, the administrative theory focuses on studying organizations structurally (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018; Edwards, 2018; Bacud, 2020). From this view, Fayol suggested that it is better to make formal procedural changes from the top down since a larger work structure can be affected by individual task-level changes (Mcgrath and Bates, 2017; Scott and Davis, 2018; Lawrence, 2021). Fayol's theory emphasizes an organization's coordination and specialization (Mcgrath and Bates, 2017; Edwards, 2018). Similar to scientific management, administrative theory focuses on studying the structured elements of an organization to maximize productivity (Dumez, 2018; Bacud, 2020).

Decision-making theory. Unlike administrative theory, decision-making theory focuses on social-psychological analysis (Scott and Davis, 2017). Herbert Simon founded decision-making theory in 1947, which is considered a rational system theory approach that reflects organizations' structural level (Hatch, 2018; Julmi, 2019; Altman, 2020). However, Simon criticized the scientific management theory's principles regarding economic rationality (Altman, 2020). Simon argued that employees typically pursue their self-interest, which may be misguided, as well as their potential choices (Scott and Davis, 2017; Avendano Perez et al., 2020). In his theory, Simon suggested that organizations simplify choices by setting priorities and premises (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). Simon considered that decision-making had broadened the perception of how employees make choices by adjusting for internal challenges and knowledge gaps (Scott and Davis, 2017; Avendano Perez et al., 2020).

Bureaucracy Theory. According to Barbosa et al. (2021) the rational organizational view was developed based on Max Weber's analysis of legitimate rational authority and ideal bureaucratic studies. Max Weber noted that there are three primary forms of authority: conventional authority, inspirational authority based on the assumed qualities of the individual, and legitimate logical authority based on written laws and procedures (Scott and Davis, 2017; Barbosa et al., 2021). Weber suggested that each form of authority is related to a specific administrative structure (Scott and Davis, 2017). Weber defined the ideal type of authority as a representation that reflects distinct features of a particular form, which is rare in society (Dash and Padhi, 2020; Robinson, 2020). Weber considered that the collection of rules and regulations, the hierarchy with orderly authority and the management of turnover, the written charter and record of operational activities, and effective management, which can teach other organizational members and is founded on an instructive set of guidelines, constitute an ideal bureaucratic type (Yilmaz and Telsac, 2021). The rational system approach relies on the formality of the organization and the common goal or interests of the organization's members. However, the rational system theory was criticized by different researchers, who opposed the assumptions of this theory regarding activities inside organizations (Hatch, 2018; Scott and Davis, 2017).

3.2.1.2 Natural Systems Theories

The naturalists challenged the increasingly formal system of rational institutions, where rationalists did not dispute the presence of the structures but challenged whether the system was essential to the organization's members (Scott and Davis, 2017). Human relations school, Cooperative System, and Institutional approaches are considered the three main approaches to natural systems (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018).

Human Relations School. Human relations theory is a natural system approach to studying organizations at the individual level. Under the human relations theory lens, organizational individuals' behavior in organizations is influenced by the social context (Tolibovna, 2020). In 1924, Mayo developed human relations theory from his organizational research at the Hawthorne plant (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). Similar to scientific management theory, human relations theory emphasizes psychological analysis (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). However, unlike science management theory, human relations theory relies on informal factors that impact organizations' productivity (Omolawal, 2021). Through the view of human relations theory, individuals' behavior inside the organization is influenced by the ideology adopted by the organization (Omolawal, 2021).

Cooperative system. The theory of cooperative systems adopts a natural system perspective, which acknowledges the essential informal elements that organizations need to exist (Isomura, 2020). In 1938, Barnard suggested that organizations exist when individuals can interact with each other, be prepared to make contributions and pursue a shared goal (Scott and Davis, 2017; Isomura, 2020). Barnard (1938) argued that an organization should have distinct characteristics and embrace communication among workers to increase their willingness to participate in a shared interest (Scott and Davis, 2017). According to Barnard, employees should be continually induced to contribute more indirectly (Valentinov and Roth, 2021). Barnard believed that an organization's informal means are essential to understanding better how it functions (Hatch, 2018).

Institutional Approach. Scott and Davis (2017) argued that Selznick took a more complex perspective and argued that organizations should be evaluated or analyzed as a whole. According to Scott and Davis (2017) in many cases, rationalists believe that organizations exist purposefully to achieve specific goals; however, Selznick agreed with the rationalist interpretation of the formal

system. In 1949, Selznick suggested that organizations should consider the unwritten and less formal frameworks in real-world organizations (Scott and Davis, 2017). Selznick believed that organizations are tools with a life of their own (Kraatz and Block, 2017; Ekberg, 2017; Radoynovska, 2020). According to Ekberg (2017) Selznick believed that organizational structure is an adaptive organism formed according to organizational members' characteristics, commitment, and external influences.

3.2.1.3 Open Systems Theories

The open systems approach emerged in the 1960s to provide a new explanation of the interrelationship between organizations and their environment (Scott and Davis, 2017). In the lens of open system theory, organizations are considered a collection of interdependent flows and processes connecting changing alliances of actors embedded in broader material resources and organizational environments (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). The open system approach considers that organizations become open systems when they are not confined to their physical walls or structures (Weber and Waeger, 2017; Bedner and Wech, 2020). Many external influences were highlighted by the open system approach, especially the operations or processes of an organization (Weber and Waeger, 2017; Bedner and Wech, 2020). Open systems focus on the importance of having total interdependence between organizations and their external environment (Hinings and Greenwood, 2017). The open system approach suggests that an organization's information, technologies, and regulatory input should depend on its environment (Turner and Baker, 2019).

System Design theory. Systems design theory views organizations as open social systems interacting with their environment for survival (Wang et al., 2019). Systems design theory defines

organizational behavior by comparing iterative input, transformation, output, and feedback cycles between the organization and its external environment (Barile et al., 2018). Organizations obtain resources or input from their environment, which are processed internally and released into the environment as an output (Barile et al., 2018). Scot and Davis (2017) suggested that equilibrium can be restored to the environment by this process, which then receives feedback to ensure equilibrium is restored.

Contingency theory. Contingency theory adopts an open-rational systems perspective (Hatch, 2018). However, bounded rationality emphasizes the importance of analyzing the social-psychological level, while contingency theory focuses on analyzing the structural level of an organization (Otenyo, 2018). Contingency theory relates to the influence of the external world on the rational behavior of organizations, where the external environment of an organization can provide opportunities or constraints (Abba et al., 2018). In 1967, Lawrence and Lorsch found that uncertainty in a specific environment can impact organizations' decision-making and other internal formal structures (Magnani and Zucchella, 2018). Lawrence and Lorsch suggested that organizational systems evolve due to rational decisions based on environmental conditions, constraints, and opportunities (Magnani and Zucchella, 2018).

Bounded Rationality theory. Bounded rationality is considered an open system-rational approach to organizations, which relies on the standard rational dimensions of organizations and, at the same time, on the external environment (Hernandez and Ortega, 2019). Based on Simon's decision-making theory, bounded rationality theory explores the environmental effect on decision-making processes inside organizations (Hernandez and Ortega, 2019). Bounded rationality theory suggests that individual awareness and understanding are constrained and connected to external

environmental conditions (Scot and Davis, 2017). In 1958, March and Simon suggested that organizations and their social environment can anticipate possible consequences, what they will not be able to anticipate, or possible alternatives decision-makers can accept or disregard (Bromiely et al., 2019; Anderson and Lemken, 2019).

3.2.2 Environmental Analysis Theories

The study of environmental impacts on organizations has become increasingly important as a means of understanding the various external influences exerted by the environment. Additional attention was given to the external environment, and new ideas were proposed at the ecological level (Elfahmi et al., 2021). The open system perspective inspired new theories and organizational research, which considered organizations part of a more comprehensive environment (Volkman et al., 2019; Roberts, 2019). The main influential environmental analysis theories are Contingency theory, developed by Lawrence and Lorsch, Thompson (1967) Transaction cost theory, developed by Williamson (1975) and resource dependency theory, developed by Pfeffer and Selznick (1978).

Transaction Cost Theory. Transaction cost theory adopted an open-rational system approach theory and was developed by Williamson in 1975. Transaction cost theory interprets external factors' effects on an organization's rational behavior by analyzing economic trade costs (Scot and Davis, 2017). Based on the notion that organizations pursue more productivity and reduce costs, trading costs can influence decision-making and other organizational processes, Williamson proposed that organizational transaction costs represent the optimal level of analysis (Scott and Davis, 2017). Transaction cost theory emphasizes the importance of organizational analysis on an ecological level, as organizational behavior is rational and can be affected by external factors (Aksom and Firsova, 2021).

Resource Dependence Theory. Resource dependency theory is also based on a natural-open system approach. Resource dependence theory suggests that organizations affect environments in the same way environments affect organizations (Baalouch et al., 2019). Pfeffer and Selznick argued that organizational structure is determined by the power of struggle between organizations and their environments and by organizational efficiency (Scott and Davis, 2018). Through the lens of resource dependence theory, organizations depend on their external environment to survive, creating an interdependent relationship and, simultaneously, creating a rivalry between organizations for environmental resources (Roundy and Bayer, 2019). Individuals within organizations can explore their surroundings for new possibilities, obtain desirable results, avoid environmental threats, or alter external environment conditions (Hatch, 2018).

Population Ecology Theory. Hannan and Freeman formulated organizational ecology theory in 1977, which focuses on the role of environmental selection forces. According to Roundy and Bayer (2019) population ecology and the resource dependence theory consider that organizations are affected by their external environment. The resource dependency theory focuses on the organizational level analysis, while the population ecology theory focuses on the external environment analysis (Aldrich and Wiedenmayer et al., 2019). The population ecologists emphasize organizations' operations within a specific environment by which these organizations compete for environmental resources (Aldrich and Wiedenmayer et al., 2019). In the lens of this theory, the external environment optimizes organizations, while organizations stay the same due to structural inertia, which does not allow organizations to optimize by themselves (Hatch, 2018).

New Institutional Theory. The new institutional theory takes an open-natural approach to analyze organizations on an ecological level (Hatch, 2018). The new institutional theory implies, similar

to other natural system approaches, that the formal structure of an organization is different from its actual operations (Mutch, 2021). According to Moser et al. (2020) the new institutional theory focuses on organizations' cognitive controls. However, unlike the bounded theory, organizational behavior is not the product of formal or rational programs but of institutional perceptions and symbols (Mutch, 2021). Selznick considered that organizations are guided by the symbols defined in their institutional setting rather than the formal goals (Morrill, 2021). Institutional theory presupposes isomorphism, similar to organizational population ecology theory (Scott and Davis, 2017).

The Enacted Environment Theory. The enactment theory presumes that an organization's members can have an objective construct about their environment based on ecological analysis data (Damsa et al., 2019). Damsa et al. (2019) considered that the analysis outcome determines the environment to which the organization will respond. Unlike the ambiguity theory, which claims that complexity and change can limit decision-makers' ability inside an organization with insufficient information, the enactment theory implies that decision-makers respond to their perceived environment, which they assumed and anticipated (Hatch, 2018). Following information theory, Weick has assumed that, regardless of belief in an objectively real environment, environmental conditions cannot be distinguished from perceived conditions (Langenberg and Wesseling, 2016; Parrish et al., 2020).

Technical Systems Theory. Due to the rapid advances and the increased reliance on technology in different processes inside organizations, organizations were considered 'technical systems' (Hoerlsberger, 2019; Bolanos et al., 2019). Sproull and Goodman considered technical systems a combination of machines and techniques an organization adopts to produce a specific outcome

(Scot and Davis, 2018). Similarly, Hughes considered that technical systems are systems of complex, problem-solving components developed to solve problems or achieve goals by utilizing available means (Haraldson et al., 2018). Van Zyl-Bulitta (2019) considered that technological systems are interrelated, co-operating components that, as a whole, produce a new function.

3.2.3 Post-Modern Theories

The global changes happening worldwide and the development of technology imposed a new relationship between different organizations. Organizations are considered interacting systems with each other and at the same time with their environment (Gurcam, 2019; Cokgungor, 2021; Arena and Hussenot, 2021; Hoogetboom and Wilderom, 2020). Organizations are no longer constrained within their borders but can extend their operations internationally (Scot and Davis, 2017). The boundaries of competition forces faded as globalization led to a new competitive situation (Akande and Akande, 2021; Etemad, 2021; Luo, 2021). The competitive pressures, along with globalization and the utilization of information technology, have radically changed the focus of developments toward the scale and scope in many markets and industries, which challenged the perception of open-systems theory internationally (Akande and Akande, 2021; Etemad, 2021; Luo, 2021). Organizations struggle to adapt and operate outside their local landscape, resulting in an altered environment (Eliakis et al., 2020). Globalization has altered the traditional organizational landscape, where organizations interact and communicate with each other in new ways (Lowell, 2020). Through the lens of such competitive environments, new theories have emerged to understand better the relationship between organizations and their environment based on the system design approach. Among these theories are Chaos theory, Network theory, and Self-organization theory.

Chaos Theory. Chaos focuses on the unpredictability of systems and implies that an organization, at certain times, resides in chaos and, at the same time, is productive but without any predictability or clear direction (Lartey, 2020; Altinay and Kozak, 2021; Benbya et al., 2020). Benbya et al. (2020) considered that organizations operate within systems, which could be patterns, ecosystems, or organization sets or fields. Li et al. (2020) considered that the chaotic behavior of the systems might appear random; however, through a mathematical formula, it can be identified that the systems are in order or have finite boundaries.

Network Theory. Network theory uses network analysis techniques to visualize and analyze the interactions between network nodes, including resources, information flows, energy, and authority (Groce et al., 2019; Kapucu, 2020; Soyyigit et al., 2020). It has been suggested by Marchiori and Franco (2020) that organizational researchers can use network theory to visualize and explain the processes of organizations as well as the emergence of inter-organizational coalitions and structures of dominance. Network theory defines organizations as informal and formal networks between members and different organizational units (Bonanomi et al., 2020). Soderstrom and Weber (2020) suggested that network theory could describe the link between organizational members and between different organizations.

Self-Organization Theory. Self-organizing relates to an organization's ability to alter its internal structure or response to external environmental settings (Gershenson et al., 2020). Self-organizing theory implies that, within a self-organization structure, different units and elements can organize themselves and, at the same time, stabilize the organizational structure or function of the whole organization (Moroz, 2020). The process of self-organization is an internal process that is not instructed outside the system (Gierlich-Joas et al., 2020). William Ross Ashby proposed self-

organization in 1947 and considered that a self-organization system could automatically evolve towards equilibrium; however, organizations could be in a state of equilibrium as an attractor in the medium of the external environment (Daria, 2019; Majumdar and Josephson, 2020). Benbya et al. (2020) noted that once an organization is in a state of equilibrium, its further evolution is constrained to remain an attractor, which requires a form of reciprocal dependence or co-operation between its organizational units.

Complexity Adaptive System Theory. Adaptive complexity theory adopts a systems approach for organizations. Adaptive complexity theory is based on natural sciences research that studies the uncertainty and non-linearity of an organization within a specific environment (Lartey, 2020). Complexity theory focuses on interactions and feedback loops, which change systems constantly and proposes that systems are unpredictable and limited by order-generating rules (Kautz et al., 2020; Galkina and Atkova, 2020). Bento et al. (2020) Complexity theory can be used to understand how organizations adapt to their environments and, at the same time, how they cope with uncertain circumstances. In the lens of Adaptive complex system theory, organizations are complex structures constantly reacting and interacting with their networks, and their relationships are not aggregations of individual static entities (Ajulo, 2020; Jarrar et al., 2020).

Several researchers (Baptista et al., 2020; Wessel et al., 2020; Scoblic, 2020; Banerjee et al., 2021; Ergene et al., 2021) agreed that the way modern organizations are working is radically different from how organizations have performed in the last ten years. However, many other organizations continue to work based on old business models, weighted down by old processes, behaviors, and systems, which must be challenged and abandoned before disruptive change happens (Sima et al., 2020; Barbulescu et al., 2020; Yun and Yan., 2020). As organizations are becoming digitalized,

they face a growing imperative to reinvent themselves, move quicker, adapt more rapidly, promote accelerated learning, and embrace a dynamic culture within their organizations (Trauttschnig and Hetz, 2020; Volberda et al., 2021; Elangovan, 2021). However, leading companies are moving beyond the design process and are currently developing a better and new organization for the future (De Smet et al., 2021). Designing the organizations of the future may be difficult for some organizations due to the nature of the processes an organization should go through to reach this state, for that, designing the organizations of the future is a continuous and never-ending process (Burton et al., 2020; Elangovan, 2021; De Smet et al., 2021).

Organizations that rise to the challenge need to adopt new ways to deal with altering external conditions and demands for new capabilities and performance (Alexander and Manolchev, 2020). In contrast to the past, organizations have typically been built for efficiency and effectiveness; however, it is not enough to achieve efficiency and effectiveness to operate in an ever-changing environment (Burton et al., 2020). Instead, organizations need to be designed for speed, agility, and adaptability to compete with other organizations in a globally competitive environment (Walter, 2021; McCormack et al., 2021).

3.2.4 Co-Evolutionary Theory

This section presents the origins of co-evolutionary theory and its adoption in organizational and management research. The section discusses the significance of the co-evolutionary approach and its ability to better understand the relationship between organizations and their environments. This section also presents several examples of co-evolutionary approaches used in research in different fields.

Origins of Co-Evolutionary Theory. Drawing on Charles Darwin's works in the field of natural sciences, Darwin based his theories on the relationships and unique mechanisms of different organisms and their environments (Abatecola et al., 2020; Crilly, 2021). Based on Darwin's theories and scientific approaches, researchers from various fields have been influenced by Darwin's exploration of the relationship between different entities and their environments (Parisot, 2020). Darwin's theory covered new fields other than science and described the relationship between entities and their environment (Du Crest et al., 2020; Pelaez, 2020). In fields like sociology, which studies the changes or development of social factors within a local or global environment, Darwinism has been introduced as a new term to describe changes within a specific environment (Indriyani et al., 2021; Baraghith, 2020). It has been concluded by several researchers (Abatecola et al., 2020; Brierley, 2020; Da Costa and Horn, 2020; Baraghith, 2020) that the terms 'evolution,' 'evolutionary,' and most recently, 'co-evolution' have replaced Darwinism as these terms are used more among scholars and in the theories of the organization.

Oyibo and Gabriel (2020) considered that the research on organizational evolution has been developed in different but intertwined directions to describe the relationship between organizations and their environments. Several authors (Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021; Robertson et al., 2021) disputed whether organizational co-evolution is created by or results from changing organizational environments. A great debate was developed among scholars from different fields on the primary sources of influence in a co-evolutionary process (Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021; Robertson et al., 2021). A debate was raised to reveal whether the co-evolution of an organization is externally pulled due to its environmental influence or internally pulled from the organization's ability, based on the organization's capability (Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Sarta

et al., 2021; Robertson et al., 2021). Sections 2.5.2 and 2.5.3 discuss the co-evolutionary literature in organization and management research.

Co-Evolution Theory in Organization Research. Several scholars (Qi et al., 2020; Shuffler, 2020; Pande et al., 2020; Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Bocken and Geradts, 2020; Garcia-Diaz and Peli., 2020; Kaipainen, 2020) investigated the main factors driving organizational co-evolution. Cantele et al. (2020) considered that organizations and their environments are reciprocal. Organizations do not operate separately from their environments, and at the same time, organizational environments are shaped by organizations that operate inside them (Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Donbesuur et al., 2020; Harsch and Festing et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Each organization has its characteristics, and at the same time, each environment has its unique setting (Donbesuur et al., 2020; Harsch and Festing et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al., 2021). The distinct characteristics of organizations and environments create mutual influence and provoke certain behaviors from each side (Donbesuur et al., 2020; Harsch and Festing et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al., 2021).

Environment settings change typically due to emerging events and circumstances, similarly, organizations undergo several changes and development, which increase their abilities and influence as an entity (Harsch and Festing et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Environmental changes create intertwined influences between the environment and the organization and may radically alter the environment setting (Harsch and Festing et al., 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al., 2021; Sarta et al., 2021).

Lundan and Cantwell (2020) believed that the mutual influence between an organization and its environment could positively or negatively affect each side. According to Margiono (2021) the

environmental setting can be affected by organizational changes due to the influences of the development or building of new organizational capabilities, similarly, the environment's new setting can affect organizational sustainability or growth. Chen et al. (2020) considered that the relationship between organizations and their environment is bounded by a unique mechanism, which also shapes the potential or existence of each side. Lundan and Cantwell (2020) agreed with Chen et al. (2020) and considered that studying co-evolution will help organizations create or reform new relationships with their environments. Abatecola et al. (2020) suggested that co-evolutionary factors bound the relationship between organizations and their environments. Research from different fields agrees that co-evolutionary approach can identify the bounding factors between organizations and their environment (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Organizations can respond to the existing bounding factors with their environments, whether internally by making necessary organizational changes or externally by reforming or leaving the environment, for the sake of its competitiveness, survival, or growth (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021).

In system theory, organizations are considered closed systems, which operate independently and depend on their internal factors without considering external factors (Moller et al., 2020). However, organizations cannot be separated from their environments and other organizations in the same environment or external resources (Walter, 2021; Pasaribu et al., 2021). The term 'Task Environment' was used to distinguish between an organization's internal and external environment,

by which organizations should consider external variables in the process of organizational evaluation and strategic planning (Foss et al., 2019; Joseph and Gaba, 2020). By that, organizations can understand and acknowledge their organizational capabilities and be able to make necessary changes in their internal and external environments (Foss et al., 2019; Joseph and Gaba, 2020; Walter, 2021; Pasaribu et al., 2021).

Research has shown that an interdependent relationship exists between organizations and their environments (Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). In this view, organizational co-evolution can be achieved through reciprocal influence and interdependence between organizations and their environments (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020). Organizations can have negative or positive influences on their environments and, similarly, can also shape the conditions or setting of their environment (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Co-evolution can be a positive co-evolution that leads to better survival conditions and organizational growth or a negative co-evolution that may affect organizational sustainability within its environment (Mingione et al., 2020; Lundan and Cantwell, 2020; Menglong et al., 2020). With such relationship, organizations can dominate and shape their survival and growth in their environment through the development of new capabilities, processes, or innovation (Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Duchek, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Das et al., 2020; Eliakis et al., 2020).

Based on biological sciences, natural selection is not the only mechanism that can bound the relationship between organizations and their environments (Ma et al., 2020; Synder, 2020;

Arghode et al., 2020; Petracca and Gallagher, 2020; Shkliarevsky, 2020). According to Sarta et al. (2021) natural selection relates to the principle of adaptation mechanism, which is limited to specific changes in organizational structures, processes, or operations to form an organization to ensure its sustainability or growth. Cantele et al. (2020) argued that natural selections and adaptation are not the only available mechanisms but do not oppose each other. However, the relationship between organizations and environments is the product of their reciprocal influences. One side can be the cause or the effect of the influences of the other side (Sarta et al., 2021). However, Abatecola et al. (2021) believed there must be a distinction between the natural selection process and competitive selection among organizations. Natural selection is a deterministic factor by which the environment shapes the roles and positions of organizations within it (Donaires and Martinelli, 2019; Fuertes et al., 2020). Sarta et al. (2021) believed that if a dramatic change happens in the environment, and at the same time an organization cannot handle or lacks essential components or factors, this will force the organization to be driven by the environment strategy. Hillmann and Guenther (2021) argued that an organization must have the self-control to face environmental changes. Duchek (2020) considered that if an organization cannot have all the required components to face challenges, it must expand its task environment. Treece (2020) suggested that, for the organization to maintain its competitiveness and uniqueness, it must acquire unequal capabilities, by which an organization can balance its internal inertia, barriers, barriers, and environmental uncertainties. According to Barisic et al. (2021) horizontal and vertical integration focuses on acquiring and expanding the utilization of technology in the presence of environmental constraints. In addition, Barisic et al. (2020) considered that technology could expand the organization's presence and add new functions, features, or roles. In this lens, organizations should consider external variables in organizational evaluation and strategic

planning (Fuertes et al., 2020). By that, organizations can understand and acknowledge their organizational capabilities, the influence exerted on their environment, and what is outside their borders (Annarelli et al., 2020).

Co-Evolution Theory in Management Research. Several researchers (Shatilo, 2020; Elbanna et al., 2020; Damanpour et al., 2020; Aronson, 2021) considered several internal factors of an organization could influence management choices and the decision-making process inside an organization. From that, dialectical approaches can be explained as the conditions of environments, organizations' capabilities and resources, and the organization's choices and decisions (Dzhengiz, 2020; De Keyser et al., 2021). Decisions at organizations are usually made by management, mainly by senior managers, who shape the strategic choices and develop the organization's future (Doz et al., 2020). For these reasons, co-evolution, from a management perspective, gains its significance in co-evolutionary research. Co-evolution can be considered a new and essential function for managers (Parisot et al 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020). Management role should be expanded from internal organizational functions to external environment (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021). This function then expands to manage or organize the interrelated processes between their organizations and environments (Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). By that, management can act as a managing force for these interactions (Fuertes et al., 2020). Management is an essential element in organizational co-evolution and a driving force of change (Kaipainen, 2020). From that, dialectical approaches can be explained as the conditions of environments, organizations' capabilities and resources, and the organization's choices and decisions.

Environments can be categorized on the degree of determinism conditions and for organizations on the strategic choices made by managers inside the organization (Koseoglu, 2020). Decisions at organizations are usually made by management, mainly by senior managers, who shape the

strategic choices and develop plans for the organization (Lejarraga and Lejarraga, 2020). Thus, an organization's competitiveness can be understood as environmental conditions and management voluntarism (Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Rabetino, 2021).

New research was introduced to investigate the role of the management, whether it is the product of environmental forces or intentional action. Lejarraga and Lejarraga (2020) suggested that the relationship between organizations and their environment can be understood by studying the strategic managerial intentionality and management influence on the external environment.

Managerial response based only on a reaction to environmental influences is given the term 'environmental determinism', while managerial intentionality, or strategic choices, is considered a voluntarist response (Fumasoli et al., 2019). For such reasons, co-evolution, from a management perspective, gained its significance in this domain (Donbesuur et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2020; Maze and Chailan, 2020; Ma et al., 2020; Adamoglou and Hajidimitriou, 2020; Jahanbakht and Romel, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020). Co-evolution can be considered a new and essential function for managers (Ma et al., 2020; Adamoglou and Hajidimitriou, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020). In the lens of co-evolution theory, management as a function expanded from internal function inside an organization to external environments managers (Ma et al., 2020; Adamoglou and Hajidimitriou, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020). Management function should expand to manage or organize the interrelated processes between their organizations and environments and can act as a managing force of these interactions (Donbesuur et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2020; Adamoglou and Hajidimitriou, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020). Management is an essential element in organizational co-evolution and a driving force of organizational and environmental change (Teece, 2020; Donbesuur et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2020; Adamoglou and Hajidimitriou, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020).

The nature of deterministic and voluntarist approaches has been debated among different researchers. The term 'Dialectical approaches' was used to describe the dilemma between deterministic and voluntarist approaches, which study managerial characteristics and respond to environmental changes (Stanczyk-Hugiet et al., 2019; De Keyser, 2021; Beycioglu and Kondakci, 2021; Mettang, 2022).

Organizational strategies or search behavior can be exploitative or explorative (Nel, 2020; Castillo Apraiz, 2021). A clear understanding of the organization-environment conditions is considered an essential role of management in understanding the relationship between organizations and their environment, or 'sense making' (Eremenko, 2022). Environmental characteristics can be identified by their degree of complexity, predictability, and stability, which influence organizations (Walter, 2021; Moller et al., 2020). Sense-making is a primary managerial function that can enable management to construct a general view of the organization's environment (Haarhaus, 2020; Khezri, 2021; Aichouche, 2021; Aricioglu, and Berk, 2022). Darvishmotevali et al. (2020) considered the ability to make sense of the organizational environment, evaluate their organizational position and status within their environment, and help respond to different external factors. Crupi et al. (2021) considered that a manager to make sense of his environment adequately depends on a sufficient and profound analysis of the setting of organizational environments. According to Sarta et al. (2020) environments can be labeled and evaluated relative to the organization and managerial capabilities, strategies, and resources. Walter (2021) argued that environments might be considered an organization's threat or an opportunity. Organizational environments can be considered analyzable or unanalyzable, for that attention should be paid to the different settings of each environment for better interaction between organizations and their

environments (Chaudhry, 2020; Arslan et al., 2021). Llopis-Albert et al. (2020) considered rapid decision-making essential in uncertain environments or constant change.

The role of management in building a construct of the relationship between an organization and its environment is considered a subjective action. Vinarski Peretz (2020) supported the construct's subjectivity since managers use their views, knowledge, and analysis abilities to evaluate their surroundings. Burgos et al. (2020) suggested that behavioral influences affect decision-making processes. At the same time, the manager's perspective can limit his ability to pursue the origination's goals and objectives, which can negatively affect the organization. Similarly, Lejarraga and Lejarraga (2020) believed that constructed or perceived reality can be subjective and emphasized by studying each side alone.

Several scholars (Li and Fleury, 2020; Bocken and Geradts, 2020; Scoblic, 2020; Naradda Gamage et al., 2020; Del Giudice et al., 2021; Do et al., 2022) argued that, as organizational environments are becoming more competitive and markets are globally open, new challenges emerge and affect the ability of organizations to survive. The understanding of environment and organization must be changed, with more emphasizes on management role (Nuruzzaman et al., 2020). With the emergence of new environmental conditions, the deterministic environment must be shifted to an intentional or voluntarist view (Wrede et al., 2020). Organizations can benefit from proactive management, which embraces strategic initiatives, intentional choices, and innovation (Sarta et al., 2020; Ahlstrom et al., 2020). Do and Nguyen (2020) considered that managers make strategic contingency plans, rather than acting passively, depending on selection and adaption mechanism, from a deterministic perspective. Sarta et al. (2020) suggested that the strategic intentionality of the organization and the environmental conditions can identify organizational change or adaptation with sufficient investigation of both sides. The significance of studying the founders of the

founding team of different organizations, as well as the turnover rates, gained significance as a method to evaluate the current status of an organization and the level of knowledge and expertise inside it (Cornelissen et al., 2020; Shepherd et al., 2020).

Through this lens, the concept of bounded rationality emerged to understand management's subjective influences in determining and responding to the relationship between an organization and its environment (Morales Burgos, 2020; Rabetino et al., 2021). Jia et al. (2020) considered that bounded rationality research provided guidelines to evaluate cognitive management schemas, abilities, and background knowledge, especially those in decision-making positions or directly influencing the organization's status and performance. Bach and Galvin (2020) believed that organizations, as a whole, can be a replicate or a reflection model of the characteristics of their top management and executives. By this relation, the rise or fall of an organization can be understood or predicted, as management qualities and capabilities are considered the core function of expertise (Bach and Galvin, 2020; Singh and Ramdeo, 2020; Maxwell et al., 2020). Due to the increasing external influences and significance of international organizational strategies, Section 2.5.4 will elaborate on these factors from a co-evolutionary perspective.

Open Markets and Globalization. International strategy created a new setting for organizational environments (Teece, 2020; Sarta et al., 2020; Walter, 2021). Many organizations changed their operations locally to integrate new organizational capabilities to operate in new environmental conditions or markets (Fuertes et al., 2020). Through the lens of co-evolutionary theory, several researchers (Lundan and Cantwell, 2020; Liu, 2020; Sarta et al., 2021) investigated the relationship between organizations and their environment in the presence of international strategy and considered the relationship as an integration and response relationship. Researchers emphasized the presence of new pressures exerted from external environments or industries on organizations

to expand internationally (Tatoglu et al., 2020; Dzhengiz, 2020; Moser et al., 2020; Cantele et al., 2020). Valarezo et al. (2021) considered that organizations should be able to satisfy local requirements by offering products or services with unique characteristics to compete locally. Hermans and Borda Reyes (2020) argued that organizations are forced to change their local operations, add and integrate new international operations, and face competition locally and internationally to be able to offer such value. Such integration can exist with other organizations by coordinating their processes and practices, which can facilitate the organization's operation in both local and external environments (Luo, 2020). Walter (2021) considered that international integration strategies help organizations acquire new products from external environments or acquire the necessary resources to satisfy local markets. To achieve international integration, organizations tried to standardize their products and processes and adopted multi-focal strategies (Tan, 2021; Rosinska-Bukowska, 2020). Other authors concluded that, through the standardization of strategies, organizations could satisfy local requirements and respond to external competition simultaneously (Sundstrom et al., 2020; Meyer et al., 2020).

Co-Evolutionary Approach. Co-evolution research has gained importance in organizational research since the last century. Based on organizational co-evolution theory, a co-evolutionary approach has emerged to better understand the interaction between an organization and its environment (Abatecola et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2022). Several researchers (Kompella, 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Van der Bijl-Brouwer et al., 2021; Cristofaro, 2022) have conducted research in different fields and disciplines using a co-evolutionary approach to investigate the main factors that determine the relationship between organizations and their environment, as well as the factors that limit organizations' ability to co-evolve with their environment. In addition, co-evolution theory helped research develop co-evolutionary frameworks that enrich its value and

utilization in organizational research (Kompella, 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Van der Bijl-Brouwer et al., 2021; Cristofaro, 2022). Co-evolutionary approaches were extended to encompass managerial capabilities to construct a more comprehensive view and understanding of the organization-environment relationship (Abatecola et al., 2020; Maula et al., 2020; Luo and Huang, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022; Cristofaro, 2022).

Several co-evolutionary frameworks will be discussed in this section. The co-evolutionary frameworks are: The Co-evolution of firm absorptive capacity and knowledge environment, Co-Evolution of firm capabilities and industry competition, and Co-Evolutionary framework for analyzing a transition to a sustainable low-carbon economy. The co-evolution of firm absorptive capacity and knowledge environment framework was developed to investigate organizational absorptive capacity in assimilating new knowledge, which is considered a driver for organizational development and adaptation. The framework explains how knowledge can be obtained from an external organizational environment and used to develop organizational capabilities and generate new organizational forms. This framework encompasses more internal and external factors than other frameworks. In addition, this framework attempts to provide a deeper understanding and a transparent overview of the relationship between organizations and their environment by adding additional factors.

Figure 3-1: The Co-evolution of Firm Absorptive Capacity and Knowledge Environment Framework

Source: Vasylieva et al. (2013)

The co-evolution of firm capabilities and industry competition framework adopts co-evolutionary theory to understand rival organizations' behavior within a competitive environment in their pursuit of new capabilities. The framework analyzes organizational search behavior and determines organizations' co-evolution over time.

Figure 3-2: Co-Evolution of Firm Capabilities and Industry Competition Framework

Source: Renard (2010)

The co-evolutionary framework for analyzing a transition to a sustainable low-carbon economy was developed to help the researcher analyze the transition to a sustainable low-carbon economy. The framework focuses on the dynamic interactions of social and technological elements of organizations on the micro and macro levels. The framework focuses on analyzing long-term industrial change due to a dynamic system based on the process of variation, selection, and retention and interactions between social and technological factors of organizations.

Figure 3-3: The Co-Evolutionary Framework for Analyzing a Transition to a Sustainable Low-Carbon Economy

Source: Fox (2011)

Several researchers and scholars (Franco et al., 2018; Amati et al., 2019; Chan et al., 2019; Edmondson, 2019; Kompella, 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Mole, 2020) from different fields have applied co-evolutionary approaches to identify the main factors that shape organizations' abilities to co-evolve with their environment and better understand the relationships between organizations and their environment and. Franco et al. (2018) adopted the co-evolution theory to analyze electric companies' co-evolution. The research focuses on the technological development of electric

companies' capabilities and their effect on the outcome and development of electric companies within their environment. Amati et al. (2019) adopted a co-evolutionary approach to study the mutual dependence between inter-organizational networks, internal organizational structure, and network structure. Chan et al. (2019) used a co-evolutionary approach to investigate how enterprises can achieve organizational co-evolution based on their IT and knowledge. Menglong et al. (2020) developed a co-evolutionary framework for business-IT alignment via the lens of enterprise architecture. Edmondson (2019) adopted a co-evolutionary approach to developing a conceptual framework to analyze the dynamics of policy mixes and socio-technical systems. Kompella (2020) used a co-evolutionary framework to explore how organizations can enable radical product innovations in a competitive environment. Based on the co-evolution theory, Mihalache and Volberda (2021) developed a co-evolutionary framework to provide a new business model that facilitates innovation in transforming economies and identifying the main environmental actors within a global digital environment. Lundan and Cantwell (2020) researched the local co-evolution of firms and governments to identify the main factors that bond organizational relationships. Chidlow (2021) adopted a co-evolutionary approach in his research to investigate the co-evolution of multinational enterprises' international activities. Mole (2020) in his research, explored the barriers to sustainable transitions in the agro-food industries by developing a co-evolutionary framework from a multi-level perspective. Schott et al. (2020) used co-evolutionary theory in their research on Operationalizing knowledge co-evolution toward a sustainable fish industry in Nunavut.

Organizational Theories Review. Based on the previous sections, the researcher reviewed organizational theories. Organizations are considered systems with rational, natural, and open characteristics through organizational theories.

Rational Systems Theories. The rational system perspective focuses on the internal factors inside an organization regarding its activities, structure and members' behavior, while this perspective does not encompass organizational external influencing factors. Rational system theories, including scientific management theory, like other rational theories, focus on narrow factors or one primary factor to analyze or better understand an organization. The scientific management theory highlights the importance of the role of management inside an organization and cooperation with other employees inside the organization. Similarly, Administrative theory focuses on studying organizations on the structural level. Although organizational structure is essential, focusing on one or a narrow factor does not give a comprehensive understanding of the nature of an organization. Likewise, decision-making theory introduced a new level of analysis inside an organization. In his decision-making theory, Simon focused on analyzing the social-psychological level of employees inside an organization. Weber (1968) also introduced his organizational theory, which focuses on the legitimate rational authority inside an organization. Rational system theories focus on specific factors inside an organization. These factors alone cannot give an organization a comprehensive view; however, these theories are beneficial if a researcher investigates these specific factors alone. As the nature of organizations is continuously changing, as well as their environments, narrow factors cannot provide a better understanding but a partial understanding, especially in changing environments. The Rational system approaches were based on the organizational formality and the common goal or interests of the organization members. The naturalists challenged the increasingly formal system of rational institutions, where rationalists did not dispute the presence of the structures but challenged whether or not the system was essential to the organization's members (Scott & Davis, 2017).

Natural System Theories. New Human Relations School, Cooperative System, and Institutional approaches New Human relations school, Cooperative System, and Institutional approaches are considered three main approaches in the natural system perspective. Like scientific management theory, human relations theory emphasizes psychological analysis (Scott and Davis, 2017; Hatch, 2018). However, unlike science management theory, it relies on informal factors that impact organizations' productivity (Enock, 2017). Cooperative system theory focuses on organizations' internal factors; however, the theory exceeds other theories and suggests that organizations are considered environmental actors within their environment, where they can interact with other organizations and, at the same time, be influenced by external factors and altered conditions. Similarly, naturalist theorists focused on an organization's internal environment. Simon's open system theory did not offer a comprehensive approach that can be used to study the nature of the organization-environment relationship (Scott and Davis, 2017).

Open Systems Theories. System design theory, contingency theory and bounded rationality theory are considered main organizational analysis theories based on the open system approach. In 1956 Ludwig von introduced Open system approach to provide a new explanation of the interrelationship between organizations and their environment from an internal perspective (Scott and Davis, 2017; Volkova et al., 2019). The open system theory expanded the role of organizations by having the ability to adapt and interact with their external environment but limited the role of organizations to respond and have a new relationship with their environment. The system design theory is based on studying organizational behavior by studying the repeated organizational routines and feedback between an organization and its external environment. Among other organizational theories, contingency theory and bounded rationality theory emerged to examine organizational factors and encompass specific external factors.

Contingency theory relates to the influence of the external world on the rational behavior of organizations, where the external environment of an organization can provide opportunities and, at the same time, constrain certain limitations. Bounded rationality is based on Simon's decision-making theory; however, bounded rationality theory explores the environmental effect on the decision-making processes inside organizations (Hernandez and Ortega, 2019). Bounded rationality theory suggests that individual awareness and understanding are constrained and connected to external environmental conditions (Scot and Davis, 2017).

Organizational theories focus on narrow factors limited to their internal environment and adaptive response to environmental changes and disregard the analysis of the organization and its environment. For that, organizational theories can be classified as organizational theories, which focus on organizational analysis, and theories that focus on environmental analysis. Since organizational theories adopt mainly internal analysis, the researcher also considered different organizational theories that focus on environmental analysis.

Environmental Analysis Theories. Transaction cost theory, Resource dependence theory, New institutional theory are considered main environmental analysis theories. Transaction cost theory is one of several organizational theories that focus on environmental analysis. Transaction cost theory focuses on how external factors affect an organization economically, which may affect the decision-makers of a particular organization. However, economic factors alone may not always affect organizational decision-making, and transaction costs cannot be taken solely without other external factors.

The resource dependence theory examines one of these theories, and organizations depend on their external environment. However, the resource dependence theory extends further than other theories and suggests an interdependent relation between organizations and their environment,

but from a resource view. The theory of resource dependence focuses on the analysis at the organizational level, while the theory of population ecology focuses on the analysis of the external environment. Population ecology suggests that environmental conditions constrain organization operations and force them to adapt to survive in their environment.

The new institutional theory adopts a symbolic analysis by focusing on an organization's formal and informal mechanisms rather than examining the organizational environment. Similar to the new institutional theory, the enacted environment theory focuses on the cognitive controls of organizations inside, specifically the analysis capability of management and its outcome, by which management determines its environment and characteristics. However, focusing on these factors alone is not enough since there are essential factors inside the organization that can affect an organization's decision-making, even if they can analyze and have the correct data. Without considering different internal and external factors, the determinants of an organization's outcome cannot be identified. Due to the escalating advancement of technology and globalization, which altered the environmental conditions, post-modern theories emerged.

Post-Modern Theories. Chaos theory, Network theory. Self-organizing theory, Chaos theory, Adaptive Complexity theory and Co-evolutionary theories are considered main post-modern organizational theories. Chaos theory examine an organization's environmental conditions and the status of an organization within its environment. However, chaos theory frame environmental conditions in a certain perspective which is not applicable in different circumstances. Network theory conceptualize organizations as a network system, and connectiveness between organizations; however, in competitive markets, organizations often compete with each other and control each other's market share, and in many cases not building new networks.

Self-organizing theory relates to an organization's ability to alter its internal structure in response to new environmental settings. This theory describes adaptation as the process of aligning organizations with the environment; however, it limits organizational options and alternatives since organizations can respond to environmental changes differently.

Adaptive Complexity theory focuses on the interactions and feedback loops which can change or shape a specific system, proposing that systems are unpredictable and limited by order-generating rules. The theory conceptualizes organizations' nature interactions, and function within an environment as adaptive systems. It focuses on identifying the unit that needs to be optimized to adapt to its environment and maintain its operation as an open system within a specific environment. In addition, Adaptive complexity theory conceptualize organizational environments to give a descriptive overview of a specific environment. However, the theory examines internal and external factors using computation algorithms. Computation equations do not show the relation between different factors, especially in a competitive environment. Since this theory focuses on adaptive responses and only organizational internal changes, the theory is unsuitable for the present research.

Co-Evolution Theory. Contrary to other organizational theories, co-evolutionary theory investigates an organization's external and internal environment and the relation between both. In addition, co-evolutionary theory emphasizes managerial role internally inside an organization and managing the relationship between an organization and its environment. Co-evolutionary theory embraces a proactive response to environmental changes, contrary to other organizational theories, which offer adaptation as the only option. Moreover, co-evolutionary theory encompasses more factors than other organizational theories, and includes several factors that

other theories adopt that can help identify the main factors limiting organizations to co-evolve with their environment.

To better decide how to apply the selected theory in this research, the researcher reviewed several frameworks that study the relationship between organizations and their environments.

3.3 Organizational Frameworks Review

The literature is filled with different frameworks investigating organizational and environmental factors. Most frameworks focus on a specific or single internal or external factor. Literature, however, includes frameworks that study organization's internal and external factors, either separately or together, without studying the relationship between them. The present research aims to investigate the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and to identify the internal and external factors limiting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment, emphasizing Lebanese management role.

Before deciding on a suitable framework for this research, the researcher reviewed the literature on frameworks investigating the relationship between organizations and their environments. The researcher gained more insight into the existing literature, gaps, and what is required to develop a comprehensive framework that can better understand Lebanese universities' relationship with their environment. The researcher also identified the primary internal and external factors that prevent Lebanese universities from co-evolving. This section will illustrate the main frameworks considered alternative frameworks in this research. However, these frameworks were not selected due to their shortcomings and inability to help achieve the research's aims and objectives. The frameworks are: Technology-organization-environment, Complex Adaptive System, Dynamic Capabilities, and Strategic management frameworks.

3.3.1 Technology Organization Environment Framework

Technology organization environment framework studies several internal organizational factors that describe and determent an organization's ability to adopt new technologies (Stenberg and Nilsson, 2020; Kwabena et al., 2020). Technology organization environment framework focuses on internal and external factors and conceptualizes the relationship between organizations, organizational environment, and the readiness of an organization to adopt new technologies (Pateli et al., 2020). Several researchers (Wolverton and Lanier, 2019; Lihniash et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020) used the technology organization environment framework in their research. Chen et al. (2020) used technology organization environment framework to investigate the readiness of Chinese construction companies to adopt new technologies, taking into consideration organizational and external environment factors. Wolverton and Lanier (2019) used Technology organization environment framework to research the adoption decision in a healthcare context. In addition, Lihniash et al. (2019) used the Technology organization environment framework to study the ability of Libyan Financial Institutions to adopt internet financial reporting. Although technological factors are essential in researching organizational co-evolution, technology is an influencing factor that affects the co-evolution of organizations; it does not provide a comprehensive construct of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. Technology organization environment framework conceptualizes the interaction between organizations and their environment, from an adaptive perspective, without providing additional options for organizations. At the same time, the Technology organization environment framework focuses on technological factors affecting the environment, its adaption, and the outcome of such integration on the organization, from one side ignoring the effect of technology organization on their environment.

Figure 3-4: Technology Organization Environment Framework

Source: Van Dyk and Van Belle (2020)

3.3.2 Complex Adaptive System Framework

Complex adaptive system framework was considered an alternative in the present research. Complex adaptive systems framework was developed to study, explain, and understand systems and their agents, which combine and interact internally and externally (Carmichael and Hadzikadic, 2019; Kaufmann et al., 2020; Dentoni et al., 2021). In the lens of the complex adaptive system framework, organizational agents produce emergent patterns via correlated feedback throughout the system that creates a persistent pattern of behavior (Carmichael and Hadzikadic, 2019; Kaufmann et al., 2020; Dentoni et al., 2021). The complex adaptive system framework investigates internal organizational grammar, external organizational environment, and the interaction between organizations and their environments (Benbya, et a., 2020). Complex adaptive system framework is used in several organizational studies. Zhang et al. (2019) adopted Complex adaptive systems framework to study the evolution of supply chains, while Glover et al. (2020) examined the innovations in hospitals using Complex adaptive systems approach. Craig (2020) used Complex adaptive systems framework to explore knowledge mobilization within a competitive environment.

However, Complex adaptive systems framework mainly focuses on agents inside an organization and their interaction with other internal and external agents. Despite the focus on organizational agents and their interactions with other agents inside the organization, identifying them is essential and a starting point for further investigation of organizational agents and their interactions. The Complex adaptive systems framework does not help identify organizational agents that should be investigated; however, it provides a study of the interactions of these agents. Complex adaptive systems framework was developed mainly to study the connections and interaction between different agents of different organizations and considers that organizations are the main actors in an extensive network. Complex adaptive systems framework suggests that organizations have an adaptive response by enhancing the connection with other environmental actors. However, organizations do not operate in an integrative environment, and each organization has unique agents. In addition, Complex adaptive systems framework uses computational equations to determine the degree of connection for organizational agents, making it difficult to unveil the specific factors or causes for how the agents work. Thus, Complex adaptive systems framework is not suitable for the present research.

Figure 3-5: Complex Adaptive System Framework

Source: Nair and Reed-Tsochas (2019)

3.3.3 Dynamic Capabilities Framework

The researcher also considered Dynamic capability framework in the present research. According to Haarhaus and Liening (2020) dynamic capabilities are an organization's ability to integrate, develop, and reconfigure its internal capabilities in response to influencing external factors. Treece (2020) considered that dynamic capability could be achieved by optimizing and developing organizational capabilities optimally and purposefully. Dynamic capability framework aims to identify the main capabilities to be developed the suitable tools, techniques, and processes to reach this goal (Gupta et al., 2020). Dynamic capabilities framework has been developed to help organizations sense and shape internal and external opportunities by recombining and reconfiguring the organizational intangible and tangible assets (Lee et al., 2021).

Several researchers (Wu, 2017; Tuohimaa, 2019; Vallaster et al., 2021) in different fields used the dynamic capabilities framework; for example, Wu (2017) used Dynamic capabilities framework to maintain corporate sustainability for supply chain firms. Tuohimaa (2019) adopted Dynamic capabilities framework to study organizational routines and the ability to innovate several retail organizations. Vallaster et al. (2021) used Dynamic capabilities framework to investigate emerging industries' micro-foundations of dynamic capabilities.

Figure 3-6: Dynamic Capabilities Framework

Source: Van Dyk and Van Belle (2020)

However, Dynamic capabilities framework has its drawbacks. The dynamic capabilities framework does not focus on identifying the main internal and external factors that limit an organization's abilities; however, it provides a process to develop internal factors of the firm. Thus, maintaining a competitive advantage by focusing only on specific factors or capabilities. In addition, the framework does not provide any role of the firm within its environment as an environment actor or the influence of an organization on its environment. Dynamic capabilities framework does not evaluate management capabilities inside the organization.

In addition, the framework lacks consensus on whether dynamic capabilities are related to the substantive organizational capabilities in a changing environment or an organization's ability to modify existing capabilities, regardless of environmental conditions. For all the factors mentioned, the dynamic capabilities framework is unsuitable for this research.

3.3.4 Strategic Management Framework

Strategic management analyzes the environmental factors of an organization internally and externally. The environmental analysis used in the strategic management framework of organizational and external environment is crucial to managing the relationship between an organization and its environment. For that, the researcher has considered a strategic management framework. A strategic management framework was developed to help decision-makers analyze their external and internal environments, evaluate organizational strategies and plans, and ensure their execution inside the organization (Tedder, 2018; Carrier and Stewart, 2019). Strategic management framework implies continuous evaluations and re-assessment of key organizational factors (Hettich and Kreutzer, 2021). The strategic management framework is typically used to align an organization with environmental changes and develop the process to reach there and achieve organizational objectives strategically. For example, Qatawneh (2019) adopted the strategic management framework to study the alignment of IT firms and organizational performance. Arifiani (2020) adopted the strategic management framework to study organizational response to changes in a turbulent environment. Georgewill (2021) used the strategic management framework to investigate structural flexibility and corporate responsiveness in the business environment.

Figure 3-7: Strategic Management Framework

Source: Jurevicius (2021)

Strategic management framework focuses on the internal changes as a response to environmental influence, making it adaptive. In addition, the strategic management framework lacks several factors essential in investigating organizations' status in an ever-changing environment.

Moreover, the strategic management framework does not assess the managerial role or capabilities.

The present research aims to identify the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' abilities to co-evolve, leaving the execution open to different approaches. Thus, Strategic management framework is disregarded as a suitable approach for this research. Since several organizational frameworks focus on the relation between the internal and external environment of organizations, the researcher decided and have a better picture and a comprehensive overview of the existing literature; the researcher reviewed the existing co-evolutionary frameworks.

In addition, the researcher reviewed several co-evolutionary frameworks in Chapter 3 (Section 3.2.4) developed by scholars and researchers interested in investigating organizational co-evolution. Although these frameworks have their pros, they have their cons regarding adapting them for this research. The mentioned co-evolutionary approaches use fundamental internal and

external factors to investigate organizational co-evolution. However, comprehensive organizational research requires additional factors, and some factors need to be investigated deeply. In addition, co-evolutionary frameworks like the co-evolution of firm absorptive capacity and knowledge environment and the co-evolution of firm capabilities and industry competition framework use specific factors to investigate specific areas or issues, whereas the first framework, knowledge transfer, and the latter focuses on organizational research behavior. However, such frameworks will not give the whole picture of what is happening inside or outside an organization, as they will give a partial view. In addition, other fundamentals need to be added to better understand an organization's status in a particular environment, like managerial role, outcome, and organizational capability. Different factors are essential when investigating organizations' co-evolution in the literature.

Thus, the researcher decided to develop a theoretical framework and integrate the main factors in a new Co-evolutionary framework. This will help the researcher construct a new view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and identify the main factors that limit their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Thus, the new co-evolutionary framework can encompass additional factors to better grasp Lebanese higher education sector and generate comprehensive results.

3.4 Research Gap

Based on the identified literature gap in Chapter 2 (Section 2.2) the researcher presents the knowledge gap by examining existing theories and frameworks that study the organization-environment relationship.

Researchers (Sarta et al., 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2020; Aronsson et al., 2021; Walter, 2021) argued that organizations should be capable of managing both internal and external environments to adapt to external changes as well as internal to make necessary development to its core components to sustain their ability to continue their operations and development. Dewar et al. (2019) considered that there is a continuous feedback relation between organizations and the environment, which should be administered by decreasing or increasing the effect of environmental changes, internal influences, or mutual influences.

Several authors (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021) argued that researchers should adopt an appropriate theory or approach to investigate the relationship between organizations and their environments that allows for better understanding and a comprehensive overview. The study of the organization-environment relationship is a continual understanding of the nature of both sides and identifying the internal and external influencing factors that shape this relationship (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021).

After presenting the development of organizational theories in Section 3.2 and reviewing them in Section 3.3, the researcher found that existing organizational theories and frameworks in the literature mainly focus on limited internal and external when investigating the relationship between organizations and their environments, which provide a partial understanding of the investigated phenomena. The review also showed that while prior organizational theories focused on either the internal or external organizational environment, few theories explored this relationship with limited factors. Prior theories examined the relationship between organizations and their

environments and disregarded key factors that shaped this relationship and didn't extensively examine their significance, influence, or the link between these factors. The focus on limited internal and external factors has limited existing studies' ability to construct a comprehensive overview of the relationship between organizations and their environments and identify factors affecting organizational ability to face external challenges and stay fit within its environment.

Moreover, the review showed that several organizational theories and frameworks investigated organizations' internal and external factors separately, disregarding key factors that operate in both environments, providing a partial understanding of the relationship between organizations and their environments and factors influencing this relationship. Table 3-1 summarizes past organizational theories and the factors they examined.

Table 3-1: Organizational Theories Review Summary

Investigated Factors	<i>Closed System Models</i>		<i>Open System Models</i>	
	<i>1900–1930 Rational Models</i>	<i>1930–1960 Natural Models</i>	<i>1960–1970 Rational Models</i>	<i>1970– Natural Models</i>
Organizational Factors	Scientific Management	Human Relations	Bounded Rationally	Organizing
Internal Organizational Factors	Taylor (1911)	Whyte (1959)	March and Simon (1958)	Weick (1969)
Social Psychological	Decision Making			
	Simon (1945)			
Organizational Factors	Bureaucratic Theory	Cooperative Systems	Contingency Theory	Sociotechnical Systems
Internal Organizational Factors	Weber (1968 trans.)	Barnard(1938)	Lawrence and Lorsch (1967)	Miller and Rice (1967)
Structural	Administrative Theory	Human Relations	Comparative Structure	
	Fayol (1919)	Mayo (1945)	Woodward (1965)	
			Pugh et al. (1969)	
			Blau (1970)	
		Conflict Models		
		Gouldner (1954)		
Environmental Factors			Transaction Cost	Organizational Ecology
Organizational External Factors:			Williamson (1975)	Hannan and Freeman (1977)
Economical, Political, Social,			Knowledge-based	Resource Dependence
Technological, Ecological, Legal.			Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995)	Pfeffer and Salancik (1978)
				Institutional Theory
				Selznick (1949)
				Meyer and Rowan (1977)
				DiMaggio and Powell (1983)
				Adaptive Complex Systems
				Walter F. Buckley (1968)
				Co-Evolution Theory
Environmental and Organizational Factors				James March (1991)
Organizational Internal and External Factors,				
In addition to managerial capabilities and roles,				
competitive abilities, capability building process,				
new organizational form and outcome.				

Source: Adopted by the researcher from Little (2019)

As environmental conditions change, additional factors that bind the external and internal environment should be explored comprehensively. The research on the relationship between organizations and their environments should encompass additional factors, and certain factors should be investigated more deeply. Several authors (Stewart, 2019; Khattak and Shah, 2020; Harsch and Festing, 2020; Walter, 2021; Gomes et al., 2022) noted that factors related to

management roles and capabilities are essential when investigating the relationship between organizations and their environments and the factors that influence this relationship, as management is considered the key link between several factors and the leading force of an organization in a particular environment.

Among organizational theories, co-evolutionary theory emerged as a new approach to understanding organization-environment relationships better and investigating organizational internal and external factors affecting organization-environment relationships (Qi et al., 2020; Shuffler, 2020; Pande et al., 2020; Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Bocken and Geradts, 2020; Garcia-Diaz and Peli., 2020; Kaipainen, 2020). Co-evolutionary theory examines both organizations and their environments, internal and external factors influencing their ability to remain fit, competitive, and co-evolve (Qi et al., 2020; Shuffler, 2020; Pande et al., 2020; Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Bocken and Geradts, 2020; Garcia-Diaz and Peli., 2020; Kaipainen, 2020). Co-evolutionary theory emphasizes management roles and capabilities and integrates additional internal and external factors to understand organizational relationships better (Cantele et al., 2020; Diaz and Peli, 2020; Mingione et al., 2020; Cristofaro et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Kompella, 2020; Walraven, 2020; Scazziota et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Sarta et al., 2021). Although co-evolutionary theory includes many factors discussed in the literature, a review of a number of co-evolutionary frameworks (Section 3.2) revealed that few of these factors were integrated in past research that studied the relationship between organizations and their environments in different fields. Table 3-2 presents factors examined using organizational frameworks, including co-evolutionary frameworks in past research.

Table 3-2: Organizational Frameworks Review Summary

Researcher (Publication Date)	Researcher Work	Factors Examined	Conclusion
Van Dyk and Van Belle (2020)	Technology Organization Environment Framework	Emerging technology and organizational readiness for the integration of new technology	Technology-organization-environment framework can investigate the readiness of Chinese construction companies to adopt new technologies, taking into consideration organizational and external environment factors.
Nair and Reed-Tsochas (2019)	Complex Adaptive System Framework	Organizational structures' continual interaction with their networks	Complex adaptive systems framework can enhance the interaction of organizations with other environmental actors in a specific landscape.
Treec e (2018)	Dynamic Capabilities Framework	Dynamic capability process	Dynamic capability framework can help organizations to identify suitable tools, techniques, and processes to reach this goal
Georgewill (2021)	Strategic Management Framework	Limited organizational and environmental factors	Strategic management framework can help in investigating and achieving structural flexibility and corporate responsiveness in the business
Vasylieva et al. (2013)	The Co-evolution of Firm Absorptive Capacity and Knowledge Environment Framework	Management capabilities, knowledge as a strategic asset, Absorbativ capacity, sense making ability	The framework can explain how knowledge can be obtained from an external organizational environment and used to develop organizational capabilities and generate new organizational forms.
Renard (2010)	Co-Evolution of Firm Capabilities and Industry Competition Framework	Search behavior, management capabilities, organizational dynamic capabilities n competitiveness	The framework is beneficial for analyzing organizational search behavior and determines organizations' co-evolution over time.
Fox (2011)	Co-Evolutionary Framework for Analyzing a Transition to a Sustainable Low-Carbon Economy	Technology, Organization strategies, management, co-evolutionary capability building process	The framework can identify dynamic interactions of social and technological elements of organizations on the micro and macro levels, and analyzing long-term industrial change due to a dynamic system based on the process of variation, selection, and retention and interactions between social and technological factors of organizations.
Kompella (2020)	Co-evolutionary framework to explore how organizations can enable radical product innovations in a competitive environment	Management capabilities, organizational outcome variation, capability building process, internal and external organizational factors	Co-evolutionary approach enable organizations to have better view, capabilities, and ability re-innovate their products and processes in a competitive environment

Source: The Researcher

Due to its comprehensiveness and need to encompass several factors on the micro and macro level, past co-evolutionary research has studied a limited number of internal and external factors and didn't focus on the mechanisms that bound them together. Prior co-evolutionary research was limited to a few factors and studied the essential organizational components of the co-evolutionary approach, and didn't extend to study the co-evolution of organizations on an industry scale (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020;

Chidlow, 2021). Past studies have examined various sets of external and internal factors that influence organizations' ability to maintain their fitness; however, they didn't offer a comprehensive approach that encompasses the main co-evolutionary approach components, such as management role, competition, capability building, organizational outcome, and new organizational forms (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021). Several authors (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Maula et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2021; Donnelly, 2021) suggested that new co-evolutionary research should be conducted, encompassing additional factors in future research.

Given the research gaps discussed in this section, it is clear that there is a need for a more comprehensive approach that can help organizations better understand their relationship with their environment and identify the main factors limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. In response, this research proposes developing a new co-evolutionary framework that addresses the essential factors organizations should investigate to construct a comprehensive overview of their organizational environment, make better decisions, and respond to environmental challenges.

3.5 Theoretical Framework Development

A theoretical framework illustrates a construct that combines different ideas that support the solution of research problems (Mensah et al., 2020). Further, theoretical frameworks reflect the paradigm shift a researcher uses to investigate specific phenomena (Mensah et al., 2020).

Referring to the research's main aim to investigate the challenges facing Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment, the researcher decided to develop a new co-evolutionary framework. The new Co-Evolutionary Framework proposes identifying the main factors limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment and providing a better understanding of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. After evaluating the literature review in Chapters 2 and 3 and the literature gap in Chapter 3, existing organizational frameworks and theories, six main factors were adopted to construct the conceptual framework in the present research. The six main factors are external organizational factors, internal organizational factors, managerial capabilities, organizational capabilities building process, competitiveness, and outcome.

Organizations do not operate independently in a vacuum medium; instead, organizations operate within an environment. Researchers considered that organizations could not be separated from their environment, as organizations belong to an environment in which organizations share their environmental conditions. Organizational environmental conditions consistently change, which results in additional pressure on organizations that operate in or relate to a specific environment. The altered environmental settings influence organizations' operations, fitness, and ability to compete, requiring the organization to make changes to align or adapt to the new environmental conditions. For that, several authors (Sarta et al., 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Stobierski, 2020; Aronsson et al., 2021; Walter, 2021) considered that organizations should focus on influencing internal and external factors in the environment since organizations operate in both internal and external environments. Co-evolution theory argues that there is an actor and reactor relation between an organization and its environment. Co-evolution, the theory suggests that an organization can also influence its environment, the same as its environment influences an organization and suggests

that a mutual influence exists between organizations and their environment. Thus, it is essential to identify the external and internal factors influencing organizations' abilities and capabilities. The internal and external environment were considered the basic components of the Co-Evolutionary Framework. In addition, since management is considered to have a significant role in managing the organization-environment relationship and their reciprocal co-evolution, the factors affecting management capabilities were investigated separately from the internal factors. An additional set of essential factors has been incorporated into the Co-Evolutionary Framework, which investigates the factors that affect organizational capabilities building, competitiveness, and outcome, which will be discussed further in this section.

Figure 3-8 Co-Evolutionary Theoretical Framework.

Source: The Researcher

3.5.1 Organizational External Factors

The first set of influencing factors relates to the external environment factors that exert pressure on an organization. The characteristics of an organization's environment are considered the primary source of external influences on organizations (Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Robertson et al., 2020; Sart et al., 2021). Identifying the external influencing factors of an organization is crucial to identifying the main factors that limit an organization to co-evolve with its environment (Chen et al., 2020; Shuffler, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020; Shattuck et al., 2020). Cantele et al. (2020) argued that increasing external pressure on organizations affected their ability

to sustain their operation and fitness within their environment. Bocken and Geradts (2020) emphasized the effect of external organizational factors on organizations' ability to compete with other rivals within their environment; thus, it is essential to continuously analyze the characteristics of the environment and the environmental actors that operate inside it. Several external organizational factors can influence organizations; however, each organization or landscape has a specific external factor that significantly influences it (Diaz and Peli., 2020; Kaipainen, 2020). In Literature, several external factors are considered by several researchers as the main external factors that can influence an organization and essential areas to investigate when examining the influencing external factors of an organization (Siddiqui, 2020; Matovic, 2020; Cox, 2020; Buye, 2021). Among these external organizational factors are: political, economic, social, technological, and ecological factors

Political factors. These factors relate to the status and characteristics of the political situation inside a country, local laws, regulations on trade, taxes, and tariffs (Fiumara and Boyle, 2020; CIPD, 2022).

Economic factors. These factors affect the organization through bank financing, interest rates, currency exchange rates, inflation, and human capital and energy costs (Fiumara and Boyle, 2020; CIPD, 2022).

Social factors. These factors relate to population structure, religious influence, national culture, educational status, and education organization (Matovic, 2020; CIPD, 2022).

Technological factors. These factors refer to the availability and adoption of various technologies within an organization (Shabalov et al., 2021). Technological factors also relate to essential

infrastructure, level of development, and organizational ability to use technological means to innovate (Shabalov et al., 2021; Yang and Gu, 2021).

Ecological factors. These factors relate to how humans deal with raw material processing, natural resources, control, and pollution reduction (Matovic, 2020; CIPD, 2022).

Legal factors. Such factors relate to laws, regulators, government requirements, standards needed to be satisfied within a specific country or industry, labor standards, and capital flows (CIPD, 2022; Cox, 2020; Buye, 2021).

3.5.2 Internal Influencing Factors

The second set of influencing factors relates to the internal organizational factors. The characteristics of the internal environment are as important as the external factors that influence organizations' capabilities and determine their strengths and weaknesses. (Satyendra, 2020; Uchebo, 2020). Through the lens of co-evolutionary theory, internal organizational factors determine the organization's ability to make necessary changes as a response to external influences (Fox, 2020; Robert et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Das et al., 2020; Eliakis et al., 2020). Understanding the internal factors of an organization is key to identifying the main factors that limit or elevate an organization's interaction with its environment, especially in the presence of external influences (Fox, 2020; Robert et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Das et al., 2020; Eliakis et al., 2020). Edmondson et al. (2020) considered that organizations' internal factors should be continually re-evaluated and re-innovated to face external changes. Hoppmann (2020) argued that if the external factors exerted from outside the organization are limited compared to the internal factors of an organization, this can allow an organization to affect its environmental setting. Several organizational internal factors shape the abilities of an organization, its response, and its

position within its environment; however, each organization has its unique factors that shape the internal environment of each organization, which affect its overall process, performance, and sustainability (Jung et al., 2020; Scharlemann et al., 2020; Cuming and Epstein, 2020). Organizational structure, value system, physical, financial, and technological resources, mission and objectives plan and policies, and culture are considered the main internal factors that significantly affect an organization's internal environment (Bhasin, 2020; Surbhi, 2020; Vanessa, 2020).

Organizational structure. Organizational structure determines the structure of the board, management, and shareholders (Basila et al., 2018; Gerged et al., 2021). An organization's structure is believed to affect its ability to make decisions and relates to how knowledge and processes are tracked inside an organization (Margherita and Braccini 2020).

Value System. The organizational values system is related to the organization's philosophy (Jacobson et al., 2022). The firm's value system includes work processes, culture, laws, climate, and work processes (Santa-Maria et al., 2022; Jacobson et al., 2022)

Physical Resources. Organizational physical resources include machinery, equipment, buildings, tools, offices, raw materials, supplies, and other tangible assets (Ofor-Douglas, 2022). Organizational physical resources include physical assets a company needs to operate, develop its capabilities, expand operations, and deliver services and products (Autio et al., 2021).

Technological capabilities. Organizational technological capabilities refer to the availability and adoption of various technologies inside an organization (Al Hadwer et al., 2021). Technological factors also relate to adopting essential, advanced infrastructure and tools to generate an outcome (Jacob et al., 2020; Al Hadwer et al., 2021; Kim and Yang, 2021).

Mission and Objectives. These factors relate to an organization's goals and objectives and can determine its current and future position in its environment (Nabella et al., 2022).

Organizational culture. Organizational culture defines the beliefs, values, and assumptions that management and employees adhere to and helps identify specific social and psychological norms (Calciolari and Prenestini., 2022). Organizational culture affects many things inside an organization, from how employees interact with each other to how key decisions are made (White, 2020; Calciolari and Prenestini., 2022).

Financial resources. Financial resources determine an organization's total capital or cash flow (Zakirova et al., 2020). A financially stable organization has more freedom to develop its capabilities and grow and explore new markets, whereas it is challenging for organizations to grow their operations with limited financial resources (Chen et al., 2021; Surbhi, 2020).

In addition, organizational plans and policies are developed to achieve company goals, establish discipline in the organization, and create an organizational image linked to the reputation and value of the company's brand in the market (Fuertes et al., 2020; Bocken and Geradts, 2020).

3.5.3 Management Capabilities

The third set of factors relates to the managerial capabilities of an organization. The role of management in an organization is an essential and crucial internal factor. Co-evolutionary theory considers management as the midpoint between an organization's external and internal environment (Shatilo, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022). Co-evolutionary theory considers management the leading force of change and the central part of the co-evolutionary process of an organization (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021). For that, co-

evolutionary theory gives additional value to management capabilities that affect the ability of an organization to manage the interaction between organizations and their environment and their response to external influences (Ciampi et al., 2022; Abatecola et al., 2022). Co-evolutionary theory suggests that if management has limited or lacks essential characteristics, it can negatively influence the co-evolutionary process of an organization, for it is essential for management to continually re-assess their abilities, knowledge, and skills to face changing environmental conditions (Haarhaus and Liening, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022; Abatecola et al., 2022). Co-evolutionary theory suggests that bounded rationality, lack of strategic intentionality, and search behavior are the main factors that affect management capabilities inside an organization (Haarhaus and Liening, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022; Abatecola et al., 2022). For that, these factors were integrated into the Co-Evolutionary Framework developed by the researcher in this research.

Bounded Rationality. Bounded rationality suggests that managers have internal cognitive limitations to control their ability to identify all the possibilities, calculate the uncertainty of external events, and evaluate the consequences of their results (Kotlar and Sieger 2019; Hong, 2020).

Strategic Intentionality. Managerial intentionality is a central cognitive component that key managers focus on at the individual level (Nenonen and Storbacka, 2020; Pedersen and Ritter, 2022). Cognitive and managerial behavior can be evaluated by studying organizations' managerial intentionality (Heubeck and Meckl, 2022).

Search Behavior. In a competitive context, rivals may choose explorative or exploitative research behavior to build organizational capabilities (Nel et al., 2020; Castillo Apraiz et al., 2021). An

exploratory research methodology employs techniques, strategies, and knowledge in order to find new alternatives to existing organizational capabilities (Ceipek et al., 2021; Lei et al., 2021). In contrast, exploitative search behavior does not provide innovative products, processes, or new capabilities; instead, it involves improving existing capabilities and updating organizational processes and technologies (Nel et al., 2020; Castillo Apraiz et al., 2021).

3.5.4 Organization's Capability Building Process

The fourth set of influencing factors relates to factors affecting an organization's capability building process. Developing an organization's capabilities is essential for its co-evolutionary process (Ferreira et al., 2020; Al Hadwer et al., 2021). Co-evolution theory aims to identify the main factors limiting organizations' ability to co-evolve with their environment (Paniccia and Baiocco, 2018; Kompella, 2020). The identification of the main factors that limit the organization's abilities or capabilities is essential in a competitive environment, in which the organization has to compete with other organizations which are also enhancing their capabilities to compete better and stay fit (Lorenzo et al., 2018; Tereece, 2020; Asghari, 2020; Duchek, 2020). In order to study the capability building process of an organization, it is necessary to adopt a proper capability building process and to investigate its outcome. The capability refinement or dynamic capability process used by an organization may affect its organizational outcomes by resulting in the creation or re-innovation of its capabilities (Lorenzo et al., 2018; Tereece, 2020; Asghari, 2020; Duchek, 2020).

Organizational Capability Building Process. Understanding the capability building processes of an organization is key to identifying how organizations' capabilities are continually developed and what factors affect the capability building process inside an organization (Duchek, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Dzhengiz, 2020). The capability-building process allows an organization to achieve a

sustainable advantage and determines the ability of an organization to convert the input obtained from the external environment and generate better or new output back into the environment (Sarta et al., 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020; Duchek, 2020). According to Ceipek et al. (2020) determining the capability building process is essential for organizations, particularly in changing environmental conditions, when organizations must continually improve and renew their abilities and capabilities to remain agile and competitive against other environmental actors. Several authors (Zhang, 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2020; Cristofaro, 2022) considered that the selection-retention-variation mechanism determines the development of an organization's capabilities. Co-evolutionary theory embraces organizational capabilities' continual renewal and development (Pillath and Hederer, 2022; Cristofaro, 2022). Co-evolution theory provides the selection-retention and variation mechanism for organizations to continuously re-innovate their capabilities (Zhang, 2020; Gabora and Steel, 2021; Herrmann-Pillath and Hederer, 2022; Cristofaro, 2022). The selection process can occur when an organization selects a new capability, resource, or process from its environment purposefully and then decides to integrate or replace it with what exists inside the organization and then transforms it into a new variant back in the environment (Herrmann-Pillath and Hederer, 2022; Cristofaro, 2022). Co-evolutionary theory recommends the continuous adoption of this mechanism as a routine inside an organization to make necessary changes and development as the organizational environment is constantly changing (Haider et al., 2021; Zhang, 2020; Gabora and Steel, 2021; Herrmann-Pillath and Hederer, 2022; Abatecola et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2020).

Refinement of Capabilities. Organizations should continuously pursue renewal or re-innovation of their existing capabilities, to create new capabilities or offer innovative outcomes for competition (Li et al., 2021; Mirega, 2020). Zhang (2021) considered that organizations limit their

capability building process to refinement and tuning in their existing capabilities, which results in incremental development in the internal environment of an organization. An organization's capability refinement is limited to improving its capabilities by re-combining resources and adopting new strategies for exploiting its existing resources and assets (Gama et al., 2020; Ferreira and Coelho, 2020; Li et al., 2021; Mirega, 2020). Refinement of capabilities is another alternative to an innovative approach by which an organization cannot allocate new resources or build new capabilities. If the capabilities refinement approach is adopted solely, this will decrease the organization's competitiveness, especially in a competitive environment where other environmental actors pursue innovation (Ferreira and Coelho, 2020).

Dynamic Capabilities Processes. By contrast to capability refinement, capability creation involves an organization's exploitative search behavior, which is not limited to replicable or immutable capabilities, as well as an attempt to build new innovative capabilities (Paavola, 2021). Dynamic capability building enhances an organization's competitiveness by adding new innovative features that can be considered an advantage over other rivals (Carvalho et al., 2021). Capability creation can ensure that the organization is not using repetitive processes or routines available and can be obtained by competitors (Wu et al., 2020; Carvalho et al., 2021). Teece (2020) introduced the term 'Dynamic capability' to describe the capability building process inside an organization.

3.5.5 Competition Factors

The fifth set of influencing factors relates to factors that affect an organization's ability to compete in its environment. An organization's competitive factors are essential for assessing its competitiveness and factors that affect its ability to compete with other rivals in its environment (La Falce et al., 2020; Min et al., 2020; Alfaro-Saiz et al., 2020). The researcher adopted

competitive factors since they allow the researcher to determine the factors that shape an organization's competitiveness as the research investigates organizational co-evolution within a competitive environment (Kumar et., 2019; Kompella, 2020; Teece, 2020; Eum and lee, 2020; Cantele et al., 2020; Sarta, 2021). Determining the competitive factors of organizations will allow the researcher to identify factors limiting an organization from the competition and identify the competitive strategy adopted by an organization, which will reveal new insights and findings on the co-evolution of the higher education institutions environment (Kumar et., 2019; Kompella, 2020; Petit and Teece, 2020; Eum and lee, 2020; Cantele et al., 2020; Sarta, 2021). Through co-evolution theory, organizations should be able to enhance their abilities and compete with other organizations in their environment (Petit and Teece, 2020; Eum and lee, 2020; Cantele et al., 2020; Sarta, 2021). The main factors that limit the capabilities of an organization should be identified to understand the relation between the organization and its environment and have suitable responses to achieve co-evolution with its environment, which enhances its ability to compete and stay fit in a competitive landscape (Kumar et., 2019; Kompella, 2020; Petit and Teece, 2020).

The ever-changing environments conditions have shift strategic approaches adopted by organizations' management and the processes followed to achieve the desired outcome (Zainol et al., 2021; Nadkarni and Prugl, 2020; Tronvoll et al., 2020). Different models were introduced to realize the factors affecting an organization's competitiveness and relationship to its environment (Nagano, 2019; Singh et al., 2021; Davis and Dewitt, 2021). Two fundamental perspectives affect organizational competitiveness: resource and knowledge-based approaches (Nagano, 2019; Sugiarno and Novita, 2022; Davis and Dewitt, 2021).

Resource-based view. Resource-based theory links an organization's competitive advantage to its existing resources and capabilities that are difficult to imitate by other organizations (Sugiarno and

Novita, 2022). In the lens of Resource-based view, organizational competitive advantage is built on an organization's ability to exploit its resources and capabilities relative to external environmental changes (Davis and Dewitt, 2021). Based on the resource-based view ensuring that the organization possesses value, rareness, and immutability and can organize its resources to enhance its competitive advantage (Freeman et al., 2021).

Knowledge-based view. Knowledge-based theory holds that knowledge is a strategic resource of an organization that is difficult to duplicate and determines its sustained competitive advantage and performance (Grant and Phene, 2022). Information technologies are key elements of the knowledge-based view of an organization, which can be used to integrate, upgrade, and accelerate large-scale knowledge management (Plekhanov et al., 2022). Therefore, organizations need to identify, improve, and employ their knowledge to enhance their operations, improve their processes, and deliver their outcomes (Plekhanov et al., 2022; Davis and Dewitt, 2021).

3.5.6 Organizational Outcome

The sixth set of factors are related to factors that affect an organization's outcome. The outcome of an organization is considered an essential factor when investigating the co-evolution of an organization since the outcome of an organization determines the variations of products and services it can provide inside its environment (Chan et al., 2019; Riasanow et al., 2019; Qi et al., 2020; Da Costa and Horn, 2021; Cristofaro, 2022; Eum and Lee, 2022). Organizational outcome can determine the degree of verification, newness and innovativeness of offered products or services (Qi et al., 2020). Organizational outcome characteristics can reveal organizations' capabilities, capability-building process, resources, and ability to compete within their environment (Da Costa and Horn, 2021; Cristofaro, 2022). Lindfors and Jakobsen et al. (2022)

suggested that organizational outcome variation can reposition an organization, add new features to its offering, and enhance its ability to compete. An organization's outcome can affect its ability to provide a new organizational form within its environment (Cristofaro, 2022; Eum and Lee, 2022). An organization's ability to verify its outcome and provide new organizational forms can determine its ability to co-evolve with its environment (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Lindfors and Jakobsen et al. 2022). For that, organizations' abilities to vary their products and services and provide new organizational forms are the primary factors that determine organizational outcomes in a specific environment (Riasanow et al., 2019; Abatecola et al., 2020; Lindfors and Jakobsen et al. 2022).

Organizational outcome variation. Organizational outcomes can be varied by offering variants of the same product or service or different versions of the same product, distinguished by their features (Clauss et al., 2021; Cyfert et al., 2022). An organization's outcome variation adds new features that can enhance products and services characteristics, type and quality inside an environment (Cyfert et al., 2022). Variations in organizational outcomes add new attributes to an organization, expand its offering and influence, give it a new function and role, and enhance its competitiveness (Lindfors and Jakobsen et al. 2022). An organization's continuous renewal of variations enhances its fitness, sustainability, and ability to co-evolve with its environment (Tece, 2020). Duchek (2020) stated that an organization's outcome reveals the organization's capability building, processes, routines, and resources used inside an organization. Contrary to genetic variations in biology, which are the product of random combinations and mutation processes, organizational variations emerge as an adaptive response to altered external environment settings, the variation of an organization's outcome results from purposeful selection (Abatecola et al., 2020).

New organizational form. The variation offered by the organization can be a new creative design, process, or knowledge that can be combined with the capabilities and resources of the organization to offer a differentiated product or service (Ochie et al., 2020). By leveraging technological capabilities, organizations are able to create new mediums and virtual forms of organization and offer new products to customers in existing or new environments (McKelvey, 2022). The ability to combine organizations' capabilities and generate new models, designs, and routines, taking advantage of internal resources and outsourcing what is needed outside, allows organizations to generate new forms of organizations (Lanzolla et al., 2020). New organizational forms may not replace the current ones but rather may be used by or with the original organization to expand market presence, improve competitiveness, and offer an alternative organizational outcome (Joseph and Gaba, 2020; Arokodare and Falana, 2021; Volberda et al., 2021). New organizational forms are being created continuously to allow organizations to sustain their operations, compete, and co-evolve with their environment, especially in the virtual world, where organizations need to have a virtual presence (Volberda et al., 2021).

In addition, additional factors were added regarding the influence of universities' location, historical development, organizational development compared to local, regional and global landscape, which are considered by several scholars (Ritter, T. and Pedersen, 2020; Stoermer et al., 2021; Ferreira et al., 2020; Belderbos et al., 2020; Ahlstrom et al., 2020; Paunovic et al., 2020) important to explore the interactions between organizations and their environments and their co-evolution.

3.6 Conclusion

In the current chapter, the researcher discussed classical, modern, and post-modern organizational theories, their development, and transition to encompass organizational environments as an

essential component of studying organizations. The chapter discusses the main factors organizations focus on and how such theories construct a view of the relationship between organizations and their environment. The researcher also discussed the development phases of organizational theories and the effect of technology and globalization on existing approaches. In addition, the researcher reviewed existing organizational frameworks, which focus on the relationship between an organization's internal and external environments, along with other co-evolutionary approaches. After reviewing the existing organizational theories and frameworks related to the present research, the researcher decided that developing a new Co-Evolutionary Framework would be beneficial to achieve the present research objectives and aim. The new framework will include additional factors, and provide better understanding and provide more comprehensiveness of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. After discussing the development of the Co-Evolutionary Framework, the following section presents the methodology adopted in this research.

Chapter Four: Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

Determining an appropriate and applicable research methodology is essential to any research. A suitable methodology determines the research approach, research design, collecting, analyzing data, and concluding results (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Sileyew, 2019). Identifying the most appropriate research methodology allows researchers to achieve the research aim, objectives, answer the research questions, and ensure credible and valid results (Thompson et al., 2021). Sileyew (2019) highlighted the importance of consistency between research questions and approaches as an essential characteristic of methodological and theoretical research. In this chapter, the researcher discusses the methodology adopted in this research concerning the research objectives and questions mentioned in Chapter 1 (Section 1.4). The present research adopts the 'Research Onion Model' (Susanto et al., 2020).

Figure 4-1 The Research Onion Model

Source: Susanto (2020)

4.2 Research Philosophy

This section presents the research philosophy adopted in this research and describes the research methodology adopted for this research. Research philosophy reflects significant assumptions about how researchers view the world (Zukauskas et al., 2018; Aguas, 2022). Kamal (2019) believed that each philosophy is a paradigm encompassing the researcher's worldview and belief system. The consideration of philosophical fundamentals is essential in any research process to ensure that the researcher remains aware of his role in the research and does not bring his beliefs and assumptions to this work (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Creswell and Creswell, 2019).

Ontology. According to Saunders et al. (2019) ontology deals with individuals' assumptions about reality and asks individuals about what is needed to be identified outside themselves. Williamson and Johanson (2017) noted that ontology mainly deals with the perceptions and assumptions of reality constructed by individuals, answers the question of what needs to be known, and identifies how social reality is constructed.

Epistemology. According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2021) epistemology reflects what individuals know about their surroundings and the method they use to acquire their knowledge. Epistemology helps the researcher identify existing knowledge, its sources, and limitations, which assist the researcher in focusing on what is possible to know and how to reach this knowledge (Dawadi et al., 2021; Gray, 2021). Research paradigms can be conceived in social science research by four main paradigms: positivist, interpretivist, radical structuralist, and radical humanist (Bonache and Festing 2020). Each paradigm refers to a different perception and view of reality that can generate distinct concepts, theories, and analytical tools (Creswell and Creswell, 2019). In social research, positivism and interpretivism are considered the main research paradigms that any researcher can

adopt (Kankam, 2019; Easterby-Smith et al., 2019; Bogna et al., 2020). Positivism considers that reality is the construction of individual rationality, validity, and truth derived from individual observation and experimentation (Erciyes, 2020). Positivism considers that knowledge can be accessed directly using natural science methods based on the assumption that reality is objective (Kalelioglu, 2020; Scauso, 2020).

On the other hand, interpretivism believes that subjective interpretation of the researched problem helps the researcher gain more understanding and gives insights that can benefit his research findings (Creswell and Creswell 2019). Mulisa (2022) believed that reality is based on the observer's analysis, giving subjective meaning and interpretations. According to Easterby-Smith et al., (2019) proposed that interpretivism recognizes reality as the product of social actors that construct reality based on their interpretation of the meanings they generate. Thus, reality is reconstructed continuously as individual experiences and interactions with the world change, constructing an individual's view of the world (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2019). Interpretivism assumes that a better understanding of any investigated phenomenon can be achieved through the perceptions and experiences of individuals related to the area of study (Lanka et al., 2021).

Throughout this research, the researcher acknowledges that different individuals hold different beliefs, viewpoints, and views regarding the same events, circumstances, or phenomena. For that, interpretivism is used in this research to explore participants' meanings, thoughts, and perceptions to understand better the phenomenon being investigated (Shufutinsky, 2020).

The researcher in this research intends to capture the perception, thoughts, and knowledge about the nature of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment to gain better insights and understanding. Since reality is reconstructed continuously as individual experiences

and interactions between different actors in a specific time and location, the researcher adopted research paradigm in the current research (Kaushik and Walsh 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2019). The interpretive research paradigm proposes that reality can be comprehended based on individuals' subjective points of view rather than objective observation and action (Bogna et al., 2020). This will help the researcher construct a better and general view of the investigated phenomena, based on the perceived reality and thoughts of the main actors and influencers of the investigated phenomena.

4.3 Research Approach

The current section discusses the selection of inductive reasoning and its benefits for this research. Creswell and Creswell (2019) noted that illustrating the importance of having an appropriate approach to any research increases validity. Deductive and inductive approaches are considered key methods of logical relearning in social science research (Bryman et al., 2018; Bougie and Sekaran et al., 2019). Inductive reasoning is a bottom-up approach that starts with the researcher's observations analysis to identify recurring patterns and eventually draw meaningful conclusions (Bryman et al., 2018; Varpio et al., 2020).

Qualitative methods are usually associated with inductive reasoning, contrary to quantitative methods, which are usually equated with deductive reasoning (Tashakkori et al., 2020; Clark et al., 2021; Levitt, 2021; Thomas, 2021; Maxwell, 2021).

In this research, the researcher adopted an inductive approach. By its very nature, inductive reasoning is considered more exploratory, while deductive reasoning is based on a narrow focus and testing hypotheses (Bryman et al., 2018). Selecting an inductive approach will allow research results to be derived from discovering the meanings of research participants instead of testing the hypothesis. By adopting the inductive approach, the findings of this research will be generated

based on exploring the research problem, which allows for a general abstract about the investigated phenomena to be constructed (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021).

Kansteiner and Konig (2020) proposed that inductive approach will determine frequent, recurring patterns or themes from the collected raw data. Reger and Kincaid (2021) noted that in research key themes are ambiguous and restructured due to biases in data collection and analysis methods imposed by deductive data analysis used in empirical and hypothesis testing research. Thus, this will help the researcher in this research to identify recurring patterns, generate meaningful data, identify themes, and answer the research questions. Thus, the present research adopted the inductive approach to collect, analyze, identify themes, and answer the research questions.

Figure 4-2 Inductive vs. Deductive Reasoning

Source: Scribbr (2022)

4.4 Methodological Choice

Research methodology aims to determine which research methods are appropriate for collecting and analyzing data that should meet the philosophical assumption of the selected paradigm (Taherdoost et al., 2022). Dawadi et al. (2021) noted that researchers are predisposed to a single or set of research methods. Mulisa et al., (2018) argued that any researcher needs to understand qualitative and quantitative methods to determine the suitable methodology for research.

According to Chali et al. (2022) qualitative research depends on words as a data source, contrary to quantitative research based on numerical data. Quantitative research analyzes data using statistical tools and techniques (Chali et al., 2022). Saunders et al. (2019) believed that quantitative research deals with the collection of numerical data or the analysis processes that produce numbers that have value; however, qualitative research produces non-numerical data based on the perceptions produced by the participant's mind. In contrast, quantitative methods are based on linear attributes, statistics, and other calculation or measurement techniques (Saunders et al., 2019). It was concluded by Easterby-Smith et al. (2019) that words and numbers, through the research process, relate to constructivism and a relativistic ontology during the research process. Taherdoost (2022) suggested that qualitative methods can be adopted in various science fields to help explore individuals' perceptions, experiences, and thoughts about certain phenomena.

In this research, the researcher adopted qualitative research methods because they can provide several contextual and applicable views in practice, which can diversify and validate research results. The adopted interpretivism and inductive approaches align with the qualitative methods used in this research. Qualitative approaches involve collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data that are not easily reduced to numbers (Vivek and Nanthagopan, 2021). On the contrary, the quantitative method does not unveil deeper underlying meaning and explanation. The quantitative method quantifies how social reality is constructed or how people interpret it, which results in a partial understanding of the investigated phenomenon (Dawadi et al., 2021; Vivek and Nanthagopan, 2021; Mulisa, 2022). Qualitative methods will yield diverse viewpoints in this research, thus providing varied and justified outcomes from the semi-structured interviews and then assimilated altogether (Dawadi et al., 2021; Vivek and Nanthagopan, 2021; Mulisa, 2022).

4.5 Research Strategy

In this section, the researcher discusses key concepts and explains the choice of a case study strategy for this research. The research strategy provides clear guidance on how a researcher conducts research (Vears and Gillam, 2022). According to Saunders et al. (2019) a research strategy identifies the main components of the research area, perspective, and design, as well as how the researcher intends to implement his methodology and answer the research questions. Alam et al. (2021) believed that research strategy is closely related to data collection and analysis methods. The researcher selected the current research case study strategy for data collection.

4.5.1 Case Study Strategy

In management and organizational research, case studies, surveys, experiments, and action research are considered appropriate research strategies (Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Alam et al., 2021). Several researchers (Tomaszewski, 2020; Hancock, 2021; Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021) emphasized the flexibility of the case study strategy and considered it a common research strategy in various social sciences research to gather data about a specific phenomenon. A case study is a suitable strategy for investigating certain phenomena because it allows researchers to use multiple evidence sources for data collection (Tomaszewski, 2020; Hancock, 2021; Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021). The flexibility provided by using case studies is widely recognized and considered one of its main advantages, by allowing the researcher to decide the boundaries of researched phenomena and provides multiple methods for collecting data (Bentzen et al., 2021; Michel-Villarreal 2021; Sayfutdinov et al., 2022).

The researcher adopted a case study as the research strategy in this research. There are few studies that investigate the relationship between universities and their environments. Given the explorative nature of the research, a case study strategy is considered appropriate to investigate this phenomenon and seek new insights (Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Saunders et al., 2019). In-depth interviews can be used in the case study method as a data collection method that generates in-depth and rich information (Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Saunders et al., 2019). In this research, the researcher aims to comprehensively understand the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and identify the factors limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Schoch (2020) argued that a case study strategy is suitable for researchers who seek a comprehensive and in-depth investigation of a specific phenomenon using data from many sources. Because of its peculiarities, the single case study strategy does not meet the basic requirements of this research. Therefore, the researcher adopted the multiple case studies strategy to explore a variety of cases in Lebanese higher education field to identify the main factors limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. In this research, adopting multiple case studies will allow the researcher to collect and analyze findings from different Lebanese universities to provide replication logic and rich information to confirm or validate the findings. Multiple case studies are selected because they provide rich data from multiple resources, can cover multiple realities to draw conclusions better and establish a chain of evidence, which enhances the analytical generalizability of findings (Rashid et al., 2019; Aspers and Corte, 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Saunders et al., 2019; Tomaszewski, 2020; Hancock, 2021; Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021). Thus, using a single case study strategy will result in incomplete conclusions based on one university's perceptions, thoughts, beliefs, and experiences (Tomaszewski, 2020; Hancock, 2021; Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021). Using a

single case will generate a partial understanding of the investigated phenomena (Tomaszewski, 2020; Hancock, 2021; Stoecker and Avila, 2021; Akerblad et al., 2021). This research attempts to understand better the factors that limit higher education institutions' co-evolution with their environment. This research is exploratory, and an exploratory, multiple case study strategy is considered appropriate to investigate higher education institutions' challenges and seek new insights (Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Saunders et al., 2019). Lebanese universities were selected as case studies, allowing the researcher to have a more detailed, varied, and extensive comprehension of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment from multiple data sources in the higher education field.

Twenty-six Lebanese universities were chosen from Lebanese higher education field. In the present research, Lebanese universities were selected based on operation location, years in the education field, number of schools, and offered programs. Universities operating in Lebanon and which have been part of Lebanese higher education field in the past ten years, have three schools or more, and offer more than fifteen programs were selected for this research. Table 4-1 shows the number of Lebanese universities and participants from each university.

Table 4-1 Lebanese Universities Participants

Univeristy no.	No. Participants
University 1	2
University 2	2
University 3	2
University 4	2
University 5	2
University 6	2
University 7	2
University 8	2
University 9	2
University 10	2
University 11	2
University 12	2
University 13	2
University 14	1
University 15	1
University 16	1
University 17	1
University 18	1
University 19	1
University 20	1
University 21	1
University 22	1
University 23	1
University 24	1
University 25	1
University 26	1

Source: The Researcher

4.6 Data Collection

In the current section, the researcher discusses the technique used to collect data, the research interview design, the process, and the participants' selection for this research.

4.6.1 Data Collection Technique

In this research, the researcher selected interviews as the main data collection technique. Interviews are concerned with exploring data based on individuals' perceptions, knowledge, and experience relevant to the investigated phenomena (Schoch, 2020). As this research aims to better understand the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment, interviews were selected as the suitable data collection technique. Muzari and Shonhiwa (2022) believed in-depth interviews aim to capture unique data, develop mature thoughts, and uncover issues not observed by the respondents or others. Easterby-Smith et al. (2019) considered that in-depth interviews could be used to identify the meanings individuals give to a specific matter, as well as assumptions, beliefs, and attitudes. Sanders et al. (2019) believed that unstructured, semi-structured, and fully structured interviews are the three main types of interviews used by any researcher. In the present research, the researcher used a semi-structured interview. According to Alam (2021) a structured interview is a systematic questioning approach that enables researchers to collect relevant information about the researched topic. In structured interviews, the researcher prepares a set of ordered questions to ask the research respondents (Roberts, 2020). An unstructured interview is considered a more open-ended technique that allows respondents to share their thoughts, experiences, and knowledge about a particular subject (Croucher and Cronn-Mills, 2021). On the other hand, semi-structured interviews enable the researcher to set premeditated questions, allowing the researcher to explore new developments, ideas, insights, and knowledge during the interview (Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021).

In the present research, semi-structured interviews were adopted for data collection. The balance between formal and informal conversational approaches that semi-structured interviews offer

allows researchers to delve deeper into participants' answers, discover new clues, and add valuable insights to the interview process (Ruslin et al., 2022). Semi-structured interviews allow researchers to answer open-ended questions about "what and how" and learn about participants' interpretations and perspectives on the investigated phenomenon (Croswell and Croswell, 2019). Knott et al. (2022) emphasized the significance of the explicit study of topics discussed, raised, and explored newly emerged topics during semi-structured interviews. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews enable the researcher to objectively compare data collected from the research respondents and provide an opportunity to explore potential topics related to the investigated phenomena (Taherdoost et al., 2020).

At this stage, after completing the interview guide, the participant informal sheet, and receiving the university's ethical approval for the present research from the university ethical comity, the researcher started his data collection phase by setting a plan to effectively contact research participants according to the location of the university they represent. At each university, the researcher contacted the suitable representative provided to assist and communicate with external individuals or parties outside the university. University receptionists and managers' secretaries were considered the primary contact points at Lebanon's universities. The researcher filled out each university's required forms and applications to request interviews with the universities' managers and provided research forms. Due to the pandemic, universities' responses were delayed and took additional time. Some universities took at least three weeks to respond and others a month to reply, while other managers that had set dates for interviewing canceled or delayed the interview for another time. The researcher continually readjusted his interview schedule and process to keep aligned with the planned interview time and overall research process.

Telephone interviews have become the standard method of conducting interviews in recent years (Moises, 2020; Gray et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2021). Through telephone calls, participants can reduce the time spent on several steps in the interview process; the preparation phase is one example, and participants can choose the appropriate place to research (Moises, 2020; Gray et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2021). The use of telephone or virtual calls can save the research processes by offering an alternative to doing interviews under challenging situations, especially in situations where interviews may be canceled or postponed, due to the difficulty of meeting or being present in the required place, which can affect the research process negatively, delay or stop it (Moises, 2020; Gray et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2021; De Villiers et al., 2022). In the present research, the researcher conducted interviews through virtual Skype and phone calls. The spread of Coronavirus worldwide, especially in Lebanon, delayed the interview process in this research. Many interviews were postponed or canceled due to physical meetings' difficulty; telephone calls facilitated the interview process by providing an alternative method to conduct interviews.

4.6.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

In this section, the researcher presents the data analysis technique applied to analyze the qualitative data collected for the present research.

According to Creswell and Creswell (2019) the determinant of the appropriate data analysis tools depends on the methods used to collect data, research conditions, and expected results. The present research used thematic analysis to analyze the qualitative data collected. According to Jain (2021) in exploratory research, the interaction between the researcher and respondents is essential since attention is given to what emerges between the researcher and the respondents. The interaction between the researcher and the respondents results in the identification of emerging themes of the current phenomena or new themes for more comprehensive results (Allan, 2020; Alam, 2021).

This research used thematic analysis to interpret the meaning of the participants' beliefs and perceptions to comprehend better the nature of the phenomenon being investigated. Thematic analysis is considered an appropriate tool to analyze the qualitative data collected in this research. Thematic analysis is considered an interpretative approach used to analyze qualitative data, which facilitates identifying and analyzing patterns or themes in a given data set (Braun and Clarke, 2022). Ozuem et al (2022) considered qualitative data as collected words or text to be analyzed to identify research respondent's ideas, thoughts and perceptions of a specific topic. Thematic analysis is typically used to examine collected data and identify common themes, similar patterns, thoughts, or repeated topics (Silverman, 2019). The thematic analysis technique is compatible with constructionist epistemology (Kiger and Varpio, 2020; Xu and Zammit, 2020; Wiltshire and Ronkainen, 2021; Braun and Clarke 2022; Ozuem et al., 2022). A theme is a central concept derived from grouping or categorizing identified similar data (Kiger and Varpio, 2020; Xu and Zammit, 2020). A code is a representation of a theme or a concept, while coding is the process of replacing or linking codes to data segments (Kiger and Varpio, 2020; Xu and Zammit, 2020; Wiltshire and Ronkainen, 2021; Braun and Clarke 2022). To structure the qualitative data analysis in this research, the researcher considered the six-stage thematic analysis method most suitable for the present research (Peel, 2020; Kiger and Varpio, 2020; Xu and Zammit, 2020; Wiltshire and Ronkainen, 2021; Braun and Clarke 2022). The six stages are: 1. Familiarization, 2. Coding, 3. Generating themes, 4. Deriving common themes 5. Categorizing 6. Defining and naming themes 7. Writing up the themes for analysis.

In the first stage of thematic analysis, the researcher reviewed the collected data, read them several times, and took notes to be more familiar with the collected qualitative data from the research interviews. Secondly, the collected data is coded by highlighted sections in the transcripts and then

labeled to give a clear and meaningful description of the coded data. In the third stage, the researcher identified the recurring patterns in the collected data. At this stage, several codes related to the exact meaning are combined into a single theme. At the third stage, the identified themes are then analyzed individually and compared to other identified themes to merge similar themes. Themes, including influencing factors regarding the internal and external organizational environment, capability building process, competition, and outcome, are then reviewed to ensure that the identified themes accurately represent the collected data. After that, the identified themes are labeled and defined to formulate meaning for each theme to help understand the data. In the fourth stage, the identified themes are analyzed in chapter 5 and then discussed in chapter 6.

Figure 4-3 Qualitative Data Coding

Source: Adopted by the researcher from Rosala (2022)

4.7 Design of Research Interview

In this section, the researcher presents the process he followed to develop the interview questions. The research interview included nineteen open-ended questions and was divided into nine sections. Roberts (2020) suggested varying the type of questions in in-depth interviews using direct, indirect, and follow-up questions. The interview structure of the present research is based on the themes identified in Chapter 3 and is designed to answer the research questions. The present research's interview questions are developed based on the main seven themes, constituting the Co-Evolutionary Framework developed in the present research. Each set of interview questions

investigates one theme and inquiries about the factors that affect this particular theme, summarized in the below section, and included in Appendix B. After collecting and analyzing data, all emerging ideas from the research participants will be integrated into the Co-Evolutionary Framework to help develop it, as presented in Chapter 6.

- The first section included questions to address the perception of the relationship between Lebanese university and their environment.
- The second section included questions about the external environmental factors affecting Lebanese universities.
- The third section included questions about internal organizational factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.
- This fourth section includes open-ended questions about Lebanese universities' management capabilities and responses to changing environmental conditions.
- The fifth section included open-ended questions about Lebanese universities' capabilities and capability-building processes.
- The sixth section included open-ended questions about factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to compete.
- The seventh section included questions about the outcome of Lebanese universities and how it relates to the co-evolution process.
- The eighth section includes open-ended questions about additional factors that add more understanding of the co-evolution processes of Lebanese universities, recommended by several co-evolutionary researchers.
- The ninth section consists of an open-ended question concerning other factors that should be considered in investigating the co-evolution of Lebanese universities.

4.7.1 Selection of Interviewees

Saunders et al. (2019) believed that data collection is better derived from a purposeful sampling method or strategy. When sampling is not generalized, it is considered judgmental sampling, which aims to understand better the investigated phenomena (Levitt, 2021). Sample selection should be based on suitable respondents who can contribute rich and varied data (Creswell and Creswell, 2019). Thirty-nine participants were selected to provide the required data to construct a general view of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and identify the challenges affecting their ability to co-evolve. Professionals have been key in managing for more than ten years and have been a part of the teaching body in Lebanese higher education system. They can provide their individual perceptions, thoughts, and views about the nature of the internal and external university environments and how they are managed. They can also provide factors affecting the internal and external environment and future recommendations. Lebanese university managers were selected based on their managerial positions and role in shaping universities' strategies and roles mentioned in section 2.4.2. University managers were also selected based on their past teaching careers at Lebanese universities and held managerial positions at the same university for at least ten years for the present research. By that, university managers can be a valuable and rich source of knowledge of the overall view of the higher education university's role and interaction between internal and external environments and factors affecting these environments. They can provide how management interacts with their environment and what actions or strategies are taken to tackle environmental challenges. Due to managers' past teaching careers and current managerial positions, university managers are aware of the chronological development of Lebanese higher education system and the university they represent, and future projections, recommendations, and suggestions. Managers from several universities will vary the

data collected, as each university has its management style, status, and strategy. Management is considered an essential component of any co-evolutionary process and the link between the organization and its environment. Thus, Lebanese universities' managers will be a rich data source for developing the theoretical Co-Evolutionary Framework. Table 4-2 presents respondents profile including their positions at each university and period spend in managerial position.

Table 4-2 Participants Profile

University no.	No. Participants	Position	No. of Years in Managerial Position
University 1	Respondent 1	Administrative Director	12
	Respondent 2	Manager	13
University 2	Respondent 3	Manager	11
	Respondent 4	Manager	14
University 3	Respondent 5	Manager	11
	Respondent 6	Administrative Director	12
University 4	Respondent 7	Manager	16
	Respondent 8	Manager	11
University 5	Respondent 9	Administrative Director	10
	Respondent 10	Manager	12
University 6	Respondent 11	Manager	11
	Respondent 12	Administrative Director	13
University 7	Respondent 13	Manager	10
	Respondent 14	Manager	11
University 8	Respondent 15	Manager	15
	Respondent 16	Campus Director	13
University 9	Respondent 17	Manager	11
	Respondent 18	Vice President	10
University 10	Respondent 19	Manager	10
	Respondent 20	Manager	13
University 11	Respondent 21	Manager	14
	Respondent 22	Campus Director	12
University 12	Respondent 23	Administrative Director	10
	Respondent 24	Manager	11
University 13	Respondent 25	Manager	12
	Respondent 26	Manager	11
University 14	Respondent 27	Campus Director	10
University 15	Respondent 28	Administrative Director	11
University 16	Respondent 29	Manager	10
University 17	Respondent 30	Vice President	10
University 18	Respondent 31	Manager	14
University 19	Respondent 32	Administrative Director	12
University 20	Respondent 33	Administrative Director	10
University 21	Respondent 34	Manager	13
University 22	Respondent 35	Administrative Director	11
University 23	Respondent 36	Administrative Director	14
University 24	Respondent 37	Manager	10
University 25	Respondent 38	Campus Director	12
University 26	Respondent 39	Manager	11

Source: The Researcher

4.8 Sample Composition

Sanders et al. (2019) suggested that researchers typically use qualitative research to identify purposefully selected research participants and introduce them to the research setting, thereby improving their understanding of the research topic. However, using random sampling is associated with quantitative research, in contrast to using purposeful sampling (Creswell and Creswell, 2019). Purposeful sampling allows the researcher to select the appropriate cases for the present research, providing rich and in-depth information (Campbell et al., 2020). Purposeful sampling assumes that the selected research participants have first-hand knowledge or experience of the researched phenomena and can discuss and express their opinions, which can be classified as probability or non-probability. Stratton (2021) suggested that a purposive sample is a non-probability sample chosen based on a population's research objectives and characteristics. Purposeful sampling is typically associated with qualitative research to identify and select cases, which can provide rich data about the researched phenomenon, in contrast to random sampling of a large population that is equated with quantitative research (Cresswell and Creswell, 2019; Mweshi, 2020; Campbell et al., 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021; Bazen et al., 2021). Non-probabilistic methods can be convenience, judgment, quota, and snowball sampling, which involve selecting participants from a non-random population (Campbell et al., 2020). Qualitative research relies on non-random sampling techniques that provide insightful information about research respondents (Cresswell and Creswell, 2019; Mweshi, 2020; Campbell et al., 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021; Bazen et al., 2021). Contrary to quantitative research, where the research aim is to collect more generalizable data and hence has breadth and probability sampling is used, when possible, the participant has an equal opportunity of being chosen for

research (Cresswell and Creswell, 2019; Mweshi, 2020; Campbell et al., 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021; Bazen et al., 2021).

In this research, purposeful sampling was considered the most appropriate technique for sample selection, which is strongly recommended for qualitative research to identify key respondents in Lebanese universities. Purposeful sampling selects specific respondents with unique attributes that allow the researcher to understand the investigated topic comprehensively (Mweshi, 2020; Campbell et al., 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021; Bazen et al., 2021). Bazen et al., (2021) argued that purposeful sampling is suitable for selecting professionals who specialize in the investigated field and are considered relevant and rich data sources for the research. Lebanese universities' managers were considered suitable for this research as they were relevant and rich data sources. Lebanese universities' management will provide data on the external and internal environment of Lebanese universities, their relationship with their environment, and management's role in managing this relation. Lebanese managers were selected based on their knowledge and past teaching careers in Lebanese higher education field, managerial roles inside Lebanese universities, and the amount of time working in management. The selection of Lebanese universities' managers will enable the researcher to shed light on the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and provide more profound insight into the researched phenomena. The collected data from Lebanese universities' managers will provide valuable data based on their roles, perceptions, and experience in Lebanese higher education field. In addition, purposeful sampling will allow the researcher to focus on comparative studies of different cases to identify distinctions.

4.8.1 Sample size

Campbell et al. (2020) considered that qualitative samples are purposively selected based on rich information. In any research, researchers should focus on the richness of collected data, which is much more important than the quantity of data collected (Mweshi, 2020; Campbell et al., 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021; Bazen et al., 2021). Campbell et al. (2020) noted that researchers could demonstrate greater effectiveness by supporting significant and related assertions by qualitative methodologists. Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik (2021) argued that there is no fixed sample size in qualitative research since the research quality is based on the richness and quality of the data collected instead of statistical data measurement. To ensure the research is valid and a piece of social science research, data were collected from twenty-six universities by conducting thirty-nine interviews with managers of Lebanese universities. The researcher disregarded Lebanese universities, when selecting Lebanese universities for this research.

Lebanese higher education system has only one private university, which is Lebanese University (Khattab, 2019; Abou Arraj, 2018; Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; Al-Khoury and Khatib, 2020 LU, 2022). Although Lebanese University operates within Lebanese higher education system, its governance, structure, and processes differ. Lebanese University is directly governed by the Ministry of Higher Education (Abou Arraj, 2018; Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; LU, 2022). Lebanese Ministry of Higher Education assigns the University's management team, determines its programs and processes, and provides financial support and an annual budget (Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; LU, 2022). Lebanese University differ from other universities operating in Lebanon as its decision-making and processes are directly linked to the Ministry of Higher Education's governance (Abou Arraj, 2018; Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; LU, 2022). The development of new programs, processes, or the adoption of new approaches at Lebanese University should follow

a bureaucratic process and, in some cases, require government meetings or the development of new national policies for higher education (Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; LU, 2022). As a result, a variety of factors outside the university's borders influence the governance of Lebanese University education (Baroudi, 2019; MERIC, 2019; LU, 2022). The difference in governance, management approach, decision-making processes, and the mechanism that bound these factors internally and externally makes it different from other universities and falls into different categories solely and affected by different competition rules and conditions (Ghazzawi, 2018; Abou Arraj, 2018; Baroudi, 2019). As a result, Lebanese University is not considered in this research as it falls under a different organizational structure, management, processes, programs, and outcomes compared to most Lebanese universities in Lebanon which shape the overall educational system in Lebanon.

4.9 Pilot Study

A pilot study can help a researcher revise data collection plan regarding data quality and procedures followed for data collection (Sileyew, 2019). The pilot test is not a preliminary test but more formative, which helps a researcher develop relevant questions (Malmqvist et al., 2019). During the pilot test, a researcher can check the accuracy of the question and whether the participants correctly understood it in terms of the language and quality of the content (Williams-McBean, 2019). Thus, the interview protocol can be significantly improved in these areas where the responses received do not meet the study's objectives or respondents do not understand them.

Therefore, to examine the clarity and relevance of the interview questions in this research, the researcher conducted three pilot studies. These tests were important for understanding the interview content and assessing the interview questions' quality. Following the pilot test, the

researcher made minor changes, including rewriting some of the questions posed by the interviewers, separating and simplifying other questions, and adding more detailed explanations to some technical and academic terms.

4.10 Research Quality

In this section, the researcher presents the criteria followed in this research to ensure its quality in terms of reliability and validity. Ensuring the research's reliability and validity is central when designing qualitative research, analyzing results, and judging the quality of the research (Stenfors et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2022; Torlig, 2022). Research quality should be constantly evaluated during the research process and not just applied after the research is completed (Stenfors et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2020; Patterson et al., 2022; Torlig, 2022). Yadav (2020) argued that for the researcher to attain reliability and validity for his research, strategies for ensuring research rigor should be used in the qualitative research process. In addition, Lemon and Hayes (2020) emphasized the importance of research reliability and validity, especially for the analysis of findings as well as the development of the research. Furthermore, qualitative research must demonstrate its scientific nature to objectively understand the investigated phenomena in a constantly changing and developing context (Nassaji, 2020; Lemon and Hayes, 2020; Ronkainen and Wiltshire, 2021).

4.10.1 Reliability

Research reliability is the extent to which the procedure used in research can generate similar or identical findings or replicate earlier research (Tuval-Mashiach, 2021; Flake et al., 2020). Research reliability implies the replicability of the same results using objective methods to ensure the truth of the findings of a particular phenomenon. The more times research outcomes can be repeated,

the more likely they are to be reliable and stable (Pratt, 2020). Reliability is achieved by the replicability, repeatability, and stability of research findings or observations (Cheleuitte-Nieves and Lipman, 2019; Cram, 2020; Meng, 2020). Creswell and Creswell (2019) stressed the importance of ensuring research accuracy and credibility. Consistent with research ethics, the present researcher seeks to ensure the present research's reliability by relying on objectivity and applying moral and ethical principles (Dobakhti, 2020). Therefore, in the present research, the researcher accurately and transparently presents adopted strategies and methodologies to ensure research reliability. Reproducible methods and techniques are used in this research to address the investigated phenomena. The researcher acknowledges that each individual is unique and differs in his traits, social skills, or research skills. For that, the degree of research repeatability is based on the researcher's ability to reflect legitimacy and ascribed characteristics (Bryman et al., 2018). To overcome potential process biases, in this research, the researcher used standardized interviews using the same words and phrases, procedures, and order in all interviews to ensure valuable practices. In addition, to overcome possible bias, the researcher used standardized interviews to apply the exact wording, procedures, length, and consistency in all interviews to ensure best practices. Any research should be reproducible and replicable to guarantee the reliability of its findings (Cheleuitte-Nieves and Lipman, 2019; Cram, 2020; Meng, 2020).

4.10.2 Research Validity

Research validity is defined by Larsen et al. (2020) as the existence of well-supported, justifiable, relevant, meaningful, and logical research that confirms the quality of being sound, just, and well-founded. Goodman et al. (2020) suggested that research validity concerns research findings' accuracy and rigor. Valid research should be able to present what is factual and accurate, as the instrument or measure used should measure what is required (Johnson et al., 2020). Alam (2021)

suggested that validity in qualitative research means selecting the appropriate techniques and methods for data collection and analysis. Wright (2019) considered credibility and transferability to be two main aspects of research rigor, where internal validity relates to research credibility, while external validity is related to research transferability. Credibility is understanding the depth and scope of the investigated phenomena (Quintao et al., 2020). While transferability is the extent to which the findings can be applied in other contexts or with other participants (Munthe-Kaas et al., 2020). In the present research, persistent observation, member checking, and prolonged engagement were used by the researcher to ensure the research's credibility. In addition, the researcher used thick descriptions and revisions to the research journals to ensure the transferability of this research, which is equated with external validity. The present research establishes validity based on the flexible and responsive interaction between the researcher and the research respondents. Based on formal inquiry for validity and rigor, the reviewed literature on organizational co-evolution in Chapter 3 (section 3.2.4) demonstrates that existing research is of academic quality and is considered an emerging topic in the management and organizational field. The validity and strength of similar studies can be encouraging, indicating that reliance on secondary data sources can lead to valuable and meaningful results.

4.11 Research Design

This section discusses the research design of this research. Research design is a blueprint linking the present research questions with the collected qualitative data, results, and conclusions (Asenahabi, 2019; Saunders et al., 2019; Nassaji, 2020). The research design gives the researcher detailed steps for collecting, analyzing, interpreting data, and reporting findings (Saunders et al., 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2019; Dawadi et al., 2021).

In the present research, the researcher decided on philosophical assumptions, research methods, techniques to collect data, and the adopted approach to analyze the findings through the research design to align the research questions and the empirical evidence.

This research is divided into three stages which are:

- First stage: Research definition.
- Second stage: Qualitative data collection and analysis.
- Third stage: Research findings and discussion.

The researcher followed a single method to answer the research questions in the present research. The researcher adopted an explorative qualitative research design, methods, and procedures in the present research. Several researchers (Saunders et al., 2019; Al-Ababneh, 2020; Mweshi and Sakyi, 2020; Dawadi et al., 2021; Muzari et al., 2022) argued that an exploratory qualitative research design allows researchers to gather rich information from research participants and explore individuals' experiences, beliefs, and ideas in natural social settings. The exploratory qualitative research approach aids the researcher in better understanding and exploring the thoughts, perspectives, and beliefs of individuals, the reason for their actions, and the way it has occurred within a natural social setting (Saunders et al., 2019; Al-Ababneh, 2020; Mweshi and Sakyi, 2020; Dawadi et al., 2021; Muzari et al., 2022). Exploratory research is one of the primary approaches to qualitative research, which is used to understand the "why" and other factors that have yet to be clearly defined (Al-Ababneh, 2020; Mweshi and Sakyi, 2020). Exploratory research is appropriate for gathering descriptive data and understanding the investigated phenomena (Dawadi et al., 2021; Muzari et al., 2022). Exploratory research will help the researcher collect qualitative data, explore the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment and gain insights into organizational co-evolution. Therefore, an exploratory

approach will be most suitable to answer the questions of this research and fill the literature gap relevant to the co-evolution of Lebanese universities in a competitive environment. Figure 4-4 presents the research design for this research.

Figure 4-4: The Present Research Design

Source: The Researcher

4.12 Conclusion

The researcher explored potential methods to collect and analyze data in this chapter. The researcher adopted an inductive reasoning approach and case study strategy and used interview techniques to collect data for this research. Thematic analysis steps were discussed to analyze empirical data and identify organizational co-evolution themes. Sample size and purposeful sampling are discussed in this chapter. The chapter also discusses validity and reliability criteria

and strategies to support this research's quality and practical value. The chapter concludes by discussing the research design used in the present research. The following chapter presents the findings and analysis of results of the present research.

Chapter Five: Findings and Analysis

5.1 Introduction

After discussing the research methodology in the previous chapter, the researcher presents the method used to collect and analyze interview data. In the current chapter, the researcher presents qualitative data findings categorized by relevant themes.

5.2 Interview Data Findings

In this section, the researcher presents the findings of the collected data after using thematic analysis. The research findings are represented in response to the identified factors in Chapter 3, Section 3.5. To systematically obtain results at this research stage, the researcher used thematic analysis to describe recurring patterns, opinions, and ideas from the collected data of the current research (Bouncken et al., 2020). In the present research, the researcher adopted thematic analysis technique to analyze the collated data due to its flexibility and ability to offer a deeper understanding of participants' experiences, perspectives, and thoughts and to identify emerging themes from recurring patterns and thoughts about the investigated phenomena (Kiger and Varpio, 2020; Byrne, 2020; Xu and Zammit, 2020). Thematic analysis was used to provide descriptive findings, which demonstrate the perception of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. Participants were chosen based on their expertise, knowledge of Lebanese higher education sector, and position at Lebanese universities. Respondents of the present research were managers from several Lebanese universities. Correspondingly, Lebanese university managers provide insights into the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and suggest several factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with

their environment. Among the various methods available for structuring qualitative data analysis, the researcher used the six-stage steps thematic steps, which include familiarization, coding, generating themes, deriving common themes, categorizing, labeling themes, and preparing themes for analysis thematic, as discussed in Chapter 4 (section 4.6.2). Seven themes emerged from the thematic analysis.

1. Theme One: Environmental Characteristics (Q1-Q4)
2. Theme Two: External Influencing Factors (Q5-Q6)
3. Theme Three: Internal Influencing Factors (Q7)
4. Theme Four: Management Capabilities (Q8-Q11)
5. Theme Five: Competition Factors (Q12)
5. Theme Six: Capability Building Process (Q13-Q14)
6. Theme Seven: Organizational Outcome (Q15)
7. Theme Eight: Mediating Factors (Q16-19)

The following sections present data analysis findings of each theme separately.

5.3.1 Theme One: Environmental Characteristics

This section aims to identify the perceived nature and characteristics of Lebanese universities' organizational environment.

Question (1)

Question (1) aims to identify the environment perceived by Lebanese universities and the reason for their selection. Most participants considered that Lebanese higher education landscape is the primary environment in which they operate.

5.3.1.1 Part of Lebanese Higher Education Environment

According to 37 out of 39 participants, Lebanese universities are part of Lebanese higher education environment. The majority of Lebanese universities managers considered that Lebanese universities operate inside Lebanese higher education environment, where inputs and outputs are exchanged.

Respondent 15 argued that Lebanese universities are a primary part of Lebanese higher education system and international higher education system.

“We provide education in Lebanon, and that does not say, that we are isolated from international higher education system. We are not part of regional group or from an international university. Our main focus is local. Our programs serve local students in the first place, and international students in the second place. We are able to attract regional and international students, and that does not make us part of them. We have, few influences here and there in our surroundings”.

Respondent 25 considered that Lebanese universities operate within Lebanese higher education environment.

“Lebanese universities operate within the local Lebanese higher education environment; as a university we operate in the same environment as other Lebanese universities located in Lebanon. Our priority lies on local environment, in Lebanon. We compete with local universities that operate inside it. The university was established in the Lebanese higher education environment and includes several traits which apply mainly to local environment. Although we focus on Lebanese environment, higher education environment has become global; we try to keep our offering equivalent to high international standards. Also, to satisfy local needs and global ranks with international universities”.

Question (2)

Question (2) aims to identify the main reasons for perceived environment selection by Lebanese universities. Lebanese universities' managers considered that Lebanese landscape is selected as a suitable environment because they were originally established in Lebanon and incapable to operate in an external environment.

5.3.1.2 Established in Lebanon

According to 36 out of 39 participants, Lebanese universities considered that because of the ease Lebanese universities have in their own country, most Lebanese universities decided to focus their operations locally.

Respondent 31 considered that Lebanese higher education environment is selected as suitable environment where universities can access resources and easily exchange inputs and outputs.

“The university operates inside the Lebanese higher education environment, where our university is located, and the place we exchange our inputs and outputs, while in other environments is difficult to allocate resources and have the capacity to generate outputs outside Lebanon”.

Respondent 35 considered that Lebanese universities mainly operate in their local environment due to a lack of capabilities or the ability to compete with other universities outside Lebanese higher education system.

“Because we do not have required capabilities to compete and to operate in the different external environment, the Lebanese higher education environment is suitable for us and to other Lebanese universities to operate in”.

5.3.1.3 Limited International Capabilities

According to 34 out of 39 participants, Lebanese universities are incapable of competing outside Lebanese higher education. Lebanese managers considered that, due to the limited capabilities of Lebanese universities and the intense rivalry in the external environments, Lebanese universities selected Lebanese environment to operate in as their main landscape.

Respondent 37 suggested that the available capabilities of most Lebanese universities limit their abilities to operate in a different environment.

“Lebanese universities, as we said before, were established in Lebanon, influenced by its surrounding attributes. Lebanese higher education conditions assist us in performing our tasks and operations. The capabilities required to have additional campuses in a different environment other than the Lebanese environment are difficult. Other environments might require not regular capabilities. Competition with other environments requires much-advanced capabilities and resources allocations”.

Question (3)

Question (3) asked the participants about the relation between Lebanese universities and their environment and the factors that bound this relation. The majority of the participants considered that the relation between Lebanese universities and their environment is bound by natural selection and the universities' ability to adapt to environmental conditions.

5.3.1.4 Natural Selection

According to 35 out of 39 participants, Lebanese universities' relation to their environment is bound by natural selection. Lebanese managers considered that the environmental setting determines Lebanese universities' ability to operate and adapt to the market.

Respondent 27 considered that environmental conditions determine Lebanese universities' abilities.

“The ability to compete with other universities is primarily determined by the environmental conditions of the Lebanese universities. The environment where the university operates impacts its input and inputs and the distinctiveness of its capabilities; if new environmental conditions are imposed and cannot be handled by the university's capabilities, they can constrain its operations, survival, and growth in the market. In many cases, external environments are full of ambiguity and sudden changes”.

Respondent 32 considered that altering environmental settings have a direct effect on Lebanese universities.

“Any change in the status quo of the Lebanese higher education environment, positive or negative, is felt at our university. Environments always change, and now more than ever. The new influences limit the abilities and provide opportunities for universities. Due to Lebanese universities' capabilities, environmental changes have a negative effect on universities in Lebanon. With each change, new attributes are required. Some universities can make changes and acquire what is required, while others cannot, limiting their position in local environment”.

Question (4)

Question (4) asked the participants about the influence of environmental actors, which operate within the same landscape, on Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants considered that the new environment actors operating within the same environment affect Lebanon's universities' fitness.

5.3.1.5 Environmental Actors Offerings

According to 36 out of 39 participants, the offerings provided by environmental actors within Lebanese higher education environment have affected Lebanese universities' ability to stay fit inside their environment. Lebanese managers considered that new offerings provided by internal and external environmental actors had affected several Lebanese universities' fitness.

Respondent 8 considered that universities' offerings are a primary influence among Lebanese universities, which universities use to compete and position themselves in the market.

“New programs and courses offered have increased the rivalry between Lebanese universities. The offering of new courses has given universities new competitive edges over other universities. With new diverse offerings, universities can attract new students, reposition themselves, and change the way of operation. Our university was among the first universities to offer advanced medical programs due to the acquisition of advanced equipment and other logistics. Many universities were affected by our medical programs. Same happens when other universities provide new program and take the lead in specific field”.

Respondent 24 considered that a new offering from a new external entrance disrupted Lebanese higher education environment.

“The entrance of new external universities to the Lebanese market allowed international universities with advanced learning models to compete with local Lebanese universities. The entrance of new external universities has disrupted Lebanese education and affected Lebanese universities’ competitive advantages. New models include integrating new technologies and flexible teaching methods, that Lebanese universities do not have”.

Similarly, Respondent 17 stated that;

“Lebanese universities are in continuous competition for better offerings. New rivalry has impacted the Lebanese environment. Global competition, advancement of technologies, and change in higher education influenced universities in Lebanon. New competition rules emerged in Lebanese. Several universities were able to make necessary changes, while others were not and that affected their position in our environment. The new competitors from external environments disrupted the Lebanese landscape and brought new variables and changes to it, resulting in redistributing the market”.

5.3.2 Theme Two: External Influencing Factors

This section aims to identify the current external factors and environmental actors' influence on Lebanese universities, affecting their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

Question (5)

Question (5) asked the participants about Lebanese higher education environmental factors affecting Lebanese universities’ ability to co-evolve with their environment

5.3.2.1 Technological Factors

According to 35 of 39 interviewees, the lack of access to advanced technologies is a critical macro-environment factor affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese university managers considered that rapid technological change limits Lebanese universities from integrating new technologies and developing new products.

Respondent 21 argued that the rate of technology change is challenging Lebanese universities' ability to make changes and adapt to new technologies.

“At least every two or three years and sometimes less, we need to update our lab's machines and equipment. The rate of technological change is increasing, making us unable to access newer technological devices and develop our resources.”

Respondent 19 made a similar point, showing how the technology rate of change limited the abilities of the university.

“The speed at which new technologies emerged in the last years is changing the way we operate. We cannot have the ability to acquire most recent and advanced technologies”.

5.3.2.2 Communication Infrastructure

According to 36 of 39 participants considered that internet and communications infrastructure are essential infrastructures that Lebanon lacks and needs further development. Lebanese universities' managers consider local infrastructure essential for universities' processes, connectivity, and new service development.

Respondent 13 argued that Lebanon lacks telecommunications infrastructure which is an essential tool for the university's ability to operate and develop new services.

“Lebanon's issue with internet infrastructure, wireless or wired connections limits universities' potential. Lack of internet infrastructure has made Lebanon lose many opportunities for new organizations and research centers to enter the country “.

In support of this notion, Respondent 10 stated that;

“Internet in Lebanon is diminishing opportunities for having a better quality of education, and introducing new services, like e-learning programs and help in the competition with other international universities that provide online or distance learning programs.”

Respondent 32 emphasized the importance of the emerging information economy and cyberspace as new competitive landscapes that universities should work to co-evolve, likewise the external physical environment.

“In your research on universities co-evolution, while we are talking about technology and the internet in particular. The internet is an important source of rich information and resources and develops classic or traditional means and methods. The internet is not given its true value. You can see that the internet is the key to enter information space and knowledge economy. Information space, is another environment that organizations should co-evolve with. It is resourceful, informative, innovative, and requirement to attain sustainability”.

Question (6)

Questions (6) asked the participants about extra-organizational environment factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese managers considered the emergence of new competitive and social factors is the main extra-organizational environment factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

5.3.2.3 New Competitors

According to 34 out of 39 participants, considered that the entrants of new competitors to Lebanese market is an important external factor that affects Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that distance learning offerings from several international universities are challenging Lebanese universities' fitness and changing Lebanese higher education into a competitive landscape.

Respondent 3 argued that Lebanese higher education has been impacted by distance learning offerings provided by international universities.

“Lebanese higher education system was not impacted by online learning like distance learning. The new distance learning methods entered the market quickly, providing programs that we offer and other new programs, with facilitated teaching methods. The new teaching methods are trying to replace the existing physical Lebanese universities and how we teach”.

Respondent 17 supports the notion that entrance of new competitors is affecting Lebanese universities, where he stated;

“International universities around the world use the distance learning technique to penetrate existing high education fields, competing with the local universities and higher education institutions.”

Respectively, Respondent 5 stated that;

“Regarding Lebanese higher education system, distance learning is disrupting higher education system, how universities operate, and its rules of competition.”

5.3.2.4 Social Factors

According to 37 out of 39 participants considered that social factors are extra-organizational environment factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that social changes have changed educational preferences, demands and how students choose education delivery methods.

Respondent 14 considered that new preferences that emerged as a result of the education sector transformation are affecting Lebanese universities' offerings and services.

“All the transformations happening around us and the digitalization of everything have created new preferences and demands in education. Due to its flexibility, ease and costs, students are seeking more flexible online programs. The attitude worldwide is toward online and virtual teaching methods rather than traditional on-campus teaching. The ease of applying and studying from anywhere is placing pressure on our offerings and competitive power”.

Respondent 10 stated that;

“Education lifestyle is changing. Any student can apply for an online or distance learning degree, and have the same degree like other students, studying in our campus.”

Additionally, Respondent 26 considered that;

“The acceptance of online degrees by many organizations, and its consideration it the same as campus-based degrees, has led students' attitude towards the use of new technologies and methods for education. Now instead of competing with known number of local universities, we are competing with many new universities in our landscape”.

In addition, participants provided additional external influencing factors that can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants considered that global universities ranking (27 out of 39) rising costs (22 out of 39) low number of international students

(18 out of 39) suppliers (13 out of 39) regulators (8 out of 39) government funding (7 out of 39) affect Lebanese universities' co-evolutionary processes. Given the importance of global universities ranking (27 out of 39) among the mentioned factors, Respondent 20 considered that; *“The international ranking system is now providing universities' identity, image, and reputation. Our local students who want to apply to our university are searching for the international rank of our university, to decide if the university can offer a world-class degree and education to help them find jobs in foreign countries or Lebanon”*.

5.3.3 Theme Three: Internal Influencing Factors

This section focuses on analyzing organizational factors affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

Questions (7)

Questions (7) aim to identify the main organizational factors affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' resources, structure, and processes are considered the main organizational factors that affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

5.3.3.1 Organizational Resources

Physical, financial, technological, and informational resources are the main organizational factors affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

5.3.3.1.1 Physical Resources

According to 38 out of 39 participants considered that universities' physical resources significantly influence internal factors that limit Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that the number of research facilities, labs, equipment, and buildings owned by the university provide additional value to its offering and sustain their operations and competitiveness.

Respondent 15 considered that acquiring additional advanced facilities enables universities to offer higher value and compete with other universities.

“One way to assess the competitiveness of a university in Lebanon is to assess its labs and research centers, including its equipment, machines, and tools used in engineering, physics, and medical domain. University's advanced facility will give it competitive advantage over its rivals”.

Respondent 31 stated that;

“Having fully equipped labs is an important factor for any university and give the university remarkable ability to offer higher-standard programs and develop new programs. Some universities are known for specific medical capabilities and others in different areas”.

5.3.3.1.2 Financial Resources

According to 34 out of 39 participants considered the university budget is an important internal factor limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese managers considered that Lebanese universities' financial resources, mainly the universities' annual budgets, limit the universities' operations and ability to make necessary developments, and capture valuable opportunities.

Respondent 26 considered that the pre-determined budget deprives the university of pursuing opportunities that lead to further development.

“Each university, has its budget pre-determined at the beginning of the academic year. University’s budget organizes spending and set constraints on new expenditures. In other words, there is a limited budget. Pre-set budget often limits universities to take advantage of many events that happen within the academic year. University boards cannot know what will happen during the academic year; other resources are kept for emergencies and critical situations.”

Respondent 37 considered that the university budget is inflexible and limits the universities operations.

“Universities, do not have an open money source. Budgets are calculated on the average spending of the last year. Who says that the upcoming year will be the same as the past years? Managers’ actions and decisions could be limited because of the amount of available funds”.

Respondent 35 argued that, due to limited budgets, the university sought out different sources to acquire funds.

“Our budget is limited, due to several factors. Universities with low budgets can go for crowdfunding methods, or try collecting money by using internal marketing campaigns to raise money”.

5.3.3.1.3 Technological Resources

According to 36 out of 39 participants considered that the universities' technological resources are an important internal factor that limits Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities’ managers considered that Lebanese universities' technological resources are limited, which affects Lebanese universities' processes and outcomes.

Respondent 18 considered that the pre-determined budget deprives the university of pursuing several opportunities to seize advanced technologies.

“Lebanese universities have well-equipped laboratories at their campuses, that require new technologies to benefit fully from them. Universities, demand new tech tools in many fields like engineering, physics, and medical departments, to develop our processes and services and ability ranks internationally”.

In addition, Respondent 28 stated that;

“Technological resources define the standards and level of the universities' operations, their services, and the variety of research offered.”

Respondent 8 considered that Lebanese universities lack AI integration within their systems.

“Universities at Lebanon are far from AI adoption. AI technology has transformed the way organizations operate. We need this transformation also in our universities. AI systems used by Lebanese universities needs to be updated. Universities need to use new software systems to help them survive and have point of existence in different landscapes in the digital age”.

Similarly, Respondent 11 stated that;

“The universities in Lebanon does not use AI as it should. AI is not just needed; it is becoming essential in several fields.”

5.3.3.1.4 Informational Resources

According to 35 out of 39 participants, the lack of informational resources is considered an important internal factor that limits Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that there is a lack of advanced informational resources and tools, affecting Lebanese universities' ability to utilize and generate valuable knowledge and assets.

Respondent 29 considered that Lebanese universities lack information resources that limit their ability to acquire valuable knowledge.

“Nowadays, information is considered an important and key resource for organizations everywhere. Having adequate information provides the university with significant input. Like other Lebanese universities, our university is limited in collecting and processing information. The reason behind that, is the limited collection tools and advanced systems; affecting the ability of universities to analyze, generate and acquire valuable knowledge”.

Respondent 23 emphasized the importance of information utilization and integration within Lebanese universities.

“Information utilization is important for any organization, and in the case of universities, it is essential. Knowledge is considered an important asset. The process is ongoing, and not all universities can cope with this. The process needs advanced systems, databases, updated libraries, web-based mediums, advanced apps and software. Lebanese universities need new system to integrate what I have mentioned, to sustain the value of its informational system, and knowledge management”.

Respondent 27 stated that;

“Due to the limited ability of the university to develop advanced information management systems, the university is focusing on developing new internal information management systems to generate new knowledge of how-to-do things. For us, to have a well-developed knowledge information management system to manage internal and external knowledge is a challenge because of the university’s limited resources”.

5.3.3.2 Organizational Structure

According to 36 out of 39 participants, the university structure is an important internal factor limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that the new environmental conditions require Lebanese universities to be less structured to achieve organizational sustainability and fitness.

Respondent 33 considered that Lebanese universities should have modern structures to achieve fitness within their environment.

“To be able to operate normally and seize the opportunities in the future, we should not rely on old approaches and structures used in the past. The old structure we now use, is adopted by many higher education institutions in Lebanon. The structured way of designing the universities has made it difficult for universities to cope with all the changes happening around us. Universities should be more dynamic, flexible, and less structured”.

Respondent 36 considered that Lebanese universities require a new organizational structure.

“Universities at Lebanon cannot continue with the same structure, and face unprecedented disruption in their field. The structure of the university should be open and flexible to face chaotic environment”.

Likewise, Respondent 39 stated that;

“Universities should be able not to be just flexible in changing environments by integrating new technologies or tools. To unlock greater value, universities should be ready to have a digital organizational structure”.

5.3.3.3 Organizational Processes

According to 37 out of 39 participants considered that the universities' processes are important internal factors that limit Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers considered that internal and external processes can affect the development of Lebanese universities' capabilities and their interaction with their environment negatively or positively.

Respondent 5 stated that the university's daily internal processes affect its capabilities, whether negatively or positively.

“Daily processes inside the university greatly influence the university operations and abilities. Everyday processes make us closer or farther to building our strength in our environment. How is that, I will tell you. The interaction and engagement between all the units inside the university generate an outcome, which is influenced by organization's policies and rules, management decisions, events happening around us and how we respond to it, how our staff uses our internal assets and capabilities, when combined specific outcome is created every day that can affect the path of the university. If every day this happens and a derivation happens, we will be far from our target and achieving positive feedback.”

Similarly, Respondent 31 emphasized the influence of the university's internal and external processes.

“A genetic mutation occurs at the universities, similar to what happens in nature. What we do every day, week, month, or year create changes. Let us be clear nothing will stay in its initial state; changes can be to the advantage of the university or not. Attention should be paid to design processes and what they generate daily. The genetic mutation of the university process will develop

new norms and actions used in the days, week and month afterwards, adding new features that can be negative or positive. What is done inside and outside of the university are both important”.

In addition, participants provided additional internal influencing factors that can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants considered that brand image (28 out of 39); research department (27 out of 39) IT department (25 out of 39) organizational grammar (16 out of 39) organizational culture (12 out of 39) and organizational stakeholders (7 out of 39) affect Lebanese universities' co-evolutionary processes. Given the importance of brand image (28 out of 39) among the mentioned factors, Respondent 3 considered that;

“We have been through many historical events that changed our position and perceived university image. What happened to us did not stop us from moving forward and enhancing our capabilities and offering in Lebanon. Our resilience, effort, and contributions helped us build a strong brand image in the Lebanese higher education field and regional environment. Our brand image gives our degrees value and attracts new students to study at our university. Keeping a good university image is crucial for us”.

5.3.4 Theme Four: Management Capabilities

This section focuses on analyzing the influence of managerial capabilities on Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

Question (8)

Question (8) aims to determine the role of Lebanese universities' management in managing the relation between universities and their environment. The majority of Lebanese universities' managers considered that the managerial role is limited concerning Lebanese universities and their environment, which is focused on internal processes and lacks strategic intentionality.

5.3.3.4.1 Limited Managerial Role

According to 36 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities' management role is limited to internal administrative tasks at the university. The majority of Lebanese managers considered that Lebanese universities' management is focused on the administration of the internal university environment and has limited engagement with its external environment.

Respondent 31 considered that management is concerned with the internal environment rather than the external environment.

“Management in our university is concerned with the daily internal process and activities. Our managers have more administrative role and concentrate on the internal side rather than working on both sides of the coin, internally and externally”.

Respondent 19 considered that management is limited to managing internal processes within the university.

“Management work direct their effort on what is happening within the university, and not what is happening outside the university. They have governance, controlling and monitoring duty of the university’s internal processes and paying less attention to the external environment that is considered to be to a certain degree uncontrollable”.

Similarly, Respondent 15 stated that;

“University's management seek to improve daily tasks, and when an external event occurs and has an effect on the university, management attention is deviated to its external environment, to take suitable actions and decrease the effect of the external factors.”

Respondent 3, respectively, stated that;

“There is less concern about the external environment in our university, whereas managers’ job is limited to the university's activities, processes, events, and how to adapt to environmental events.”

Question (9)

Question (9) asked the participants about the factors affecting management's abilities to respond to universities' environmental changes. The majority of the participants considered that bounded rationality and strategic intentionality are important factors that limit the universities' management capabilities.

5.3.3.4.2 Bounded Rationality

According to 34 out of 39 participants, the bounded rationality of Lebanese universities' management is an important factor that shapes managers' capabilities. Lebanese universities' managers considered that bounded rationality determines how university managers make sense of their surroundings and make decisions accordingly.

Respondent 27 considered that management's bounded rationality affects their ability to make sense of and scan their surroundings.

“Understanding university’s environment is bounded by the prior knowledge, skills, and knowledge of the individual scanning his environment. Since it is made by senior management, these skills should always be developed to have a constructive and logical rationale”.

Respectively, Respondent 31 outlined that;

“The method used by university managers to analyze external events is based on their learned skills and acquired abilities. So, if management is faced with new challenges, it will not be easy

for them to reach the best decision and take a suitable course of action. As a result, opportunities and threats are not fully differentiated since they are not analyzed correctly”.

Respondent 34 stressed the importance of not limiting the decision-making to senior management and embracing organizational learning to overcome one-sided or bounded rationality inside the university.

“At this university, although managers have more skills and experience to make decisions for the internal and external environment of the university. Decisions can be wrong or have errors. Decision-making at the university should also include the views of lower or all levels of the organization to understand the situation from different angles better. The result will be achieving better decisions and overcoming bounded rationalities inside the university. When used across different departments, organizational learning can embrace knowledge interaction for better decisions”.

5.3.3.4.3 Lack of Strategic Intentionality

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese managers lack strategic internality. The majority of participants considered that the lack of strategic internality is a main managerial limitation that affects management capabilities and their role in administering the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment.

Respondent 39 argued that Lebanese managers tend to respond to external environmental changes or events instead of taking proactive steps.

“The majority of the managers lack the intent to take strategic initiative on academic and administrative matters. Managers’ behavior is adaptive, and the market is full of adapters. Without strategic intent, adaptation will replace co-evolution and universities will lose many opportunities outside their borders, and many challenges cannot be avoided in case proactivity is missing”.

Respondent 32 emphasized that universities' management should cultivate strategic intentionality.

“Voluntaristic action is needed more than before in these changing circumstances. The manager should have a forecast of the future and where the university is heading to have suitable responses to changes ahead and not derivations. Contingency plans and pre-emptive actions can be made. In our university, not much is made, and we need a lot to cultivate these capabilities”.

Question (10)

Question (10) asked the participants about the role of management search behavior in building Lebanese universities' capabilities. The majority of participants considered that management's search behavior is focuses on explorative search and lacks exploitative search behavior.

5.3.3.4.4 Lack of Explorative Search

According to 37 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities lack explorative search behavior and the ability to introduce new or innovative capabilities. Most participants considered that Lebanese universities' search behavior is limited to capability replication and improvement of universities capabilities.

Respondent 35 considered that Lebanese universities' search focuses on replication processes from other universities within the same environment.

“The search behavior of the university concentrates on what is available in the market. The search concentrates on what our rivals have to acquire the same level of competitiveness. Our search is more explorative, by which 80 to 90 percent replication of other innovations in Lebanon. Our search behavior is directed to capability improvement and we do not adopt an innovative approach”.

Respondent 37 considered that university search behavior focuses on improving the university's capabilities.

“In this university, search behavior is limited by ensuring the competitive advantage of our capacities. We are determined to keep the level of our universities with other universities. Our university's search behavior is continually working on improving our current capabilities and practices. We cannot easily purchase and change our capabilities each time something new is offered in Lebanon. We improve what we have to keep our work going”.

Respondent 38 considered that Lebanese universities lack innovative proliferation.

“Our search for new capabilities is centered on modifying our pre-owned capability and adding new capabilities to our abilities. Being pioneers and introducing new capabilities to the market is difficult and needs more capabilities in the first place to generate results like this”.

Question (11)

Question (11) asked the participants whether their environment is considered analyzable and the factors determining their analytical ability. Most participants considered that the higher education environment is not analyzable and that environmental analysis is determined by limited managerial absorptive capacity and bounded rationality.

5.3.3.4.5 Absorptive Capacity

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that the lack of absorptive capacity limits Lebanese universities from adequately analyzing their external environment. Most participants considered that the external environment's causal ambiguity and limited absorptive abilities are the main factors that limit managerial analysis abilities.

Respondent 20 considered that the university's external environment is not analyzable since the university cannot collect enough data to analyze the environment adequately.

“Our processes are concerned with the internal environment more than the external. We as a university lack processes to collect data from our external environment, assimilate it and apply it. Data collection and analysis data processes are absent in our university’s processes. We will not analyze to have an overview of the environment. We want to analyze so that we develop new capabilities and suitable respond based on valuable knowledge”.

Respondent 22 considered that casual ambiguity hindered the analysis of Lebanese universities' external environment.

“In this competitive environment, we are finding it difficult to reach the correct data and make full understanding of it, due to casual ambiguity. The cause and effect and root causes of events happening in our environment set barriers to analysis process. When local and international students' numbers suddenly drop, we could not accurately relate this effect to its initial causes”.

5.3.4 Theme Five: Competition Factors

This section focuses on identifying the main factors determining the competitiveness of Lebanon's universities.

Question (12)

Question (12) asked the participants about the main factors that affect universities' ability to compete in their environment. The majority of Lebanese managers considered that the competitiveness of Lebanese universities is mainly based on a resource-based approach.

Lebanese managers consider the main factors affecting Lebanese universities' ability to compete

within their environment are: the dependence on a resource-based view strategy, lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) and lack of skilled human resources.

5.3.4.1 Resource-Based view

According to 34 out of 39 participants considered that adopting a resource-based view as a competitive approach by Lebanese universities limits universities' competitiveness. Lebanese universities' managers considered that focusing solely on universities' resources as the main source of competitiveness is decreasing Lebanese universities' strategy to compete with their rivals and in the same time disregarding other important resources.

Respondent 28 considered that the university's competitive advantage is based on resource-based view.

“The adoption of a resource-based approach, focuses on generating sustained competitive based on the university's-based resources. Having more resources, from labs, campuses, machines, PCs, IT techs, auditoriums, research facilities outperform other universities with fewer resources, that weaken their competitiveness”.

Similarly, Respondent 26 stated that;

“Physics research facilities in our universities are considered core competitiveness among other universities. Advanced facilities and continual development have given us competitive advantage in Lebanon. Today we are increasing our focus in different research domains, and took decision to acquire advanced equipment, giving us important resources to offer and compete better”.

Respondent 36 considered that the university's competitive advantage strategy lacks a knowledge-based approach.

“Lebanese universities compete by their assets and resources. The issue here is less competition in knowledge assets and its generation. Depending on how universities are resourceful, does not

mean not paying attention to other resources, like knowledge. By acquiring valuable knowledge, universities in Lebanon can become source of knowledge. In another way, knowledge hub, by which it is an important asset to compete with, and give additional value to its adopters”.

5.3.4.2 Lack of Valuable, Rare Imitable, and Organizable Resources (VRIO)

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that the lack of valuable, rare, imitable, and organizable resources, affects Lebanese universities' ability to compete. Lebanese universities' managers considered that Lebanese universities own imitable resources and lack rare resources.

Respondent 10 considered that Lebanese universities possess imitable resources accessible to other universities.

“Lebanese universities offer many common qualifications, as a result of similar resources owned by universities and can be acquired by any university. Universities need to adopt new approach to acquire new resources, because their resources have reached their peak development, making their resources accessible by other universities. Similar resources, provide similar replicable offerings”.

Respondent 35 considered that Lebanese universities lack rare resources.

“Each university has its resources. These resources present an important aspect of the university's competitive advantage. Strategic, rare, and unique resources give competitive edge. Not all universities have rare resources; Lebanese universities resources should be diversified, and unique. For example, there is an emphasis in Lebanon on medical and engineering programs. Each field has its courses and required specific resources. Few universities have unique resources, and have the ability to offer unique degrees and compete with other universities”.

5.3.4.3 Lack of Skilled Human Resources

According to 34 out of 39 participants considered that the shortage of skilled human resources is an important factor affecting Lebanese universities' competitiveness. Lebanese managers considered that the availability of skilled human resources could affect Lebanese universities' teaching and research offerings and their future development.

Respondent 33 argued that Lebanese universities have a shortage of professors from high-ranking universities.

“We offer education, through our professors and lecturers. The degree of skills, qualifications, and experiences of our human resources give more value to the university. The majority of our lectures are from an academic background. We have difficulty attracting skilled lecturers with an industrial background to offer more value to our teaching and practices at the university”.

Respondent 14 respectively stated that;

“Our university has a shortage of professors who graduated from international prestigious universities with higher academic standards and experience. The majority of our academics are graduates from Lebanon. Variety in skills are needed for better teaching, research, and higher quality ranks”.

In addition to the factors mentioned in this section, participants (26 out of 39) considered that marketing activities could affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Respondent 18 stated that;

“Our marketing team is doing a good job in enhancing our competitive abilities by initiating new advertising campaigns, brand development activities, engaging with the world around us using social media, promoting new programs, and importantly helping us taking a better decision based on marketing department's research”.

5.3.5 Theme Six: Capability Building Process

This section aims to identify the factors affecting Lebanese universities' capacity building process.

Question (13)

Question (13) asked the participants about the factors that affect universities' capability building. Most Lebanese managers consider that the lack of dynamic capability, imitable resources, shortage of skilled human resources, and the adoption of a resource-based view are the main factors that affect the capability building process of Lebanese universities.

5.3.5.1 Lack of Dynamic Capability

According to 36 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities' capability building processes are centered on capability proliferation. Lebanese universities' managers considered that universities' capability building process lacks dynamic capability building and focuses on capability proliferation.

Respondent 3 argued that university capability building processes are repetitive with similar outcomes.

“The processes followed inside the university are similar to other universities’ processes with few differences. The outputs of these replicable routines guarantee same outputs and processes, especially that the Lebanese higher education sector is not asking for more. We process data and events and take actions when needed; and not develop voluntarily. Many Lebanese universities do this, resulting in a replicable daily routine instead of capabilities building process for more

sustainable competitive advantages. The research and development teams at the universities should be empowered for further intervention and innovation”.

Similarly, Respondent 5 stated that;

“Processes in our university, whether in teaching or research, are similar to other processes in different Lebanese universities with similar same results. Similarities, has filled the Lebanese landscape with imitable universities capabilities, processing the same input and similar results. You can find the same program taught by different Lebanese universities in the same way and have the same result, what differs is the university campus, professors, equipment, and the university name. Since universities adopt same capability building processes, we will have the same result and standards in Lebanon”.

Respondent 17 argued that Lebanese universities lack a dynamic capability building process and emphasized the importance of AI integration in higher education.

“As AI technologies are becoming important in our daily life, the significance of knowledge is increasing. Like the process of acquiring, developing, and generating new knowledge. Knowledge helps us acquire new resources, assets and processes at the university. The capability to generate knowledge to improve to advance our process is needed more than before. The utilization of AI aid in generating new knowledge, that help universities generate new knowledge and acquire new capabilities and assets”.

5.3.5.2 Capability Refinement

According to 37 out of 39 participants considered that capability refinement shapes the outcome of Lebanese universities' capability building process. The majority of Lebanese universities' managers considered that Lebanese universities' capability building process lacks capability creation and is limited to improving existing capabilities.

Respondent 16 considered that the capability building process is limited to incremental improvement of available capabilities.

“In general, any market is made up of innovators and replicators. Some innovate their capabilities, and some replicate or do both. In our case, innovation is somehow difficult. Our work is mainly focused on refining and improving our capabilities to be up to the required level.”.

Likewise, Respondent 36 stated that;

“We do not introduce new capabilities. We are concerned about what our resources let us do. The university is concerned with making suitable modifications of our capabilities to operate and compete in a certain level”.

5.3.5.2 Co-Evolutionary Capability Building Process

According to 38 out of 39 participants, Lebanese universities do not adopt a specific capability building process by which new variations are continuously acquired, retained, and generated. The majority of Lebanese universities' managers considered that the lack of a selection-retention-variation process limits Lebanese universities' ability to renovate processes and capabilities.

Respondent 10 noted that the university lacks a continual capability process that concentrates on the acquisition, retention, and generation of new variations.

“We do not use a specific capability building process that to develop our capabilities. External changes happen regularly impact or decisions for developing universities' capabilities. We are not able to develop new capabilities because of the old methods and tools we are using. Sometimes it takes one or two semesters to have changes or annually, and that is in normal situation”.

Respectively, Respondent 15 outlined that;

“Environmental scanning and selecting what is new and useful for the universities' development is beneficial. There is no definite process to facilitate their application in our university. Old

resources and processes are retained and used in our operations; while these should be disregarded and replaced, they remain part of our system. Without having a definite capability building process, we cannot ensure the renewal of our resources and capabilities. and limit us to the old processes and same outcome”.

Moreover, participants considered that lack of adequate training (28 out of 39) lack of process innovation management (26 out of 39) and lack of knowledge assets (22 out of 39) could affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Given the significance of the need to have adequate training for Lebanese universities' capability building processes, Respondent 26 outlined that;

“Training is needed for university's human resources when it comes to what constitutes university’s capability building process. Training includes teaching our human capital new skills, methods, routines and providing new tacit knowledge to engage effectively in universities capability building process and have better outcome”.

5.3.6 Theme Seven: Organizational Outcome

This section aims to determine the characteristics of Lebanese universities' outcomes.

Question (15)

Question (15) investigates the outcome of Lebanese universities based on the capability building process. The majority of participants considered that Lebanese universities lack new outcomes and offerings forms.

5.3.6.1 Lack of New Outcome

According to 34 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities outcome is an important factor that limits Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese managers considered that Lebanese universities offer similar outcomes in the market.

Respondent 27 considered that Lebanese universities offer similar offerings; however, the processes and tools differ.

“The university offers more than thirty degrees from several schools. Our offering is not unique, and we share almost all the degrees with other Lebanese universities with the same schools. What distinguish us from others are the methods, tools, and facilities used to offer a program”.

Respondent 37 argued that most Lebanese universities' programs are imitable; some universities can compete in specific programs.

“Lebanese higher education system lacks new offerings. Many of what is offered by different universities, including us, are similar to what has been offered in the past. The market lacks new programs. The same offering will be provided as universities include the same schools. There are unique programs at each school, but no decision to offer new qualifications. Program’s curriculum is usually updated”.

In support of this notion, Respondent 28 outlined that;

“Lebanese universities have the same school structure and similar offerings.”

5.3.6.2 Lack of New Organizational Forms

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that the outcome of Lebanese universities lacks new organizational forms. The participants considered that the outcome of Lebanese universities is offered using traditional methods and processes.

Respondent 9 considered that universities use similar capabilities to provide their offerings.

“Teaching occurs in the same traditional classes inside a campus. I am not saying this should be canceled; it needs to be combined with other forms, like virtual forms. International universities have preceded us by offering a new way of teaching. Virtual forms at least need to be integrated into our educational system, not just for education and also for research. Distance learning and online learning are new forms used by other universities. These forms have allowed the universities to compete with other universities internationally and helped them grow worldwide. The offer form of Lebanese universities should be re-invented.”.

Respondent 26 considered that Lebanese universities prefer traditional higher education methods.

“Sole dependance on in-campus courses limits Lebanese universities. Students need to come to campus, study, do their exams, and research in the labs. That is the maximum the university can offer to a student. Student needs to come physically to the new-old form in Lebanon. Universities should use technologies to get us out of our limited outcomes. Different universities nowadays have different forms to offer for students. Students required new services and better resources from us”.

Respondent 35 considered that Lebanese universities' offerings lack digital forms.

“Lebanese universities should develop their digital forms and services. Using new forms, Lebanese universities can go international. New forms could be the result of combining universities' capabilities and resource”.

In addition to the factors mentioned in this section, participants (20 out of 39) considered that offering a new capability or a process as an organizational outcome can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Given the significance of the introduction of a new capability or process as an organizational outcome, Respondent 35 stated that;

“We can also give Lebanese higher education and other organizations from other fields new solutions to enhance their performance. We do not need to be limited to repetitive services. We can offer new methods and processes which help improve organizations' performance”.

5.3.7 Theme Eight: Mediating Factors

This section focuses on asking about mediating factors considered important by several researchers concerned with organizational co-evolution. In addition, this section includes additional factors considered by the participants of this research, essential for the co-evolutionary path for Lebanese universities.

Question (16)

Question (16) asked the participants whether Lebanese universities' location affects their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

5.3.7.1 Universities' Location

According to 33 out of 39 participants considered that the location of Lebanese universities does not affect the ability to co-evolve. The majority of Lebanese managers considered that universities' location is not only important at the initial stages, but also for the survival and growth of Lebanese universities in the future.

Respondent 34 considered that Lebanese universities' system matters more than their location.

“Our location in Lebanon is beneficial for our university, for its location and historical values. It does not determine or provide one hundred percent of our survival or growth or how we compete. Our systems, resources, and the combination of them with all the university units, along with the

approaches we adopt, determine our survival and co-evolution with our environment. Our capabilities and approaches greatly allow us to succeed or limit us”.

Respondent 38 considered that the physical location and global rules had put new rules that surpass the dependence on the university's physical location.

“University’s location is in the middle of the middle East region. Yes, it helped. Reviewing the importance of location, new landscapes has surpassed geographical locations and distances. New landscapes become more flexible, connected and exist in virtual dimensions. Whether in Lebanon or not, the competition rules have changed. Virtual landscape is becoming important like the physical. International changes changed entity's presence, expansion, and relocation. We do not have much of a presence virtually”.

Question (17)

Question (17) asked the participants if Lebanese universities have recently co-evolved with their environment.

5.3.7.2 Universities’ Historical Development

According to 34 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities have not co-evolved. Most Lebanese managers considered that Lebanese universities had undergone incremental development.

Respondent 20 considered that the university did not co-evolve, but its components incrementally evolved over time.

“The university has gone several developments lately. Our development process was not radical in the sense of the word. It is improving several components inside the university. These developments are considered incremental. The university needs more than that. Co-evolution

covers more areas, we did not integrate into our university's strategy and actions to reach co-evolution. We are better than we are from where we began. Developing our facilities, using new technologies, reconfiguring and optimizing our systems, and offering new degrees are the areas that have been developed. It will not make too much difference, or we call it co-evolution; it is taking necessary actions to stay updated and up to competition”.

Similarly, Respondent 10 stated that;

“We increased our programs, we added additional schools, opened new campuses, our students' number has increased, advanced our labs and developed our processes and teaching techniques. We have evolved, and not co-evolved. Our main focus is internally, and not externally and that is not enough to consider our progress co-evolution”.

Respondent 21 considered that the university had achieved partial improvement and not co-evolution since it is focused mainly on the internal environment.

“We are in the stage of developing internal organizational units as our first step, and then we focus on other external matters. You can say that we are working on internal and then external. The external environment was not like this, so our focus was only on Lebanon. We need additional characteristics and actions to reach co-evolution”.

Question (18)

Question (18) asked the participants about the relevant environment on which decisions to develop universities' capabilities are based.

5.3.7.3 Local Responsiveness

According to 37 out of 39 participants, considered that Lebanese universities' focus is limited to the local higher education landscape. According to most Lebanese university managers, Lebanese universities develop their capabilities based on local requirements and needs, while ensuring that their processes and outcomes meet international higher education standards. Respondent 13 considered that Lebanese universities made developments in response to local challenges.

“Our operations are in Lebanon, and we compete with local competitors. The standards of the Lebanese higher education sectors let us compete with other universities, both regionally and internationally. Development and changes were made accordingly to local changes. The university did not limit its activities to only local. We had several actions taken to keep our standards and competitive advantages recognized by international universities. To answer your question, we are trying to manage our university and its external environment better, starting from local to regional and international. Our work in the past helped us survive and grow within our local environment, retaining international standards”.

Likewise, Respondent 17 stated that;

“The undergone changes and development at our university are toward the Lebanese environment. We are facing many challenges to co-evolve with our local environment. It was difficult to co-evolve with one environment, and it will be harder to try to co-evolve with another external environment with different conditions and difficulties. Competition has been mainly with Lebanese universities, and our development processes is in progress”.

Question (19)

Question (19) asked the participants if there are any additional internal or external factors that limit Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

5.3.7.4 Local and Global Integration

According to 38 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities' ability to integrate their operations with other organizations in their environment is an important factor that enables Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. Lebanese universities' managers emphasized the significance of local and international integration with other organizations within their environment.

Respondent 6 considered that Lebanese universities lack international and regional activities.

“We do not participate in international and regional activities because we do not have presence in our external environment. Our campuses are located in Lebanon. We can have an external presence through partnerships and joint projects with other universities to add value to our university and offer new ways of collaborations and spread of knowledge”.

Similarly, Respondent 29 considered that;

“Universities should have more international activities. Not just the universities should look at how they can make connections locally with internal organizations, they should also do the same as these international organizations. Lebanese universities should search for new ways to integrate their process and activities with international organizations, to open new opportunities internationally. The new experiences and opportunities can then be used locally, to help universities develop new ways of doing things and bring new practices to the community”.

Respondent 31 considered that Lebanese universities should make new acquisitions or mergers with other universities and organizations locally and globally.

“Lebanese universities should be able locally to integrate new features and attributes with international educational organizations to expand their exposure and have new functions inside Lebanon and provide new forms and services. Universities can share their classes with international organizations, like the British Council, Amidst, and others. The university can offer its auditoriums for distance learning degrees. New partnership and value can be achieved”.

5.3.7.5 Management Guidance and Support

According to 37 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities' management role inside the university affects Lebanese universities' co-evolution process. Most Lebanese universities' managers consider management guidance and support essential for the co-evolutionary approach adopted and applied by Lebanese universities.

Respondent 13 considered that the management role is essential to guide the integration of a co-evolutionary approach within the university.

“Without the proper guidance for new approach adoption, it will be difficult to use and benefit from the new approach outcome. Management can enable the proper utilization of the co-evolutionary approach. Showing the new approach's importance, steps, and repetitively checking its implantation are necessary management roles in guiding new approaches”.

Respondent 5 emphasized the importance of management support for a co-evolutionary approach to be adopted by the university.

“Management support is important for having a new strategy for the university. Management can invoke necessary actions to make us closer to our strategic objectives and correct derivations when

they happen. We do not need the support of departments of facilities, we need management support to keep the flow of it with the help of the university's departments and staff members. To adopt co-evolution strategy, we need additional resources, and changes to be made. Management support will make it easier to take like this decision”.

5.3.7.6 Internal Integration of Co-Evolutionary Mechanism

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that integrating the co-evolutionary approach inside Lebanese universities is essential for Lebanese universities' co-evolution. The majority of Lebanese universities considered that the co-evolutionary approach should be integrated with the main processes and operations to ensure the application of a co-evolutionary process inside Lebanese universities.

Respondent 37 considered that for any co-evolutionary approach to succeed, integration with the main processes is essential.

“Co-evolutionary process is a big project. To be well used, it should be available to use it. The strategy is associated to many areas at the university. One cannot use it here and not use it in other area. To be followed, it should be used alongside universities' processes and replace many processes. It cannot be just the work of this department or this staff; it should be linked to have full value”.

Respondent 32 considered that the co-evolutionary capability building process should be integrated with university practices and activities.

“For co-evolutionary approach to be practically used by the university, its main functions should be used by the university's units. We do not have all the functions, so we need to develop them to utilize them efficiently and effectively. Co-evolution processes should be used by different levels

inside the university. Its functions should be linked to senior managers, middle managers and staff members”.

5.3.7.7 Organizational Means for Interaction

According to 33 out of 39 participants considered that Lebanese universities lack suitable interactive means to interact with their environment and communicate with other environmental actors. Lebanese universities' managers considered that universities needed well-developed interactive tools that enable Lebanese universities to interact with other environmental actors locally and globally.

Respondent 27 considered that there is no formal tool or agent available to interact with other universities.

“We need to develop tools to facilitate interactions with our surrounding, build communication channels, to collaborate and co-work with others. It is important to have public relations team, programs that can be shared, joint team and outreach programs. It is important, to mention that without using the cyber, we cannot expand our reach and develop new ways of communication. We should have virtual platforms to use them for interaction. In the higher education system. We do not have good communication channels with local universities nor with international universities. We live in days where meeting or e-mailing are not efficient to build relations in a connected world”.

Respondent 32 argued that Lebanese universities need new tools to interact with external environmental actors.

“At Lebanese we need new tools to interact with other universities. There are many universities in higher education without tools and systems to interact with each other, whether it is technological tools or physical methods. Universities have difficulty communicating and interacting with each

other without tools and stay limited to their local environment. How we can say that the university is an open system if it is not fully open and able to interact, it should be considered closed without connecting its units and tools”.

5.3.7.8 Altered Ecological Conditions

According to 39 out of 39 participants considered environmental factors important when researching organizations' co-evolution. The participants considered that altered environmental factors constrain Lebanese universities' ability to function normally and affected their development.

According to respondent 38, the Coronavirus pandemic greatly impacted Lebanese higher education services and academic programs.

“Covid-19 has delayed Lebanese universities' progress and activities. We are focused on how we can refine our internal capabilities, to maintain their function during the pandemic, rather than progressing forward”.

Likewise, Respondent 35 stated that;

“Covid-19 has influenced higher education everywhere in the world. We, are trying to decrease its influence. Until then, it will cost us time and money, to respond to what is happening. This pandemic is one of the hardest challenges we are facing. Environmental outbreaks and hazards should be considered new factors that can affect organizations in all countries”.

5.3.7.9 Industry Competitive Dynamics

According to 36 out of 39 participants considered that the industry competitive dynamics are important factors that affect Lebanese universities' co-evolution. The majority of Lebanese

universities' managers considered that rivals' competitive behavior and response between universities has shaped the way universities operate and respond to industry competitive rules.

Respondent 26 considered that replication is the norm for Lebanese universities response to changes within the Lebanese higher education sector.

“Universities in Lebanon do similar processes and have nearly similar outcomes, in a way, it can be said that universities in Lebanon, replicate what other universities do and offer. When a university offers a new service and offers a new process or program, other universities replicate it. The replication is also found in universities response. You can find identical response to the same event happening in the Lebanon”.

Respondent 12 considered that the explorative nature of Lebanese landscape might be challenged by an exploitative action that disrupts the local environment.

“The explorative nature adopted by most Lebanese universities has deprived the higher education system of innovative action. If a new innovative project enters the market, it can affect the Lebanese market and disrupt the Lebanese universities' activities, because they are accustomed with common norm”.

5.3.7.10 Path Dependence

According to 35 out of 39 participants considered that path dependence is an important factor that limits Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of Lebanese managers considered that the approaches adopted over time had limited the ability to make necessary changes to respond to new environmental conditions in Lebanon.

Respondent 16 considered that the adoption of traditional approaches and focus on the local environment negatively affected Lebanese universities' co-evolution ability.

“The path we have taken is affecting us now. We were concerned with the internal more than the external. Old tools we use to make sense of what is happening around us, has determined our position in Lebanon and internationally. Alternatively, we are taking the same adaptive respond, that limited us to the internal environment and constrained our actions and responses. When external influences increased, we found the new situation difficult to be handled with available approaches and tools at our disposal. The path we took worked perfectly in old times. Now it is not easy to keep adopting it and relying on old ways for the new days. For us, we need time to rebuild ourselves and reposition ourselves in our external environment, and several changes need to be done internally, to be able to co-evolve with our environment”.

In addition to the mentioned factors in this section, participants considered universities' contributions and publications (24 out of 39) job-related certificates (19 out of 39) integration of blockchain technology (17 out of 39) initiation of university technology transfer programs (14 out of 39) location and city development of the university (12 out of 39) dual degree offering (9 out of 39) integration of augmented learning methods (5 out of 39) the adoption of mini campus strategy (1 out of 39) can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Given the significance of the introduction of a new capability or process as an organizational outcome, Respondent 27 stated that;

“Universities are sources of knowledge. When we cannot assimilate data from our surroundings and provide new and valuable knowledge for our students and back to our surroundings, we are not doing our job completely, far from our role to provide higher education. We have our faculty

members, research facilities, labs, and students, combining their efforts can provide theoretical and practical contributions including articles, books, research papers and journals”.

5.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, qualitative data were presented and analyzed to understand better the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and the challenges they face to co-evolve with their environment. Qualitative data analyzed in this chapter reveal the competitive nature of Lebanese landscape and the internal and external challenges Lebanese universities face to co-evolve with their environment. The results are relevant to the theoretical and empirical considerations of the academic researchers presented in the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3). Based on empirical evidence, the chapter's findings support the present research's primary aim to investigate the main challenges limiting Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. The following chapter discusses the results presented in this chapter.

Chapter Six: Data Discussion

6.1 Introduction

In the current chapter, the researcher validates the link between the present research, academic contributions, and the practical context of Lebanese higher education. The research aims to explore the main factors affecting Lebanese universities' co-evolution in a competitive environment. The researcher discusses the main themes within Lebanese higher education field concerning the research findings presented in Chapter 5, in accordance with the research objectives, regarding the theoretical overview outlined in the systematic literature review. The chapter discusses each theme and sub-theme separately and concludes with a summary.

6.2 Themes Discussion

In this section, the researcher discusses the main themes identified in Chapter 3, which investigates the co-evolution of Lebanese universities with their environment. The themes are environmental characteristics, influencing external factors, internal factors, competition factors, capability building process, organizational outcome, and mediating factors.

6.2.1 Environmental Characteristics

The first theme in the research; investigates the main relationship between the Lebanese universities and their environment and the mechanism which bind this relation. Organizational co-evolution occurs when reciprocal change occurs between organizations or their environment species as they interact with each other (Abatecola et al., 2020). The mutual effect between the two interacting sides reveals a causal relationship between both sides (Falgueras-Cano et al.,

2021). Co-evolution occurs as a result of mutual selective pressures and adaptation actions between two or more entities, whereas an entity has a causal influence on another entity's evolution process (Yildirim, 2020). Organizational co-evolution is perceived as a process of environmental actors and interactors within a specific or several landscapes (Haider et al., 2020). An organization's co-evolutionary challenges may differ from those of its counterparts in another industry. For that, defining a specific environment, its environmental actors, and conditions is essential to studying organizations' co-evolution (Fatas-Villafranca and Almudi, 2022; Cristofaro, 2022). Several scholars (Abatecola et al., 2020; Chapman and Schott, 2020; Williams and Shepherd et al., 2021; Cristofaro, 2022) emphasized the importance of identifying the binding mechanisms that shape organizations' response and interaction with their environment. Thus, it is essential when investigating the co-evolution of an organization to identify the causal relationship between an organization and its environment (Abatecola et al., 2020).

It was perceived by the research participants that the higher education in Lebanon is limited to the local environment and a causal relationship bind their relation with other environmental actors. Most participants (37 out of 39) considered Lebanese universities were originally established in Lebanon and developed their services and offerings, which led to Lebanese universities' incapability to operate in an external environment other than Lebanese landscape. Lebanese universities' operations and capability development are limited to the local environment. Therefore, the Lebanese higher education landscape is chosen as the best environment for Lebanese universities. Participants (36 out of 39) also considered that Lebanese universities are part of the international higher education environment; however, they are located in Lebanon and simultaneously satisfy international higher education standards. Participants (34 out of 39) have noted that the influencing number of external factors and the entrance of new competitors into

Lebanon have altered Lebanese higher education landscape into a competitive one. In addition, participants (36 out of 39) considered that the new competitors' offerings had influenced Lebanese universities' ability to compete and face local and global challenges. Resulting in inbound interaction with their environment and other environmental actors and limiting it to a reactive response, by which natural selection is perceived to be preponderant in Lebanese higher education landscape as outlined by most participants (35 out of 39) of this research.

The bound relationship between Lebanese universities and their organizational environment revealed in this research is in line with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) and several past researches (Kompella, 2020; Riasanow et al., 2020; Abatecola, 2020; Hallett and Hawbaker, 2021; Daudin et al., 2021; Chapman and Schott, 2020; Williams and Shepherd et al., 2021; Cristofaro, 2022) that emphasized the importance of the identification of the causal relationship between organizations and their environment, to analyze further the internal and external influencing factors. Thus, the ability of organizational co-evolution can be investigated.

The causal relationship between organizations and their environment reinforces prior studies (Amati et al., 2021; Paniccia and Baiocco, 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Kytzia et al., 2020; Jovanovic et al., 2021; Xing et al., 2022; Han et al., 2022) that suggest the important role of identifying the causal relationship between organizations and their environment to investigate organizational co-evolution. Han et al. (2022) investigated the co-evolution of bike-sharing firms in China. The research investigates the causal relationship between bike-sharing and their environment and the factors limiting their competitiveness with their environment. In the mentioned research, the researchers first identified the bound relation between bike-sharing firms and their environment and then identified the factors affecting their firms' competitiveness and limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

The significance of identifying the causal relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment and other higher education institutions locally and internationally is aligned with the co-evolutionary approach to investigating the co-evolution of Lebanese universities (Benner, 2022). The finding reveals the perception and response of Lebanese universities to their environment and environmental actors and the mechanism that bound their relation, is essential to investigate the co-evolution of Lebanese universities with their environment.

In the following section, the researcher discusses the external factors influencing Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

6.2.2 External Influencing Factors

The second set of influencing factors relates to external factors that are considered an important component of any co-evolutionary approach that includes external factors that limit Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their environment. External factors had a significant role in determining Lebanese capabilities and their response to environmental changes in the higher education landscape. The four sub-themes considered as the main external influencing factors by the research participants include Technological factors, Communication infrastructure, New competitors, and Social factors.

6.2.2.1 Technological Factors

Technological factors were found in this research to significantly influence participants' responses to the main external factors influencing Lebanese university landscape. This research indicates that access and the rise of new advanced technologies affect Lebanese universities' ability to stay fit and compete with their environment. The majority of participants in the present research (34 out of 39) considered that the technology development rate challenges Lebanese universities'

ability to make changes and adapt to new technologies. Participants (35 out of 39) stated that the inability to access advanced technologies limited organizations' ability to develop their capabilities and achieve sustainable advantage, especially when competing organizations adopt advanced technologies and exploit their advantages.

Technological factors influence is consistent with the findings of several researchers (Peter, 2020; Herath et al., 2020; Rath et al., 2021; Beier et al., 2020; Siew et al., 2020; Zilberova et al., 2020) who reported that technological factors are important external factors that shape organizational capabilities, response and outcome. This research reaffirms the findings of several studies mentioned above. These studies suggested that the speed and pace of new emerging technologies make it difficult for organizations worldwide to access and adopt them within their systems.

The significant influence of technological factors on organizations' external environment is in line with several research which identified the influence of technological factors on organizations (Nahar, 2021; Banda, 2020; Nazir, 2019; Lau, 2020; Engidaw, 2021; Zhang, 2021). Engidaw (2021) investigated the influence of external factors on organizations' performance in Ethiopia. Engidaw (2021) research revealed the significant role of technological factors and how the ability to access and acquire advanced technologies shaped the performance and growth of small and medium-sized enterprises in Ethiopia.

6.2.2.1 Communication Infrastructure

Moving on to the next external influencing factor, the results of the present research show that Lebanese universities are influenced by the lack of proper communication infrastructure in Lebanon the fact that. Lack of proper communication infrastructure factor limits Lebanese

universities' capabilities and deprives them of an essential tool for improvement and advancement since communication infrastructure is essential in Lebanese universities' processes. Most participants (36 of 39) considered that because Lebanon lacks telecommunications infrastructure, Lebanese universities are deprived of essential tools inside Lebanon. Participants considered telecommunication infrastructure essential for Lebanese universities to develop their abilities and operations and provide new services.

The external influence of communication infrastructure on an organization supports the results obtained by several researchers (Eliwa et al., 2022; Vasilev et al., 2020; Franca et al., 2021); Lima, 2021; Wang et al., 2021) indicating that the availability of communication infrastructure provides suitable environments for organizations to grow, expand their operations, and develop a new outcome. Wang et al. (2021) considered that advanced access to communication infrastructure allows organizations to achieve community mobilization, connectivity, sharing of knowledge, and integration into the knowledge economy. According to Vasilev et al. (2020) the availability of advanced internet and communication infrastructure can increase productivity, competitiveness and support organizations in achieving digital transformation.

The significant influence of communication infrastructure on an organization's environment is similar to other research that investigated communication infrastructure in different environments (Mwantimwa, 2019; Zhou, 2019; Araujo, 2020; Jere and Ngidi, 2020). Zhou (2019) investigated the role of information and communication technologies in supporting the development of China. The findings show that the availability of information and communication technologies can support the development of innovative capabilities in an organization that operates in the same area.

6.2.2.3 The Entrance of New Competitors

This research considered new competitors' entrance as a significant external influencing factor. Participants of this research considered that the entrance of new competitors into Lebanese higher education landscape has influenced Lebanese universities' competitiveness and transformed Lebanese higher education environment into a competitive landscape. The majority of participants (34 of 39) considered that Lebanese universities' traditional offering was challenged by the new programs and offerings provided by new educational providers. In addition, participants argued that the newly entered competitors disrupted Lebanese higher education competition norms.

The influence of the entrance of new environmental actors into a new landscape, of which other organizations of the same industry provide similar services and products, was noted by several scholars (Younger and Fisher, 2020; Darvishmotevali and Koseoglu, 2020; Klimas and Fredrich, 2022; Berman et al., 2022). Berman et al. (2022) considered that the new entrance of new organizations into a new industry landscape could become rivals to the existing organization, and if these competitors own better capabilities, this can affect the ability of the existing organizations and organizational environment conditions. Younger and Fisher (2020) considered that the emergence of new competitors, or organizational forms inside an environment, should be acknowledged by other organizations that operate in the same environment. Younger and Fisher (2020) emphasised that new organizational forms are usually initiated by a pioneering venture adopting new organizational design and strategy, which can disrupt the landscape, and thus affect other organizations within a certain environment.

The significant influence of newly entered competitors on the organization's external environment is in line with the findings of this research (Etemad, 2019; Sikumbang, 2019; Tian et al., 2020; Tsenduren and Chuluunbat, 2020; Ogunyemi, 2020; Wales et al., 2021) which considered that

the emergence of new competitors is an important external actor influencing organizations in their local environment. Ogunyemi (2020) investigated the factors affecting Nigerian companies' competitiveness. (Ogunyemi, 2020). The findings of the mentioned research show that new competitors entering Nigeria have affected small and medium-sized companies' ability to compete. Ogunyemi (2020) found that the local environment in Nigeria is becoming a multiplier environment that can be affected by a new competitor from the external environment, which has the potential to disrupt the environment's setting and increase its competitiveness intensity.

6.2.2.4 Social Factors

Social factors were considered a main external factor influencing Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants of this research considered that new environmental changes have resulted in altered preferences and demands for new services and programs, exerting additional external pressure on Lebanese universities. Participants (37 out of 39) considered that the use of advanced technologies, the opening of the markets, and the emergence of new teaching methods have exerted additional external factors on Lebanese universities. The new external factors require Lebanese universities to make internal and external changes to their processes and services, requiring more resources and capabilities, which the universities lack or are unable to access.

The effect of changing social factors as an external factor on organization was noted by several scholars (Daugaard, 2019; Ghahtarani et al., 2020; Broccardoa and Zicarib, 2020; Lim et al., 2022). Lim et al. (2022) that suggested that new social factors have emerged from the local and global environment, affecting customers' needs and requirements. Broccardoa and Zicarib (2020) argued that organizations should re-evaluate their systems and services and renew customer value in response to new social norms.

The significant influence of changing social factors on the organization's external environment confirms the findings of several research (Nazir, 2019; Mageed, 2021; Dada, 2021; Xuan, 2021; Hamer and Smith, 2021; Almaiah et al., 2020; Alenezi, 2021) which suggested the effect of social factors on changing customers' preferences and needs. Alenezi (2021) investigated several social factors that affect students' online learning satisfaction. Alenezi (2021) found that social factors, namely, social interaction, social space, social identity, ease of online learning, and the emergence of working from jobs, affected students' satisfaction with online learning significantly. The results show that several social factors affect students' preferences and needs, which require higher education institutions to make necessary changes in their processes, services, and products offered to satisfy altered preferences and needs.

The significance of the effect of a social factor on organizations is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests the effect of external factors on organizations' internal and external environment and organizational ability to co-evolve with their environment (Li et al., 2020; Shuffler, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020; Shattuck et al., 2020; Bocken and Geradts; 2020; Diaz and Peli., 2020; Kaipainen). The findings of this research show that technological factors, communication infrastructure, the entrance of new competitors, and social factors are the main external factors influencing Lebanese universities and limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

Having discussed the findings related to the second theme, the next section presents a discussion of the findings related to the influencing internal factors.

6.2.3 Internal Influencing Factors

The third set of factors in the research is related to the influencing internal factors, which is an integral part of any co-evolutionary approach and includes organizational factors that limit

Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Internal factors had a significant role in determining Lebanese capabilities and their response to environmental changes in the higher education landscape. The three sub-themes that were considered as the main internal influencing factors by the research participants are organizational resources, which include physical, financial, information, knowledge resources, organizational structure, and organizational processes.

6.2.3.1 Organizational Resources

Organizational resources were considered a main internal factor that influenced Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants of the present research considered that the universities' physical, financial, information, and knowledge resources shape their internal environment and capabilities.

6.2.3.1.1 Physical Resources

Organizational physical resources were considered a main internal influencing factor, affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants (38 out of 39) in this research regarded university physical resources as an important internal factor limiting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their surroundings. Participants of this research argued that Lebanese universities own research facilities, labs, equipment, and buildings provide additional value to their offerings and sustain their operations and competitiveness. Therefore, it is important for universities to possess suitable and advanced physical resources.

The influence of physical resources on organizations' abilities and capabilities was noted by several scholars (Murimi et al., 2019; Hong and Kim et al., 2020; Brennan et al., 2020; Ferreira et al.,

2022; Hong and Kim et al. (2020) who suggested that possessing varied, unique, and rare tangible resources provides better organizational performance and a sustainable competitive advantage. Murimi et al. (2019) considered that organizations should constantly identify and exploit new tangible resources to achieve superior performance. Brennan et al. (2020) considered that the integration of organizational physical resources with advanced technologies enables an organization to improve its processes, production and services, research and development, and performance.

The significant influence of physical resources on the internal environment of an organization is in line with the findings of this research (Lee et al., 2019; Ramon-Jeronimo et al., 2019; Eric et al., 2019; Murimi et al., 2019) which suggested that organizational physical resources influence the operations development and performance of an organization. Murimi et al. (2019) investigated the influence of tangible organizational resources on small and medium companies and manufacturers' performance in Kenya. Murimi et al. (2019) found that continuous investment in tangible resources has enhanced Kenyan companies and manufacturers' ability to exploit their tangible resources to generate better value and improve organizational performance.

The significance of organizational physical resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that the internal organizational environment is determined primarily by its physical resources, their level, and their combination outcome shape the ability of an organization to operate, process inputs and outputs and compete within its environment.

6.2.3.1.2 Organizational Financial Resources

Lebanese universities' financial resources were considered a main internal influencing factor, affecting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants of this research (34 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities' financial resources limit their operations and ability to make necessary developments. Participants argued that the pre-determined budget is inflexible and deprives the university of the opportunity to pursue new research and further developments.

The influence of financial resources on the organizations' abilities and capabilities was noted by several scholars (Okari et al., 2019; Owusu et al., 2021; Bakhtiari et al., 2020; Muthama and Wurai, 2021). According to Bakhtiari et al. (2020) financial capacity refers to an organization's ability to generate and administer funds and organizational and physical resources. Lack of financial resources impedes organizational performance, growth, and the ability to introduce new innovative products and services (Owusu et al., 2019). Moscalu et al. (2020) considered that, financial management is critical for an organization to develop and re-innovate its capabilities, seize opportunities, and carry out new projects and ventures. The significant influence of financial resources on the ability of an organization to develop its capabilities and carry out competitive actions within its environment is in line with the findings of several research (Nitto, 2020; Dambala, 2021; Owusu et al., 2021; Perez-Alaniz et al., 2022) which suggested financial resources directly affect the ability of an organization to pursue its purpose, expand and grow in the market. Owusu et al. (2021) investigated the effect of organizational financial resources on building capacity among small and medium enterprises in Ghana. Owusu et al. (2021) found that financial resources have a significant effect on the performance of small and medium supply chains and suggested that multiple financial resource sources can ensure the sustainability, competitiveness,

and performance of small and medium supply chains. The significance of organizational financial resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which emphasizes the importance of organizational resources, including financial resources, and their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

6.2.3.1.3 Technological Resources

Lebanese universities' technological resources were considered a main internal influencing factor, affecting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (36 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities' technological resources are limited, influencing Lebanese universities' processes and outcomes. Participants of the present research argued that the pre-determined budget deprives the university of pursuing several opportunities to seize advanced technologies, like artificial intelligence, that can lead to further developments. The influence of technological resources on the development of organizations' abilities and capabilities was noted by several scholars (Garcia-Sanchez et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2019; Dhasarathy et al., 2020; Nadkarni and Prugl, 2021). Dhasarathy et al. (2020) suggested that technological resources are an essential element of any organization seeking transformation, contrary to the past when modern technology was linked to organizations' performance and capabilities. Nadkarni and Prugl (2021) considered that an organization's ability to achieve digital transformation is based on its existing technological resources. Zhang et al. (2019) argued that organizational suitability is closely linked to the adoption of high technology and innovation management. The significant influence of a lack of advanced technological resources on an organization's capabilities, outcomes, and competitiveness is in line with the findings of several pieces of research (Mahler and Westergren, 2019; Yadav et al., 2020; Budd et al., 2020; Haefner et al., 2021) which suggested

the effect of technological resources on the ability of an organization to sustain its competitive advantage and survival within its landscape. Haefner et al. (2021) studied the influence of adopting new technologies on organizations and human resources. Haefner et al. (2021) found that technological resources impact an organization's ability to embrace digital transformation and become digitalized. In addition, Haefner et al. (2021) found that new technologies replaced human resources inside these organizations. The significance of organizational and technological resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests the effect of organizational resources, including financial resources, and their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

6.2.3.1.4 Informational Resources

Lebanese universities' informational resources were considered a main internal influencing factor, affecting their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants argued that lack of advanced informational resources and tools, is affecting Lebanese universities' capabilities and outcome. The majority of respondents (35 out of 39) considered that there is a lack of advanced informational resources and tools, hindering Lebanese universities' ability to produce valuable knowledge and assets.

The influence of informational resources on the development of organizations' capabilities, processes, and outcomes was noted by several scholars (Chatterjee et al., 2020; Altindag and Ongel et al., 2021; Gaviria-Marin et al., 2021; Awwad et al., 2022; Pashutan et al., 2022). Pashutan et al. (2022) argued that the investment in organizational informational resources is becoming essential, as informational resources are considered strategic resources that an organization can use to develop its capabilities, outcomes, and ability to compete to achieve its goals. Chatterjee et al.

(2020) considered that organizations could use information technology to foster innovation and explorative search behavior. Gaviria-Marin et al. (2021) believed that information and communication technology influences organizational capabilities, innovation, and performance. The significant influence of a lack of organizational information resources on the internal environment of an organization confirms the findings of several researchers (Melian-Alzola et al., 2020; Shahzad et al., 2020; Mikalef and Gupta, 2021; Makhoulfi et al., 2021) which suggested the effect of lack of informational resources on organizational capabilities, ability to innovate and performance. Melian-Alzola et al. (2020) investigated the use of information technology on hotels' ability to stay fit and compete in the Canary Islands. The research results confirmed the role of information technology in enhancing hotels' agility, considering the importance of IT management and its application inside hotels.

The significance of organizational informational resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests the effect of organizational resources, including information resources, on the internal environment of an organization, which limits its ability to co-evolve with its environment.

6.2.3.2 Organizational Structure

Moving on to the following internal factors, the present research results show that Lebanese universities' internal environment is influenced by the lack of a new and innovative organizational structure, which limits their ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of this research participants (36 out of 39) considered that the new environmental conditions require Lebanese universities to be less structured. Participants suggested that Lebanon's universities should develop and improve their structures to achieve sustainability and fitness in their environment.

This significant influence on organizational structure supports the results obtained by several researchers (Andersson et al., 2019; Palepu et al., 2020; Duchek, 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021; Verhoef et al., 2021) indicating that the availability of communication infrastructure provides suitable environments for organizations to grow, expand their operations, and develop new outcomes.

Duchek (2020) stated that the traditional organizational structure is disrupted by new environmental influences. Modern environmental influences demand modern organizational structures to be more flexible and faster at making decisions and delivering output (Verhoef et al., 2021). Andersson et al. (2019) argued that a fit, flat, and fast organizational structure allows for more agility and ability to provide value.

The significant influence of rigid organizational structure is in line with the findings of this research (Torres Zapata, 2019; Wittrock et al., 2021; Rakova et al., 2021; Nowotny et al., 2022) which suggested that organizational structure determines organizational flexibility, fitness, and performance. Nowotny et al. (2022) investigated the effect of organizational structure on multiple European companies' performance. The research results illustrate the significant influence of organizational structure on companies' ability to make necessary changes, adapt, and enhance their ability to offer value.

The significance of organizational informational resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that organizational structure influences an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment.

6.2.3.2 Organizational Processes

Organizational processes were considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Most participants (36 out of 39) considered that universities' processes are important internal factors that limit Lebanese universities to co-evolve with their

environment. Participants argued that internal and external factors may negatively or positively affect the development of the capabilities of Lebanese universities and their interactions with their environments.

The impact of organizational processes on organizational capabilities, operations, and outcomes has been studied by several researchers (Sunmola and Javahernia, 2021; Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020; Kosieradzka and Rostek, 2021; Roglinger et al., 2022). Kelly and Cordeiro (2020) who outlined that organizational processes are influenced by the rise of new digital capabilities that, if utilized appropriately, can allow an organization to initiate innovation and readiness for future environmental influences. Sunmola and Javahernia (2021) have argued that the deployment of process innovation within an organization is crucial to administering, developing, and implementing the necessary changes to handle external influences. Kosieradzka and Rostek (2021) considered that organizational performance and capabilities could be determined by the organizational ability to improve, develop, and innovate its processes. The significant influence of organizational process is in line with the findings of this research (Mwantimwa, 2019; Akpoviro et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2019; Aguiar-Quintana et al., 2020; Jere and Ngidi, 2020) which suggested that organizational process innovation influences organizational capabilities to pursue its objectives and deliver its products and services. Akpoviro et al. (2019) studied the impact of process innovation on the organizational performance of several telecommunication companies in Nigeria. Akpoviro et al. (2019) found a correlation between process innovation and organizational performance, sales, collaboration with other organizations, and readiness for altered environmental factors.

The significance of organizational processes is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that organizational processes influence the internal environment of an organization, its capabilities, and ability to co-evolve in a competitive environment.

The following section discusses findings related to factors that influence Lebanese universities' management capabilities.

6.2.4 Management Capabilities

The third set of influencing factors relates to the factors influencing Lebanese universities' managerial capabilities. Management capabilities are considered an essential component of any co-evolutionary approach, limiting an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment. Several factors were identified that significantly affected Lebanese managerial capabilities. The four sub-themes considered the main factors affecting the managerial capabilities at Lebanese universities are influencing factors by the research participants, including administrative role, strategic intentionality, bounded rationality, explorative search, and managerial absorptive capacity.

6.2.4.1 Limited Managerial Role

The limited managerial role of Lebanese universities' management was considered a main factor that influenced Lebanese management capabilities at Lebanese universities, which can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (36 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities' management role is limited to internal administrative tasks within the university. Participants argued that Lebanese universities' management is focused on internal university administration and has limited engagement with its external environment. In addition, participants outlined that the managerial

role at Lebanese universities is focused on what is happening inside the university, controlling, monitoring, and improving daily internal tasks.

The influence of the limited managerial role of an organization on its interaction with its environment was noted by several scholars (Le and Lei, 2019; Alhawamdeh and Alsmairat, 2019; Ambrosini and Altintas, 2019; Widiyanto et al., 2021; Tasheva and Nielsen, 2022).

Ambrosini and Altintas (2019) outlined that management roles should not be linked to the internal environment of an organization; however, managers should realize their role in both the internal and external organizational environment. Widiyanto et al. (2021) argued that management role is evolving across different organizations to include the management influence on their environment. Tasheva and Nielsen (2022) suggested that while traditional managers perform classical tasks inside their organizations and limit external actions within their environments, the concept of 'global dynamic managers' is rising within management research.

The significant influence of a limited managerial role is in line with the findings of this research (Holzmayer and Schmidt, 2020; Haapanen et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Lyu et al., 2022) which suggested that management has a leading role in developing, transforming and improving the abilities and capabilities of an organization as a response to external environmental influencing factors.

Haapanen et al. (2020) investigated the role of senior managers in developing existing organizational resources and capabilities and the international growth of several organizations.

The study results reveal that management has an essential role in leading the development of organizational capabilities and the ability of organizations to adapt and expand internationally.

The significance of a limited managerial role is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that managers' role in managing the relationship between organizations and their

environment leads to necessary changes and the development of organizational abilities and capabilities to co-evolve with their environment.

6.2.4.2 Strategic Intentionality

Lack of strategic intentionality was considered as a main factor that influences Lebanese management capabilities at Lebanese universities, which has the potential to affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

The majority of participants in this research (35 out of 39) considered that Lebanese managers lack strategic internality. Participants argued that the lack of strategic intentionality is a main limitation of management capabilities and roles, resulting in adaptive behavior. In addition, participants argued that Lebanese market emphasized the cultivation of strategic intentionality and proactive actions by universities' management.

The effect of the lack of strategic intentionality on the organizations' abilities and capabilities was noted by several scholars (Hutzschenreuter et al., 2019; Pedersen et al., 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Wang, 2022).

Hutzschenreuter et al. (2019) considered that there is a lack of management studies that study managerial intentionality, which is essential to determining a central building block of management capabilities inside an organization. Levinthal (2021) believed that the lack of managerial intentionality in changing circumstances and conditions in an organizational environment leads to inertia. Wang (2022) identified management intentionality as a capability of an organization to make necessary changes and development to its capabilities, processes, and outcomes in response to external influences, achieving fitness and agility within its environment.

The influence of lack of managerial intentionality is in line with the findings of prior research (Hamidov et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2021; Makowski, 2021 Farndale et al., 2021) which

suggested that managerial intentionality is an essential attribute of modern management which is challenged by altered environmental conditions.

Nguyen et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between the sustainability of international pulp and paper companies and managerial intentionality. The study's results illustrated that there is a positive relationship between organizational sustainability and management strategic intentionality. The results of the mentioned research showed that senior management and executives of the best-performing organizations could sustain their operations and positions in the market, if they adopt strategic intentionality, take proactive actions, and be determined to face environmental challenges.

The significant influence of lack of strategic intentionality on managerial capabilities is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests strategic intentionality an essential managerial characteristic required in the organizational co-evolution process.

6.2.4.3 Bounded Rationality

Bounded rationality was considered a main factor that influences Lebanese management capabilities at Lebanese universities, which can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants in this research (34 out of 39) considered bounded rationality to be an important factor influencing managerial capabilities, perceptions, and actions at Lebanese universities. Participants argued that bounded rationality determines how Lebanese universities' managers make sense, scan their surroundings, and make decisions accordingly.

The influence of bounded rationality on managerial capabilities is in line with the findings of this research (Hernandez, 2019; Hernandez and Ortega, 2019; Lejarraga and Pindard-Lejarraga, 2020; Shafran et al., 2020).

Hernandez and Ortega (2019) argued that bounded rationality determines managerial decisions' rationality. Lejarraga and Pindard-Lejarraga (2020) considered that 'Ecological Rationality' is new managerial research that studies management's decisions based on environmental conditions. Shafran et al. (2020) considered that bounded rationality research enables researchers to study the link between management's cognitive abilities and organizational development and performance. The influence of managerial bounded rationality is in line with the findings of this research (Hong, 2019; Burgos et al., 2020; Jordao et al., 2020; Gong and Diao, 2022) that suggested that managerial bounded rationality affects sense-making, analysis, decision-making process of managers inside an organization, which affect its outcome and response to environmental influences.

Jordao et al. (2020) studied the managerial decision-making process of port and construction companies in Brazil to identify the impact of bounded rationality on their decision-making process. Jordao et al. (2020) found that managerial bounded rationality impacted decisions made in both sectors and concluded that overconfidence, optimism, and anchoring are the main factors affecting management team capabilities.

The significance of managerial bounded rationality is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that bound rationality affects decision-makers' cognitive capabilities, resulting in poor decisions and responses to external environmental influencing factors.

6.2.4.4 Lack of Explorative Search

Explorative search was considered a main factor that influences management capabilities at Lebanese universities, which could potentially affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of this research participants (37 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities lack explorative search behavior and the ability to develop or introduce new or innovative capabilities. It was argued by participants that Lebanese universities' search

behaviors hindered their ability to improve their capabilities and replicate processes from other universities that operate in a similar environment.

The effect of managerial exploitive search behavior on organizational capabilities, organizational outcomes, and competitiveness was noted by several scholars (Valenzuela-Fernandez and Penaloza-Briones, 2019; Riera and Iijima., 2019; Arzubiaga et al., 2019; Marin-Idarraga et al., 2020).

Marin-Idarraga et al. (2020) considered that an organization's ability to adopt exploitative or exploratory search behavior depends on its internal and external factors, contrary to other researchers that focus only on internal organizational factors. Valenzuela-Fernandez and Penaloza-Briones (2019) linked an organization's search behavior to its managerial capabilities, strategies, ability to exploit internal resources, and sense-making capability.

The significant influence of the lack of explorative search behavior on managerial capabilities is in line with the findings of this research (Saldanha et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2020; Trivellato et al., 2020; Semke and Tiberius, 2020). Semke and Tiberius (2020) studied the impact of managerial sensing capabilities on companies' search behavior. Semke and Tiberius (2020) found that the combination of managerial capabilities and organizational capabilities can help organizations adapt to their environment and determine their search behavior.

The significance of the lack of exploratory search behavior is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that managerial search behavior can affect the ability of an organization to renovate or create new capabilities, which constrain its competitiveness and ability to provide innovative processes, products, and services.

6.2.4.5 Absorptive Capacity

Limited absorptive capacity was considered as a main factor that influences management capabilities at Lebanese universities, which can affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants in this research (35 out of 39) considered that the lack of absorptive capacity limits Lebanese universities from adequately analyzing their external environment. Participants argued that the external environment's causal ambiguity and limited absorptive abilities are the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' analysis abilities. In addition, participants outlined that Lebanese universities lack adequate processes, methods and tools to collect data on regional and global environment and generate value of it to anticipate or acknowledge what is happening in the international higher education system.

The effect of lack of absorptive capacity on management capabilities was noted by several scholars (Butler and Ferlie, 2019; Muller et al., 2020; Dabic et al., 2020; Tidd, 2021).

Butler and Ferlie (2019) suggested that a lack of adequate absorptive capacity limits the organizational ability to assimilate data from the organizations' external environment, analyze it, and generate valuable data from it to use it as a strategic asset and construct an objective view of the organizations' surroundings. Muller et al. (2020) emphasized the significant role of absorptive capacity in re-innovating organizations by enabling organizations to exploit knowledge from their surroundings to initiate explorative and exploitative search strategies.

The significant influence of limited managerial absorptive capacity is in line with the findings of this research (Medase and Barasa, 2019; Senivongse et al., 2019; Sancho-Zamora, 2021; Asogwa et al., 2020) which suggested that absorptive capacity can affect management's perception of their external environment, and ability to recognize and apply valuable external knowledge. Asogwa et al. (2020) investigated the impact of absorptive capacity on Nigerian manufacturers and service

providers' innovation. Asogwa et al. (2020) found that absorptive capacity is closely related to the ability of an organization to develop new programs, strategies, and innovative services, products, and processes that improve organizational performance.

The significance of managerial absorptive capacity is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that absorptive capacity can constrain management capabilities, reflecting on innovative processes and data acquisition and conversion to valuable assets.

Having discussed the findings related to the second theme of this research, the next section presents a discussion of the findings related to the factors that influence Lebanese universities' competitiveness.

6.2.5 Competition Factors

The fourth set of factors in the research relates to the influencing factors that affect an organization's competitiveness. Identifying factors that shape an organization's competitiveness is considered an essential component of any co-evolutionary approach. Organizational competitive strategies can affect an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment. The competitive strategies adopted by Lebanese universities had a significant role in shaping Lebanese universities' ability to compete and co-evolve with their environment. The four sub-themes that the present research participants identified as the prime factors affecting the competitiveness of Lebanon's universities are the adoption of a resource-based strategy, lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable Resources (VRIO), irreversibility, and lack of skilled human resources.

6.2.5.1 Adoption of Resource-Based Strategy

Adopting a resource-based strategy was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this

research (34 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities competitiveness is based on resource-based approach. Participants argued that adopting a resource-based view as a competitive approach by Lebanese universities is limiting Lebanese universities' competitiveness with their environmental rivals. Participants considered that Lebanese universities mainly use internal physical resources as the main source of competitiveness and disregard knowledge-based approaches.

The effect of the adoption of resource-based approaches as the main competition strategy in a competitive environment was noted by several scholars (Davis and DeWitt, 2021; Griggs, 2021; Celtekligil et al., 2021; Nurjaman et al., 2021). Nurjaman et al. (2021) stated that utilizing strategic resources within an organization can enable it to compete with competitors' resources, develop new capabilities, processes, products, and services, and enhance its agility and fitness within its environment. On the contrary, Griggs (2021) argued that organizational resource-based strategy alone does not lead to organizational innovation and suggested that an organization's process management, design thinking, and other internal factors are essential in the innovative process of an organization.

The significant influence of the adoption of a resource-based strategy on the competitiveness of an organization is in line with the findings of this research (Chumphong et al., 2020; Collins, 2021; Laura D'Oria et al., 2021; Beamish and Chakravarty, 2021) which suggested that adoption of a resource-based strategy can enhance the abilities of an organization; however, it needs to be integrated with other strategies and organizational elements or units to efficiently enable an organization to generate value, re-innovate its capabilities, and products, and achieve competitive advantage. Chumphong et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between adopting a resource-based perspective and dynamic organizational capabilities in small and medium-sized companies

in Thailand. Chumphong et al. (2020) found that a resource-based view alone does not enhance organizational performance and competitiveness and it needs to be integrated with other approaches, supported by management, and integrated with organizational dynamic capabilities.

The significance of resource-based strategy adoption is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that integrating a resource-based perspective alone, disregarding other approaches like the knowledge-based approach with other essential organizational factors limits organizational performance and competitiveness and the ability to co-evolve with their environment.

6.2.5.2 Lack of Valuable, Rare Imitable, and Organizable Resources (VRIO)

The lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants in this research (35 out of 39) considered that the lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) affected Lebanese universities' ability to compete with other environmental rivals. Participants considered that Lebanese universities own imitable resources and lack imitable resources.

The effect of the lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) on an organization's ability to compete was noted by several scholars (Kim and Makadok, 2021; Nikmah et al., 2021; Kaukab et al., 2020; Mielcarek and Dymitrowski, 2022). Kim and Makadok (2021) suggested that possessing valuable, rare, and imitable resources inside enhances an organization's ability to compete and generate a unique organizational outcome. Murcia (2020) considered that valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) provide organizations with a competitive advantage since they cannot be replicated or substituted. Bia et al. (2019) argued that

continuous evaluation of organizational resources is essential to assess their rarity, value, imitability and development for additional value.

The significant influence of the lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) on an organization's competitiveness is in line with the findings of this research (Buzatu et al., 2019; Widiati and Sefudin, 2019; Migowski et al., 2019; Murcia, 2022) which suggested the effect of social factors on changing customers' preferences and needs. Murcia et al. (2022) studied how organizational resources and capabilities characteristics can enhance an organization's ability to compete and achieve higher performance in several international small and medium-sized companies. Murcia et al. (2022) believed that organizational resources and capabilities that have distinct characteristics, including rare, imitable, and valuable, contribute to organizational competitive advantage.

The significance of the effect of a lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that an organization's ability to own valuable rare and imitable resources enhances its capabilities, organizational outcome, and competitiveness.

6.2.5.3 Lack of Skilled Human Resources

The lack of skilled human resources was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants in this research (34 out of 39) considered that the shortage of skilled human resources is an important factor affecting Lebanese universities' competitiveness. Participants considered that the availability of skilled human resources affects Lebanese universities' teaching and research offerings and further development. The effect of a lack of skilled human resources on an organization's ability to compete was noted by several scholars (Werdhiastutie et al., 2020;

Sedyastuti et al., 2021; Karman et al., 2022; Piwowar-Sulej, 2022). Piwowar-Sulej (2022) who argued that there is a shortage of skilled workers among many organizations from different industries due to disruptive environmental conditions. Sedyastuti (2021) believed that organizations should continuously ensure that they have skilled human capital relevant to the environmental setting and suggested continual training, knowledge sharing, collaborations with other educational institutions and the development of existing human capital skills and abilities inside organizations.

The significant influence of the lack of skilled human resources on the competitiveness of an organization is in line with the findings of this research (Tien et al., 2021; Sim et al., 2021; Wu and Kao, 2022; Sharma et al., 2022; Valecha, 2022) which suggested skilled human resources enhance the skill variety, improvement of organizational operations, capability building process and outcome of an organization. Sim et al. (2021) investigated the impact of outsourcing skilled human resources on achieving a varied of skills and enhance organizational performance for Malaysian manufacturers. The research results revealed that outsourcing skilled human resources directly impacts manufacturers' ability to achieve and improve organizational performance. The research indicated that a specific set of criteria must be incorporated into the outsourcing framework to maximize the benefits of the outsourcing process and the improvements made to human capital.

The significance of the availability of highly skilled human resources is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that skilled human resources enhance organizational processes and capability building routines and offer better value and competitiveness.

After discussing the factors affecting Lebanese universities' competitiveness, the following section discusses the main factors that affect Lebanese universities' capability building process.

6.2.6 Capability Building Process

The fifth set of factors in this research relates to factors that affect organizations' capability building process. Identifying the factors that affect the capability building process inside an organization is considered an essential component of any co-evolutionary approach. Organizational capability building processes can affect an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment. Lebanese universities' capability building process significantly shaped universities' ability to develop their capabilities and co-evolve with their environment. The three sub-themes considered the main influencing factors by the participants are lack of dynamic capabilities, capability refinement, and the co-evolutionary capability building process.

6.2.6.1 Lack of Dynamic Capabilities Process

The lack of a dynamic capability process was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (36 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities' capability building processes are focused mainly on capability proliferation. Participants considered that the capability building process of Lebanese universities cannot re-innovate existing capabilities or introduce new innovative solutions and capabilities in Lebanese market.

The effect of the lack of a dynamic capability process on an organization's ability to develop its capabilities was noted by several scholars (Siems et al., 2021; Cyfert et al., 2021; Mikalef et al., 2022; Farzaneh et al., 2022). In a competitive environment, Farzaneh et al. (2020) proposed that organizations pursuing innovative approaches need dynamic capabilities to achieve innovation ambidexterity. Mikalef et al. (2022) emphasized the role of dynamic capabilities in allowing

organizations worldwide to adapt, re-innovate, and develop organizational capabilities to face external challenges.

The significant influence of the lack of a dynamic capability process on organizational capabilities is in line with the findings of this research (Paavola, 2021; Bocken and Geradts, 2020; Engstrom and Norman, 2021; Linde et al., 2021) which suggested that dynamic capabilities impact the ability of an organization to develop its existing capabilities or introduce new capabilities and processes to face environmental influences. Engstrom and Norman (2021) investigated the impact of dynamic capabilities on organizational performance and outcomes in farming in Sweden. It was found that organizational dynamic capabilities play a significant role in enabling organizations to sustain their operations, enhance their outcomes, and make innovations possible.

The significance of the effect of Lack of dynamic capabilities process is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that dynamic capabilities process enhances the ability of an organization to re-innovate and develop organizational capabilities to face external challenges.

6.2.6.2 Capability Refinement

Lack of capability creation and dependence on capability refinement was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (37 out of 39) considered that focusing on capability refinement shapes the outcome of Lebanese universities' capability building process. The majority of Lebanese universities' managers considered that Lebanese universities' capability building process lacks capability creation and is limited to improving existing capabilities.

The dependence on capability refinement as an organizational capability building process and its effect on organizational capabilities development and organisation's competitiveness was noted

by several scholars (Valenzuela-Fernandez and Penaloza-Briones, 2019; Reim et al., 2020; Hillmann and Guenther, 2021; Montealegre and Iyengar, 2021).

Hillmann and Guenther (2021) considered that innovation through capability building process is essential for organizations to achieve sustainable competitive advantage and emphasized on the internal coordination of different units to sustain innovative organizational behavior. Montealegre and Iyengar (2021) suggested that a balance between capabilities renewal and refinement should be adopted due to organizations' inability to create new capabilities or offer innovative outcomes. The significant influence of lack of capability creation on the development of organizational capabilities is in line with the findings of this research (Saragih et al., 2020; Rampa and Agogue, 2021; Pufal and Zawislak et al., 2021; Matarazzo et al., 2021) who suggested lack of ability capability creation affect organizational fitness, competitiveness, performance and ability to introduce new innovative outcomes. In their study, Guo et al. (2022) examined Chinese companies' ability to introduce innovative processes, products, and services through the adoption of generative capabilities models. Based on the research of Guo et al. (2022) organizations can achieve higher performance and competitive advantage through the introduction of innovative solutions and re-innovating processes and strategies. In addition, the research results illustrated the role of knowledge acquisition, inheritance, and integration in the organizational capability building process to achieve the required outcome.

The significance of the effect of the capability refinement approach is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that relying on the capability refinement approach alone affects the ability of an organization to renew its capabilities and its limited ability to cope with industry dynamics.

6.2.6.3 Co-Evolutionary Capability Building Process

The lack of a co-evolutionary capability building process was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese university's ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (38 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities do not adopt a specific capability building process by which new variations are acquired, retained, and generated continuously. The participants considered that the lack of a selection-retention-variation process limits Lebanese universities' ability to renovate their processes, capabilities and outcome.

The lack of adoption of a co-evolutionary capability building process inside an organization influence on the continual development and innovation of organizational capabilities was noted by several scholars (Kompella et al., 2020; Rong et al., 2021; Abatecola et al., 2020; Cristofaro, 2022).

Kompella et al. (2020) considered that co-evolutionary capability process refers to organizational routines to select the suitable resources, processes, and organizational units from their external environment and integrate them with organizational processes to develop or generate a new or varied outcome. Abatecola et al. (2020) believed that a co-evolutionary capability process is a valuable method and source of development, change, and organizational co-evolution with their environment. The selection-retention-variation capability processes help organizations develop their capabilities and respond better to external influencing factors, enhancing organizational outcomes and co-evolution with their environment (Rong et al., 2021; Cristofaro, 2022).

The significance of adopting a co-evolutionary capability building process for the development and renewal of organizational capabilities and competitiveness is in line with the findings of several resaeches (Parisot et al., 2019; Menglong et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Biazzin et al., 2022) which suggested that continued adoption of a co-evolutionary capability

building process can help organizations achieve a sustainable competitive advantage, fitness and ability to co-evolve with their environment. Kompella (2020) investigated the capability building processes of several public organizations to re-innovate their processes in response to external influencing factors in comparison to a co-evolutionary mechanism. Kompella (2020) found no continuous development of organizational capabilities among several public organizations. Kompella (2020) concluded that the adopted approach in these organizations depends on examining the direct internal and contingent factors relevant to innovative processes and outcomes, disregarding comprehensive approaches that examines essential and additional internal and external factors. Kompella (2020) concluded that the inconsistency of using and developing capability building processes and focusing on narrow factors limits organizations' ability to develop their capabilities, achieve innovation, and co-evolve with their environment.

The significance of adopting a co-evolutionary capability building process is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that organizational capabilities can be developed using purposeful selection, retention, and generation of new capabilities. The next section discusses the main factors that affect Lebanese universities' outcomes.

6.2.7 Organizational Outcome

The sixth theme in this research relates to the factors that affect organization's outcome. Identifying factors that affect an organization's ability to offer varied outcomes is considered an essential component of any co-evolutionary approach. Organizational outcomes can affect an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment. Lebanese universities' outcomes had a significant role in shaping Lebanese universities' ability to provide varied and differential programs and services and co-evolve with their environment. The two sub-themes that were considered the main

influencing factors by the participants were the lack of new outcomes and the lack of new organizational forms.

6.2.7.1 Lack of New Organizational Outcome

The lack of new outcomes was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (34 out of 39) believed that the outcomes offered by Lebanese universities limit their ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants argued that Lebanese universities' offerings lack differential or unique outcomes in the market. The effect of the inability of an organization to offer new or varied outcomes on organizational competitiveness was noted by several scholars (ElMaraghy et al., 2021; Hermundsdottir and Aspelund, 2021; Moller et al., 2022; McIntyre et al., 2022).

Moller et al. (2022) argued that organizations' ability to develop digital services or integrate digital capabilities with their existing products and services determines their competitiveness. Hermundsdottir and Aspelund (2021) considered that the new digital environment requires new organizational outcomes, processes, and the utilization of new technologies.

The significant influence of the lack of new organizational outcomes on the ability of an organization to compete in its environment is in line with the findings of several research (Li et al., 2019; Bottcher and Weking., 2020; Soto Setzke et al., 2021; Pesch et al., 2021) that emphasized the importance of continual development and re-innovation of organizational outcomes to maintain sustainability and stay relevant to what is required within its landscape. Soto Setzke et al. (2021) investigated the integration of new digital transformation strategies and their impact on several international organizations' processes and outcomes. Soto Setzke et al. (2021) found that integrating new digital transformation approaches leads to the development of organizational capabilities, processes, and the ability to re-innovate and provide new digital services. Soto Setzke

et al. (2021) found that new digital services improve competition and organizational performance in a competitive landscape.

The significance of organizational outcomes is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that an organization's ability to offer new products or services with unique characteristics enhances its ability to compete and co-evolve in a competitive environment.

6.2.7.2 Lack of New Organizational Forms

The lack of new organizational forms was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (35 out of 39) considered that the outcome of Lebanese universities lacks new organizational forms. Participants considered that the outcome of Lebanese universities is offered using traditional methods and processes that need to be re-innovated to cope with changing environmental conditions. In addition, participants argued that Lebanese universities' offerings lack digital forms and services.

The effect of the lack of new organizational forms on the organizational outcome was noted by several scholars (Lanzolla et al., 2020; Dentoni et al., 2020; McIntyre et al., 2020; Volberda et al., 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021) who emphasized on the importance of re-innovating and re-creating new organizational forms. Konopik et al. (2021) argued that digital technologies and advanced telecommunication tools help organizations reconfigure their operations and generate new organizational forms in several landscapes. McIntyre et al. (2020) believed that the interdependence of multiple environments offered new mediums for organizations to operate and expand their presence. It is essential to take advantage of the new environmental norm and reconfigure organizational operations to enter new landscapes and with new forms or benefit from

the multiple medium traits to develop a new organizational form for the whole organization with new characteristics and abilities (McIntyre et al. 2020; Dentoni et al., 2020).

The significant influence of the lack of new organizational forms is in line with the findings of several research (Aldrich and Wiedenmayer, 2019; Yu et al., 2021; Saarikko et al., 2021; AlNuaimi et al., 2022) which suggested that the generation of new organizational forms enables organizations to achieve fitness, ability to compete and offer new and varied outcomes in several organizational environments. Yu et al. (2021) investigated the impact of digital technology integration on Chinese companies' ability to generate new organizational forms and improve their performance. Yu et al. (2021) found that organizational digital transformation can enable Chinese companies to develop their capabilities processes, improve its search behavior, and innovative outcomes, improving their resilience in the Chinese market.

The significance of generating new organizational forms is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that the lack of offering new organizational forms affects an organization's sustainability, fitness, and competitiveness.

Having discussed the main six sets of factors that affect Lebanese universities' co-evolution, the following section discusses additional influencing mediating factors.

6.2.8 Mediating Factors

The seventh set of factors in this research relates to mediating factors that were considered by the research participants as important factors that can affect the co-evolution of Lebanese universities. Several sub-themes emerged as important factors that affect Lebanese universities' co-evolutionary process. The sub-themes are local and global integration, management guidance and support, internal integration of co-evolutionary mechanisms, organizational means for interaction, altered

ecological conditions, competitive industry dynamics, and path dependence. In addition to these factors, participants of this research provided their view of the influence of the location of their universities, the historical development of the universities' capabilities, and the relevant environment on which the decisions to develop universities' capabilities are based.

6.2.8.1 Universities' Location

The location of Lebanese universities was considered a main factor that affected universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (33 out of 39) considered that the location of Lebanese universities affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve. Participants argued that location is important for the establishment phase and the survival and growth of Lebanese universities in the future. The effect of organizational location was noted by several scholars (Pradeep and Chanka, 2019; Obiekwe and Nwaeke, 2019; Dzwigol et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021) who suggested that the location and origin of organizations had a significant effect on the facilitation and support offered by the country and their brand image in the past; however, in the presence of globalization and the openness of markets, the role of country location is decreasing. In addition, the effect of organizations' location on organizations' fitness is in line with the findings of several research (Kostova et al., 2020; Svensson, and Karlsson, 2021; Donbesuur, 2020; Kretschmer et al., 2022) which suggested that an organization's location is essential to specific industries since location can provide more facilities and openness to international markets. The significance of having a suitable location for operation is considered a new emerging factor not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). Organizational location was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.2 Universities' Historical Development

The identification of an organization's historical development provides a better understanding of its previous developments and actions taken toward its development or achieving co-evolution with its environment. Among the participants in this research, 34 out of 39 considered that Lebanese universities have recently undergone incremental development in terms of their programs, methods, tools, and services, but haven't co-evolved with their environment. In addition, participants argued that Lebanese universities are focused on Lebanese landscape and less on their external environment. The effect of incremental development on organizational capabilities and outcomes was noted by several scholars (Alves et al., 2018; Li ad Huang, 2019; Ertosun, 2020; Ezquerro et al., 2022) who suggested that organizations should be able to identify their recent developments in terms of incremental or radical development, to comprehend their past and future progress better. The significant influence of incremental development is in line with the findings of several research (Jackson, 2019; Patora-Wysocka, 2019; Osorio Tinoco et al., 2020; Gui et al., 2022) which suggested that incremental development decreases the ability of an organization to sustain its competitive advantage, fitness, and growth. Incremental historical development is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) which suggests that the reliance on incremental development alone limits the ability of organizations to develop their capabilities, compete, and co-evolve with their environment. Organizational historical development was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.3 Local Responsiveness

The development of Lebanese universities' capabilities primarily relevant to their local environment was considered a main factor that affected their ability to co-evolve with their

environment. Most participants (37 out of 39) believed that Lebanese universities' focus was limited to Lebanese higher education. Participants argued that Lebanese universities' capabilities development is based on the requirements and needs of their local environment, with the assurance that their processes and outcomes satisfy international higher education standards. The effect of local responsiveness on competitiveness was noted by several scholars (Li et al., 2019; Sklyar et al., 2019; Meyer et al., 2020; Ferraris et al., 2020) who suggested that organizations that lack an international integration strategy can limit the ability of an organization to its local environment. In addition, it was suggested that having both a local and global strategy can expand operations and ability to compete in different environments, and face the challenges of international competitors that enter the local environment of an organization (Li et al., 2019; Sklyar et al., 2019; Meyer et al., 2020; Ferraris et al., 2020). The significant influence of the lack of global and local integration strategy adoption is in line with the findings of several research (Banc and Messeghem, 2020; George and Schillebeeckx, 2020; Galvin et al., 2021; Birkinshaw, 2022) which suggested that developing organizations' capabilities is primary to in response to local environment on organizations' ability to compete internationally and limits their operations to local landscape. The lack of global and local integration strategy is aligned with the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) that suggests that local responsiveness should be acquainted with an international integration strategy to sustain organizational fitness and sustainable competitive advantage in local and international environments.

6.2.8.4 Local and Global Integration

The ability to integrate internal operations with local and international organizations was considered a main driver, which can enhance Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their

environment. The majority of the participants of this research (38 out of 39) considered that integration of Lebanese universities' operations and process locally and globally enhance universities co-evolution abilities. Participants stated that collaborations and joint activities, both locally and internationally, with other universities or organizations are essential for Lebanese universities' co-evolution with their environment. The effect of lack of local and global integration on organizational fitness, growth, and competitiveness was noted by several scholars (Ponte, 2019; Fischer et al., 2020; Kano et al., 2020; Shenkar et al., 2021) who suggested that collaboration, joint ventures, and alliances between different organizations provide new features and abilities for organizations, which can enhance their performance and acquire new capabilities both locally and internationally. The significant influence of the lack of local and global integration on organizational growth and competitiveness is in line with the findings of several research (Hofstetter et al., 2022; Woetzel et al., 2019; Herath et al., 2021; Meyer et al., 2021) which suggested that integrating organizational operations, processes, and outcomes with different organizations can increase organizational capabilities, develop existing capabilities and resources, and improve their outcome. The significance of integrating internal operations with other local and international organizations is considered a new factor that is not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). This research added local and global integration to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.5 Management Guidance and Support

Management guidance and support were considered main drivers that enhance Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Most participants of this research (37 out of 39) considered that Lebanese management role inside the university affects universities' co-

evolution process. Participants considered that management guidance and support are essential to adopting a co-evolutionary approach and implementing it by Lebanon's universities. Participants argued that without the proper guidance and support of a new approach by management, it would be difficult to use it and benefit from its outcome. Management guidance and support for the adoption of new approaches and strategies inside an organization were noted by several scholars (Allas and Schaninger, 2020; Steiss, 2019; Kools and George, 2020; Tsou and Chen, 2022) who emphasized the central role of management to support the adoption of a new strategy and lead the change process inside an organization. The significant influence of management guidance and support is in line with the findings of several research (Rodriguez et al., 2019; Zaidi et al., 2022; Ferreira and Santos, 2022; Fernandez-Vidal et al., 2022) which suggested that management role is considered a driving factor for implementing new approaches, methods, and strategies inside organizations. The significance of management guidance and support is considered a new factor not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). Management guidance and support were added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.6 Internal Integration

The integration of new approaches with internal organizational processes and tasks was considered a main driver, which enhanced Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Most participants of this research (35 out of 39) considered that integrating a co-evolutionary approach with Lebanese universities' processes and tasks is essential for enhancing universities' co-evolution ability within their landscape. Participants argued that co-evolutionary approach should be integrated with the main processes and operations of Lebanese universities in order for

a co-evolutionary approach, dynamic and process to be appropriately implemented. The importance of integrating new approaches with internal organizational processes and activities was noted by several scholars (Farida and Setiawan, 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Oh et al., 2022; Bulturbayevich, M.B. and Abduvafojevna, 2022) who suggested that to implement a new approach inside an organization and to benefit fully from its value, organizational members should be trained to use it and be integrated with several organizational processes. The significant influence of proper implementation and integration of new approaches inside an organization is in line with the findings of this research (Adamides and Karacapilidis, 2020; Khraiwesh et al., 2020; Srimarut and Mekhum, 2020; Cuevas-Vargas et al, 2022) which suggested that management is responsible for providing guidance and proper implementation and integration of new approaches inside an organization. Integrating the co-evolutionary approach with internal organizational processes and tasks is considered a new factor not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). The integration of co-evolutionary approach with the internal organizational processes and activities was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.7 Lack of Means for Interaction

The lack of means for interaction with other environmental actors was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Most of the participants of this research (33 out of 39) considered that Lebanese universities lack suitable interactive tools and means to interact with their environment. Participants considered that Lebanese universities need well-developed interactive tools to interact with other environmental actors locally and globally. The effect of lack of means or tools of interaction on organizational

fitness and adaptability was noted by several scholars (Alexander et al., 2020; Rodriguez and Boyer, 2020; Froehlich, 2021; Wiseman, 2021) who suggested that organizations are required to develop or acquire new tools to be able to continually engage with their customers locally or across the globe and collaborate with other organizations from different industries. The significant influence of the lack of organizational means or tools for interaction is in line with the findings of several research (Morrison-Smith and Ruiz, 2020; Shipilov and Gawer, 2020; Yun et al., 2020; Mathrani and Edwards, 2020) which suggested that virtual platforms, software and applications are facilitating collaboration and engagement with customers and organizations, which lead to a more customized outcome and enhanced organizational processes.

The significance of the lack of organizational means or tools for interaction is considered a new factor that is not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). Means of interaction were added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.8 Environmental Factors

The influence of environmental factors was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. All the participants of this research (39 out of 39) agreed that environmental factors can significantly impact the operation and outcome of Lebanese universities. The participants considered that environmental factors constrained Lebanese universities' ability to function normally and affected their development. Participants believed that COVID-19 had a significant impact on Lebanese higher education industry and the universities' ability to operate normally. The effect of altered ecological factors on organizational operations and outcomes was noted by several scholars (Quilter-Pinner and Ambrose; Su et al.,

2020; Hamsal and Ichsan, 2022; Begum et al., 2022) who suggested that ecological factors can affect organizational operations, performance, development, and outcomes. The significant influence of altered ecological factors is in line with the findings of several research (Marqueset al., 2022; Hermundsdottir et al., 2022; Zulkifli, 2022; Crawford and Cifuentes-Faura, 2022) which suggested that ecological factors should be considered in organizational forecasts, contingency plans and strategies. The significance of altered ecological condition is considered a new factor that is not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach. Altered environmental factors was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.9 Industry Competitive Dynamics

The influence of industry competitive dynamics was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of the participants of this research (36 out of 39) suggested that industry's competitive dynamics have a significant impact on Lebanese universities' co-evolution ability within their landscape. Participants considered that rivals' competitive behavior shapes how universities operate and respond to industry competitive rules. The effect of industry competitive dynamics on shaping the competitive rules of organizational environment was noted by several scholars (Ducarme et al., 2019; Galvin et al., 2020; Knudsen et al., 2021; Brandenburger and Nalebuff, 2021) who suggested that industry competitive dynamics can determine the abilities, response, and outcome of competing organizations inside an environment. The significant influence of industry competitive dynamics is in line with the findings of several research (Chen et al., 2021; Travassos Rosario et al., 2021; Sund and Lindscov, 2022; Olasehinde et al., 2022; Avila, 2022) which suggested that competitive

dynamics can have a negative effect on organizations by shaping their capabilities and response. Industry competitive dynamics is considered a new external factor not mentioned in the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). This research added industry competitive dynamics was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.2.8.10 Path Dependence

Path dependence was considered a main factor that affected Lebanese university's ability to co-evolve with their environment. The majority of participants in this research (35 out of 39) considered that path dependence is an important factor that limits Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Participants argued that the approaches adopted over time had limited Lebanese universities' ability to make necessary changes to new environmental conditions in Lebanon. The effect of path dependence on the ability of an organization to make necessary changes as a response to external environmental factors was noted by several scholars (Sydow et al., 2019; Sedgwick and Jensen., 2020; Simeonov, 2020; Allen and Donaldson, 2022) who suggested that the adopted methods, techniques, norms, and strategies determine the ability of an organization to make necessary changes or ability to re-innovate its capabilities in the future and particular events. The significant role of path dependence in shaping organizational fitness and competitiveness is in line with the findings of several research (Silvestre and Țirca, 2019; Samuelsson et al., 2020; Suddaby et al., 2020; Ghosh et al., 2022) which suggested that organizational path dependence should be regularly and strategically examined, so that the value of adopted approaches, do not result in inertia or weakness in different conditions and circumstances. The significance of path dependence is considered a new factor not mentioned in

the literature review regarding co-evolutionary approach (Chapters 2 and 3). Path dependence was added to the factors investigated in the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework in this research.

6.3 Validation of the Co-Evolutionary Framework

In this section, the researcher sought to validate the results of empirical research into the Co-Evolutionary Framework developed in Chapter 3. The researcher thoroughly analyzed the gaps and examined key elements of the new framework. This section presents a revised theoretical Co-Evolutionary Framework based on academic research findings and empirical evidence. The present research aims to study the theoretical assumptions drawn from the literature through empirical research and validation of the Co-Evolutionary Framework.

The Co-Evolutionary Framework in Chapter 3, Figure 3-1, is based on key academic research findings. The primary purpose of the Co-Evolutionary Framework is to identify the existing literature gap, confirming the need for a strategic framework to investigate the relationship between universities and their environment. Therefore, the researcher first identified the key factors that shape an organization's ability to co-evolve with its environment (Chapters 2 and 3) then validated their impact and importance through empirical research (Chapters 5).

In the literature, Co-Evolutionary Frameworks were developed mainly around an organization's internal and external environment, by which internal and external factors were mainly integrated to investigate the co-evolution of an organization. Afterward, management was added to have a more in-depth investigation of the main influencing factors that affect the co-evolution of organizations. In the present research, the researcher considered management an essential component when investigating the co-evolution of an organization and integrating it into the Co-Evolutionary Framework. The study of managerial role and capabilities provides more

comprehensive understanding of the co-evolution process of higher education institutions and identify the main factors limiting their ability to co-evolve. Capability building processes, competitive factors, and organizational outcomes were added to the developed Co-Evolutionary Framework of this research. Adding additional components allows the identification of several new factors and an extensive understanding of the relationship between universities and their environments, especially as these components are mentioned in literature as an essential component of organizational co-evolutionary process. After explaining the main theoretical foundations of the Co-Evolutionary Framework, the researcher validated the key factors influencing Lebanese universities' co-evolution. Figure 6-1 presents the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework, which illustrates some of the main empirical findings that impacted the assessment of the previous version of the Co-Evolutionary Framework (Figure 3-8).

Figure 6-1 Revised Co-Evolutionary Framework

Source: The Researcher

The revised Co-Evolutionary Framework provides a comprehensive understanding of the key factors that influence Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. As presented in Figure 6-1, the Co-Evolutionary Framework assumes that the co-evolution of higher education institutions is influenced by five sets of influencing factors related to external factors, internal factors, management capabilities, capability building process, and organizational outcome.

Firstly, technological factors, communication infrastructure, new competitors, social factors, competitive industry dynamics, and ecological factors were considered the main external factors affecting Lebanese universities. The empirical findings confirm the importance of technological factors, communication infrastructure, new competitors, and ecological and social factors in the co-evolutionary process. The researcher has adopted these factors in the original frame and added industrial competitive dynamics factors to the external set of influencing factors into the Co-Evolutionary Framework. Moreover, global university ranking, rising costs, low number of international students, location of the university and its city development, suppliers, regulators, and government funding were considered by the current research participants as additional external factors that can affect Lebanese universities' co-evolutionary processes.

Secondly, it has been revealed by the empirical finding that organizational resources, including organizational, physical, financial, informational, and technological resources, structure, path dependence, and processes, were considered the main internal factors affecting Lebanese universities. The empirical findings confirm the effect of organizational resources, structure, path dependence and internal processes on the internal organizational environment, which the researcher adopted in the Co-Evolutionary Framework. In several co-evolutionary studies, organizational resources were considered the main influencing internal factors without any

classification of the types of influencing resources. The developed Co-Evolutionary Framework classifies organizational resources, into physical, financial, information, and knowledge resources when examining the effect of organizational resources on organizational co-evolution. Furthermore, brand image, research department, IT department, organizational grammar, organizational culture, and organizational stakeholders were considered additional factors that could affect Lebanese universities' co-evolutionary processes.

Thirdly, it has been revealed by the empirical finding that the management role is affected by strategic intentionality, bounded rationality, explorative search, absorptive capacity and limited administrative role, management support, and guidance for adopting a new approach and integrating it inside an organization. The empirical findings are aligned with the adopted factors in the Co-Evolutionary Framework, including strategic intentionality, bounded rationality, explorative search, absorptive capacity, and limited administrative role. However, management support and guidance for integrating new approaches with organizational processes have been added to the Co-Evolutionary Framework to better examine management's role and capabilities.

Fourthly, the fourth set of influencing factors relates to the capability building process, which suggests that co-evolutionary capability building process integration, capability refinement, and lack of dynamic capabilities impact organizational capability building process. The empirical findings revealed in the present research are aligned with the capability building influencing factors adopted by the researchers in the Co-Evolutionary Framework. Moreover, participants considered that lack of adequate training, lack of process innovation management, lack of knowledge assets, and the ability to integrate blockchain technology could affect Lebanese universities' ability to develop their capabilities and co-evolve with their environment.

Fifthly, the fifth set of influencing factors relates to factors that affect organizational competitive abilities. The dependence on a resource-based view is aligned with the adopted competitive factors in the Co-Evolutionary Framework, which suggests that dependence on a resource-based view alone limits organizational abilities and focuses more on tangible resources than essential resources, like knowledge and organizational learning from a knowledge-based perspective. Moreover, research participants considered that the marketing campaigns of Lebanese universities affected their ability to compete in their environment.

Finally, the sixth set of influencing factors relates to organizational outcome. The identified influencing factors in the empirical findings align with the adopted factors in the Co-Evolutionary Framework, which suggests that the lack of varied organizational outcomes and new organizational forms affect universities' ability to provide new outcomes in their environment. In addition to the two main factors, the ability to offer a new capability or a process as an organizational outcome, provide academic contributions publications, job-related certificates, the initiation of university technology transfer programs, the ability to offer dual degrees, integrate augmented learning methods, and the adoption of a mini campus strategy, were considered to affect Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment.

Additionally, the lack of local and global integration and the need to develop means for interaction were considered important factors influencing the interaction between Lebanese universities and their environment by the participants in this research. The new set of factors suggested additional factors, methods, and tools that can be used as a midpoint that links management with their external and internal organizational environments. Integration of new interactive tools inside an organization can be considered an extension of managerial practices

that can be used to interact between the internal and external environment and can be combined to develop new organizational forms or provide new varied organizational outcomes.

Moreover, local and global responsiveness, universities' location, and historical development factors, were considered additional factors that can give additional information and view about the effect of the influence of organizational location, its local and global strategy, and whether it has co-evolved over time within its landscape.

The research findings mentioned above reveal the alignment of the factors integrated into the Co-Evolutionary Framework and the importance of the added factors, which are industry competitive dynamics, global and local integration, means for interactions, management support and guidance, capability building process integration, expanded the studied internal and external factors and provided a better understanding of the organization-environment relationship. In the revised Co-Evolutionary Framework, economic, political, and legal factors were removed from the main set of external influencing factors in the Co-Evolutionary Framework. Organizational value systems, mission and objectives, plans and policies, and organizational image factors were removed from the main set of internal influencing factors. The dependence only on a knowledge-based view was removed from the set of factors that affect organizational competitiveness.

The revised Co-Evolutionary Framework, similar to the original framework, considers management a linking factor or a midpoint between an organization's internal and external environments; however, in the revised framework, management is linked to two additional environments: regional and global organizational environments. In addition, due to the importance of organizational virtual presence, a fourth environment was added to illustrate the interdependent relationship between several environments. A third pillar was added to the previous two pillars (external and internal environments) in the original framework to include a

new set of interaction factors that management can use to interact between the internal and external environments. Additional triads were constructed to show the link between management, the internal-external environment, and organizational interactive tools within several environments. The upward triad demonstrates managerial ability to link several factors and manage the relationship between organizations' internal and external factors. The downward triad, presents the reflection of the upward triad, that include management, internal and external environment, and interaction tools, shows the link between several factors inside and outside an organization and management to generate organizational outcomes of new or developed variant products and services or new organizational forms.

Although several key external and internal influencing factors can affect an organization's abilities and capabilities, the role of management is essential and linked to almost every factor, as its response and action can impact the organization's capabilities and future outcome. Thus, it is essential to shed light on management role in co-evolutionary process and its adoption inside organizations where managerial guidance and support are required.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter has covered the findings related to the identified themes in the present research. Results indicate a causal relationship between Lebanese universities and their environments. This research reveals the main internal and external factors affecting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment, focusing on causal relationship between Lebanese universities and their environments, managerial roles and capabilities, capability building process, competitiveness, and organizational outcome factors. In addition, the chapter includes validation of the Co-Evolutionary Framework and provides a revised version of the framework. The

following chapter concludes the present research by presenting its results, contributions and offering suggestions for further research.

Chapter Seven: Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

The current chapter presents research contributions and illustrates that the research objectives and research questions are answered. This chapter concludes by presenting research findings and contribution to policy, practice, knowledge and offer suggestions for future research. The researcher reviews the research aim, objectives, and research questions in this chapter (Section 7.2). This chapter also includes research limitations (Section 7.3), contributions to knowledge (Section 7.4), contributions to practice (Section 7.5), and contributions to policy (Section 7.6) and concludes by providing recommendations for future research (Section 7.7).

7.2 Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions

The current section reviews the main research aim, objectives, and questions to illustrate their achievement. The primary aim of the present research is to investigate the challenges affecting Lebanese universities to co-evolve in a competitive environment.

The main aim of the research has been achieved. The reviewed literature in Chapters 2 and 3 presents various contributions that provide several key elements in higher education. Thus, an opportunity has been provided to discuss published research on co-evolutionary approaches and offer a theoretical and empirical basis for Co-Evolutionary Framework development in Chapter 3. The development of the Co-Evolutionary Framework (Figure 3-8) is based on a gap in the literature that reflects an understanding of various organizational topics and development motives that directly impact its development, adoption, and implementation.

The researcher set five research objectives:

1. To review and evaluate the literature related to the relationship between universities and their environment to identify gaps in the literature.
2. To explore the role of Lebanese universities' management in dealing with changing environmental conditions.
3. To develop a new Co-Evolutionary Framework that addresses the relationship between universities and their environments.
4. To explore the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' involvement in their environment.
5. To address the implications of applying co-evolutionary theory in higher education.

In this research, the researcher thoroughly reviewed key research findings, theories, and contributions in Chapters 2 and 3. Various organizational theories, co-evolutionary theories, and frameworks were analyzed to identify relevant components to help the researcher develop a new Co-Evolutionary Framework.

The theoretical Co-Evolutionary Framework (Figure 3-2) was developed at the theoretical stage of the research. The Co-Evolutionary Framework was developed through empirical research to investigate the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment, as described in Chapter 5.

The developed Co-Evolutionary Framework has been transformed into a strategic management approach that can be used in higher education. The present research's main aim and objectives were achieved by answering the research questions.

The first research question addresses the literature review of the relationship between organizations and their environments, notably higher education institutions.

1. What is the relationship between universities and their environment?

To answer this question, which relates to the development of organizational theories over the last six decades, the researcher reviewed various academic research and contributions regarding the historical development of organizations' analysis and study of their relationship with their environment, as mentioned in Chapter 3 (Section 3.2). The researcher identified a fundamental change in the factors that have been considered when investigating organizations over the last six decades. Organizational theories evolved from closed systems to open systems, by which an organization's nature cannot be investigated without researching the environment in which they operate and not just focusing on internal factors alone (Saukkone and Kirjavaine, 2019; Volkmann et al., 2019; Spies and Alff, 2019). Chapter 3 presents significant factors that drove researchers to focus on organizations' internal and external environments. The theoretical review analyzes the factors investigated by past and modern theories and theoretical and conceptual frameworks that investigate the relationship between organizations and their environments, as presented in Chapter 3 (Sections 3.2 and 3.3).

The existing literature on the co-evolution of organizational theories suggests that researching internal and external factors has become essential for any organization to operate, survive, and compete in its environment (Volkmann et al., 2019; Spies and Alff, 2019). The researcher agrees that a new construct of the relationship between organizations and their environmental factors should be developed, as external environmental influences are increasing, and organizations need a better response (Manyika and Tuin, 2020; Finn et al., 2020; Minnaar, 2020; Scoblic, 2020; Mosca, 2020). In addition, literature analysis shows that most theories embrace organizations'

adaptive responses to external environmental factors (Manyika and Tuin, 2020; Finn et al., 2020; Minnaar, 2020; Scoblic, 2020; Mosca, 2020).

Higher education institutions were considered classical systems, closed, and focused solely on their local environments competitiveness (Zalite and Zvirbule, 2020; Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020). The literature shows that higher education institutions' primary response was limited to the incremental development of their internal institutional factors (Recio and Colella, 2020; Jandric et al., 2020; Bergan et al., 2020). However, with the opening of markets, the integration of new technologies, and the rise of new educational forms, the higher education environment was disrupted, and new conditions were set (Vykydal et al., 2020; Geng and Zhao, 2020). The new environmental conditions have exerted external pressures on higher education institutions and influenced their fitness ability, survival, and competitiveness within their landscape (Recio and Colella, 2020; Jandric et al., 2020; Bergan et al., 2020). As a result, the need for an adequate external and internal response has increased for higher education institutions to overcome these challenges (Chankseliani et al., 2020; Fumasoli, 2021). Several higher education institutions were able to overcome these challenges; however, others could not face the new challenges (Chankseliani et al., 2020; Fumasoli, 2021).

The existing literature lacks comprehensive research investigating how higher education institutions face new environmental settings, their interactions with their environment, and make necessary changes to face emerging challenges. The lack of research in higher education has limited the number of studies that could provide new approaches and alternative responses that universities can adopt to tackle environmental challenges and enhance their ability to construct a better view and understanding of their environment. In addition, the lack of research in higher

education has limited universities leaders' ability to identify the main factors that bound their relationship with their environment and ability to respond to external influences.

The qualitative analysis of empirical data reveals that most participants observed increasing external influences on Lebanese universities and increased interest in making suitable internal changes to face the new challenges facing Lebanese higher education landscape. The research outcome corroborates the theoretical and empirical discussions of the academic contributions presented in the literature review (Chapters 2 and 3). In this research, the qualitative interview results reveal that several internal and external factors limit Lebanese universities' ability to better interact, respond to environmental challenges, and co-evolve with their environment.

The second research question addresses the managerial role in managing the relationship between universities and their environment.

2. What is the role of management in managing the relationship between universities and their environment?

Management is considered the primary and common component of any organization, as it was considered the fundamental component in most organizational theories and one of the initial factors upon which the first organizational theory set its foundations (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021; Kaipainen, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020). After reviewing the literature, it has been revealed that as organizational theory evolved, management's significance has decreased, as the focus has deviated to newly added factors as primary factors. In contrast, management was considered part of organizational factors, whose existence is definite. The shift in organizational theory occurred when additional factors were introduced into the research

process, especially external factors, as evidenced by modern and postmodern theories of organization. In addition, attention to management has decreased because management research has become an independent field of study.

In several organizations, management role has ceased to function as a form of governance, limiting its function to monitoring, controlling, and working with different organizational units (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021; Kaipainen, 2020; Fuertes et al., 2020). Management's primary focus is on the organization's internal environment. However, as mentioned before, the increasing external environment exerted new pressures on organizations and required new responses (Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). For that, new theories were developed regarding management's role in administering the relationship between organizations and their environments. However, these theories and approaches were limited by focusing primarily on one side, whether internally or externally. The focus on limited organizational factors shaped management's response, characterized by a limited adaptation. As a result of the new environment, the old management approach was replaced by more proactive and strategic responses from organizations; however, many organizations adopted an adaptive management approach. Lately, new theories have emerged, expanding their role in the context of the external and internal environment of the organization and giving management a leading role in managing the interaction of both environments.

As discussed, higher education institutions were considered closed systems in the past when markets were not open worldwide (Zalite and Zvirbule, 2020; Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020). Management's role was administrative, focusing on organizational factors and less on the external environment. As part of the global environment, universities face new challenges and limitations

like any organization. Management role was considered adaptive, shaped by environmental conditions (Shatilo, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022). In literature, many international universities have adopted the same approach; however, different approaches can provide better value and results, available for universities' management to adopt (Garcia-Morales et al., 2020; Mitchell et al., 2020; Williamson, 2021). While international universities adopt the same approach, other universities have developed new approaches (Garcia-Morales et al., 2020; Mitchell et al., 2020; Williamson, 2021). Several international universities were able not just to have suitable responses to environmental changes but also to have a role in the external environment and, in many cases, influence their external environment and shape its setting (Garcia-Morales et al., 2020; Mitchell et al., 2020; Williamson, 2021). Co-evolutionary approach greatly emphasizes management and its role in managing the relationship between organizations and their environment and leading change through competitive selection rather than natural selection (Shatilo, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022). Management is an essential component that should be studied to analyze and evaluate organizations' management elements.

Chapter 5 shows the significant role of management at Lebanese universities in the internal and external contexts. Management is considered the source and link of the main functions of universities, in which management assesses the environment, manages the capability building process, and makes decisions regarding the university's operations. The findings also show that management is essential in guiding and supporting the application of new approaches at universities. However, the findings also show that the role of Lebanese management is adaptive, which needs to be replaced by a new approach that expands management roles and improves universities' management capabilities.

The reviewed literature in Chapters 2 and 3 focuses on organizational theories, which investigate the nature of organizations and their relationship with their environment. Previous research that studied the relationship between organizations and their relationship lacked an empirical perspective of developing a co-evolutionary approach that investigates the relationship between universities and their environment and identifies the main factors that limit their ability to co-evolve with their environment.

The third research question intends to identify the main factors critical to developing a Co-Evolutionary Framework.

3. What are the key organizational factors to develop a Co-Evolutionary Framework?

After evaluating the relevant literature contributions and identifying knowledge gaps, the researcher identified the critical determinants to develop a Co-Evolutionary Framework to investigate the co-evolution of Lebanese universities with their environment. These factors were categorized into six main categories: external environment factors, internal environment factors, management role and capabilities, capability building process competition, and organizational outcome.

As discussed in Section 3.5, each Co-Evolutionary Framework theme includes sub-factors that offer deeper investigation and better results. External environment factors include external environmental factors. The internal environment includes organizational factors. Management factors that influence managerial role and capabilities within and an organization. The outcome includes the variation of outcomes or forms offered by an organization. In addition, since the research is investigating organizational co-evolution in a competitive environment, environmental

competitive factors were added. Additional research questions were asked about specific necessary factors by other researchers with past work in organizational co-evolution. The researcher concludes that while several academic researchers investigated organizational co-evolution, researchers have considered some of the mentioned factors; however, there is a lack of an extensive review or adequate evaluation of these factors in the literature (Sarta et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Donbesuur et al., 2020; Brown et al., 2020; Mellor et al., 2020; Altinay et al., 2020). Based on these factors, a Co-Evolutionary Framework was developed.

The following question deals with the main factors that limit Lebanese universities' co-evolution with their environment.

4. What are the main factors limiting Lebanese universities' involvement in their environment?

Qualitative data reveal that several internal and external factors influence Lebanese universities' co-evolution. The results show that the external environment of Lebanese universities is affected by the rise of new technologies, the lack of advanced communication infrastructure, the rise of new competitors, and the emergence of new social norms regarding education worldwide. On the other side, internally, the organizational environment of Lebanese universities is mainly affected by pre-owned resources which the participants emphasized the influence of the lack or shortage of technological and informational resources, the need for additional physical resources, and better financial resources to operate and perform adequately and for future development and advancement. Participants of this research considered that the organizational structure of Lebanese universities and their daily operations influence the co-evolution of Lebanese universities. The participants considered that management role is limited at Lebanese universities, focused on the

administration of the internal environment, and reactive toward the external environment. In addition, participants considered that Lebanese university management lacks strategic intentionality and, to a certain point, is bound to their rationality, which affects their managerial capabilities, search behavior, and sense-making of their environment. The data shows that Lebanese managers' search behavior is limited to explorative research behavior and that their environment is considered unanalyzable due to limited management capabilities and absorptive capacity. It was determined that the primary factors affecting the competitiveness of Lebanese universities were based on a resource-based approach, the lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) resources, the irreversibility of investments, and the lack of skilled human resources. The qualitative data shows that Lebanese universities' capability building process is affected by a lack of dynamic capability processes and limited capability proliferation. The participants reveal that continual development, in which there is a lack of continual capability building processes, aids Lebanese universities in coping with changing environmental conditions and renewing their capabilities. The outcome of Lebanese universities is affected by the lack of new outcomes and new organizational forms.

Furthermore, participants in this study provided additional factors that can be considered to provide a better understanding of the factors that affect Lebanese universities. The participants emphasized the significance of management role in guiding and supporting the adoption of a co-evolutionary approach inside Lebanese universities. In addition, participants argued that the co-evolutionary approach should be integrated with the universities' practices, operations, and operations and focused on the essentiality of having proper capability-building processes that ensure the renovation and acquisition of new capabilities. The participants considered that there is a lack of local and global integration of their processes and facilities with other organizations and

a lack of means for interaction with other environmental actors within their environment or worldwide. The participants also considered that environmental factors were necessary when considering organizational co-evolution, emphasizing the effect of COVID-19 on Lebanese universities' operation and development process. Industry competitive dynamics, path dependence, and local focus have limited their ability, and operations and development were limited to the local environment and open internationally. The participants also suggested that management is essential to the co-evolution of Lebanon's universities. It was agreed by the participants that the management of Lebanese universities was crucial to adopting and applying a co-evolutionary approach and that they should be provided with guidance and support for change and development.

The fifth research question addresses the main factors for successfully implementing a co-evolutionary approach at Lebanese universities.

5. What are the critical factors for applying a Co-Evolutionary Framework at Lebanese universities?

Theoretically, there is a lack of practical implications for implementing a co-evolutionary approach inside an organization and higher education institutions. The application of co-evolutionary approaches is insufficiently explored. Existing literature relating to organizational co-evolution focuses on an organization's internal and external environment with an examination of other factors; however, there is a lack of research that investigates practical steps or critical factors to implement co-evolutionary approaches.

Qualitative data shows that management's role in guiding and supporting the adoption of co-evolutionary approaches is essential in applying the co-evolutionary approach inside Lebanese universities. In addition, participants considered that integrating co-evolutionary processes with universities' primary practices and operations and developing a proper capability building process is essential to implementing the co-evolutionary approach. Furthermore, the identified organizational factors can aid management in better adapting the Co-Evolutionary Framework by re-assessing each factor's value and effect, disregarding limiting factors, and retaining critical factors that aid the application of the co-evolutionary approach concerning universities' capabilities and resources.

7.3 Limitations of the Research

This research offers new insights and draws valuable results concerning organizational co-evolution; however, some limitations are worth considering for future research.

- The researcher has adopted a single research method to collect and interpret data. In this research qualitative case study has been used as a research strategy to help the researcher collect the required data to reach the research objectives (Tomaszewski et al., 2020; Dawadi, 2021).
- The emphasis on a specific sector and one country for the research limited the investigation to the higher education field in Lebanon (Snyder, 2019; Chung and Lippe, 2020; Erickson, 2020).
- The empirical investigation was limited to participants who worked at higher education institutions. The sample size was limited to thirty-nine participants at Lebanese universities, from twenty-six Lebanese universities (Aguinis and Solarino, 2019; Rigtering et al., 2019; Campbell et al., 2020). The participants were mainly Lebanese universities' managers and didn't include academics or students.

7.4 Contributions to Knowledge

The researcher presents key contributions to research knowledge in this section.

- Firstly, the research provided an in-depth review of various themes and principles of organizational co-evolution (Abatecola et al., 2020; Mihalache and Volberda 2021 et al., 2021; Menglong et al., 2020; Kligyte et al., 2021). A thorough review was supported by academic literature and the contributions of several researchers and scholars in the field, seeking to explain the development of organizational theories over the last six decades (Riasanow et al., 2019; Kompella, 2020; Abatecola et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Kligyte et al., 2021; Lundan and Cantwell, 2020; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021).
- Secondly, proposing a framework that investigates the external and internal environment for higher education institutions to understand better the relationship between institutions and their environments (Abatecola, 2020; Kompella, 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021). The framework investigates the internal and external factors that affect higher education institutions' ability to co-evolve with their environment and the role of management in managing and leading the co-evolutionary process (Abatecola, 2020; Parisot et al., 2020; Lundan and Cantwell, 2020; Chidlow, 2021). The framework shows the importance of considering several factors to achieve co-evolution, including external factors, internal factors, management roles, capability building processes, competitiveness, and outcome (Menglong et al., 2020; Schott et al., 2020; Menglong et al., 2020; Abatecola, 2020; Kompella, 2020; Chidlow, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda 2021).
- Thirdly, determining additional factors required to achieve organizational co-evolution, including local and global integration, means for interaction, environmental factors, industry

competitive dynamics, and re-evaluation of path dependence (De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Pinner et al., 2020; Momper et al., 2020; Lindscov et al., 2020; Chiegboka, 2020; Samuelsson et al., 2021). In addition, the results show how management guidance and support are important for implementing the co-evolutionary approach inside higher education institutions and integrating it with the institution's internal and external processes and capability building process (Allas and Schaninger, 2020; Kools and George, 2020; Miller, 2020; Wilde, 2021).

- Fourthly, to the researcher's knowledge, the present research is one of the few pieces of research investigating the relationship between universities and their environment and the factors limiting their ability to co-evolve with their environment.
- Fifthly, the research investigated Lebanese universities' organizational co-evolution. The sample selected for the interviews comprised thirty-nine Lebanese university managers who were considered valuable and rich data sources for the desired outcome of the present research (Tomaszewski et al., 2020; Dawadi, 2021). In this research, the researcher provides a better apprehension of Lebanese higher education landscape setting and highlights the main factors that limit Lebanese universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. The present research offers a better comprehension of the managerial role and its significance in implementing a co-evolutionary approach at Lebanese universities (Govindarajan and Srivastava, 2020; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; García-Morales et al., 2021; Young and Pinheiro, 2022; Klein 2022; Barbato et al., 2022).
- Sixthly, most empirical studies investigating organizational co-evolution adopted limited forms of quantitative studies that study specific aspects of the co-evolutionary process, overlooking the value of qualitative research's rich descriptive context (Tomaszewski et al., 2020; Dawadi, 2021). Adopting qualitative methods to collect and analyze data in this research

provided a new methodology to investigate organizational co-evolution (Dawadi, 2021; Taherdoost, 2022; Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

7.5 Contribution to Practice

The present research provides an alternative way for universities to manage their interaction with their environment and to identify the factors that limit the universities' ability to co-evolve with their environment. Contributions of this research will extend the view of how a university can achieve fitness, sustainability, and competitiveness through adopting a co-evolutionary framework. The research offers several practical contributions, which are:

- Portraying how to manage the relationship between the internal and external environment is a significant factor influencing or leveraging universities' fitness and ability to compete within their environment (Klein et al., 2022; Barbato et al., 2022; Young and Pinheiro, 2022). Empirical findings confirmed that the approach adopted by Lebanese universities had limited their interaction with their environment and environment and their response to environmental challenges. The findings help better understand the nature of Lebanese higher education environment and the existing mutual influence between Lebanese universities and their environment.
- Obtaining important insights into how Lebanese universities perceive and interact with their environment by identifying the main internal and external influencing factors of the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. Findings show that the main external influencing factors are technological, communication infrastructure, new competitors, and social factors (Matovic, 2020; Cox, 2020; Buye, 2021). The finding shows the main internal factors are organizational resources, which include financial, technological,

informational, and physical resources, organizational structure, and organizational internal and external processes (Bhasin, 2020, Surbhi, 2020, Vanessa, 2020).

- Identifying a gap in managing the relationship between Lebanese universities and their environment. It was found that within Lebanese universities, the nature of the interaction between Lebanese universities and their environment is adaptive due to the management capabilities of Lebanese universities. The finding of the empirical work identifies gaps in practice, demonstrating that managerial capabilities are influenced by the lack of strategic intentionality, bounded rationality, limited absorptive capacity, and limited search behavior (Gong and Diao, 2020; Tidd, 2021; Marin-Idarraga et al., 2020; Dagenais, 2022).
- Finding the main deterrents of the capability building process and competitiveness of Lebanese universities. The results show that higher education institutions lack a proper capability building process, and the dependence on capability proliferation determines Lebanese universities' ability to re-innovate or acquire new capabilities (Annarelli et al., 2020; Ferreira et al., 2020; Dzhengiz, 2020; Nguyen et al., 2021; Vargas et al., 2021). The results also show that adopting a resource-based view strategy, lack of valuable, rare imitable, and organizable resources (VRIO) resources, inability to reverse investments, and lack of skilled human resources affect the competitiveness of Lebanese universities (Davis and Dewitt, 2021; Grant and Phene, 2021; Waddill 2021; Piwowar-Sulej, 2021).
- Setting a benchmark for a new strategic direction for managing the relationship between organizations and their environment, emphasizing an understanding of emerging global challenges, and providing a co-evolutionary approach as an alternative solution for universities to face new environmental settings and challenges (Appio, 2021; Awan et al., 2021; Moss, 2020; Lundan and Cantwell, 2020; Qi et al., 2020; Da Costa and Horn, 2021; Chidlow, 2021;

Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). The framework leverages a reconsideration of traditional responses and perceptions of the organizational environment and enables organizations to investigate factors that shape their interactions with their environment to enhance their competitiveness and fitness in their environment (Qi et al., 2020; Da Costa and Horn, 2021; Chidlow, 2021; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021).

7.6 Policy Implications

The present research offers several implications for Lebanese policymakers, including:

- Continual re-evaluation the relationship between local universities in Lebanon, local universities, and other regional and international universities (Waghid et al., 2021; Do et al., 2021). Policymakers may propose or adjust future policies that encourage communication and collaboration between local universities on one side and local and international universities on the other side through new programs or processes that benefit the overall Lebanese higher education system locally and internationally (Waghid et al., 2021; Do et al., 2021).
- Continual assessment of the main external and internal influencing factors that are negatively or have a negative impact in the future on Lebanese higher education and institutions to offer better support, interventions, and adjustments to current strategies (Alam, 2022). As a result of several factors that may influence particular or several universities, new policies can be set to help other universities that are part of Lebanese higher education system to support the universities, which reflects on the whole higher education system and its constituents. (Alam, 2022)
- The development of a new national framework that can assess the main strengths, weaknesses, capability building, competition, and outcome to provide support and aid to a better university future design that allows Lebanese universities to face changing environmental conditions and

future trends and challenges (Nazari-Shirkouhi, 2020; Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020; Miao et al., 2021; Marks and Alali, 2022).

- Suggest flexible policies that are open to change and update, especially in the phase of altered environmental conditions, to overcome inertia and avoid the repercussions of path dependence (Chankseliani et al., 2021; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Hendriarto et al., 2021).
- Additional higher education research and development activities can be conducted for Lebanese universities, similar to the attention to Lebanese secondary and vocational educational institutions (Chankseliani et al., 2021; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Hendriarto et al., 2021; LHE-Policy 2023-2027).
- Offer training for Lebanese universities' managers, as part of the Ministry and development for better administration and ability to face environmental challenges and new ways to collaborate between universities and the Ministry of Higher Education to develop the country's higher education system (Izumi, 2021; Karakose, 2021; Antonopoulou et al., 2021; Nunez-Canal et al., 2022). The new Lebanese higher education policy (2023-2027) offers limited training for Lebanese universities' managers focused on crisis management training after the Covid-19 pandemic (LHE-Policy 2023-2027).
- Provide new policies prioritizing Lebanese universities' programs over external programs that can disrupt Lebanese higher education system, like online, distance learning, or new future educational forms that can be alternatives to Lebanese higher education institutions (Dozhnikov, 2020; Fernando, 2020; Gourlay et al., 2021; Kuleto et al., 2021; Akhmedov, 2022). Policymakers may initiate programs to replicate new educational institution forms, structures, processes, and outcomes to integrate new features and organizational forms into

Lebanese higher education system (Dozhdikov, 2020; Fernando, 2020; Gourlay et al., 2021; Kuleto et al., 2021; Akhmedov, 2022).

- Offer new tools and methods for universities to share knowledge and build database centers that Lebanese universities and policymakers can use for the development of the higher education system and universities connected to it, and not just for communication or contact tools (De Bem Machado et al., 2022; Quarchioni et al., 2022).
- Offer collaborative programs between Lebanese government, universities, and industrial firms inside and outside the country, which offer new forms of artificial intelligence capabilities, knowledge sharing, organizational learning, improved outcomes that reflect in better communion between higher education, government and industry, which benefit students, academics, professionals, and dive more dynamism into the higher education system (Hervas-Oliver et al., 2021; Apa, 2021; Bertello et al., 2022).
- Giving more attention to the higher education's virtual environment by offering additional research and programs that embrace the integration and use of new technologies, software, and applications in universities' programs, processes, and outcomes. The virtual world is expanding at a pace faster than traditional physical educational methods, especially with attention given to artificial intelligence (Rapanta, 2020; Jilke, 2021; Kuleto et al., 2021; Akhmedov, 2022). Adapting new technological tools and methods improves universities' ability to offer new programs and expand their presence internationally using distance or online learning (Kuleto et al., 2021; Akhmedov, 2022).

7.7 Recommendations for Future Research

The co-evolution of organizations is a continual process, so integrating additional factors when investigating the co-evolution of organizations is essential for better understanding and results when investigating the relation between organizations and their environment (Abatecola et al., 2020; Parisot, 2020; Schumm and Hanelt, 2021). In developing the Co-Evolutionary Framework for the present research, the researcher used additional factors to investigate the co-evolution of Lebanese universities, including the essential factors which constitute co-evolutionary process, based on the nature of the investigated organizations and their environment setting. The researcher recommends re-using these factors to re-evaluate their value and adding intensifying new factors to construct more comprehensive co-evolutionary approaches. Integrating additional organizational factors will revalidate the value of organizational co-evolutionary approaches, expand the research and generate additional value (Abatecola et al., 2020; Hoppmann, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022).

- The researcher highly recommends further investigating management's role in the co-evolutionary process. Future co-evolutionary research should include managerial capabilities, roles, guidance, and support for implementing co-evolutionary approaches inside organizations (Garcia-Morales et al., 2020; Mitchell et al., 2020; Williamson, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Izumi et al. 2021; Hanelt et al., 2021; Wagire et al. 2021). Management is the link between an organization's external and internal environment and the guiding force for organizational change (Parisot et al., 2020; Moroz, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Lartey 2020; Shatilo, 2020; Levinthal, 2021; Ciampi et al., 2022).

- Using quantitative methods in future research is recommended to extend the research to a larger population (Dawadi, 2021). For better results, qualitative collection and analysis methods are essential to studying the relationship between organizations and their environments (Tomaszewski et al., 2020). Quantitative methods can be used afterward to identify each factor's effect on an organization's co-evolution process from various participant views across the organization (Dawadi, 2021; Taherdoost, 2022).
- The sample of this research is limited to one country (Lebanon) and one field (Higher Education). A co-evolutionary research approach can be recommended for future research in other organizations or industries to provide a varied outcome with more valuable insights (Awan et al., 2021; Appio et al., 2021; Schumm and Helt, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Leoni and Cristofaro, 2022; Ciampi et al., 2022; Halkias et al., 2022).
- Lastly, the researcher suggests future research on the alternative use of co-evolutionary approach as a tool for evaluating other organizational abilities, forecasting their possible interactions with their environment, and a tool to construct a comprehensive view and have better understanding of a specific field or industry by analyzing related organizations comprehensively (Awan et al., 2021; Appio et al., 2021; Schumm and Helt, 2021; Mihalache and Volberda, 2021; Leoni and Cristofaro, 2022; Ciampi et al., 2022).

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Appendix A

Interview Guide

Section (1): Organizational Environment Characteristics

1. Can you please, describe the university's environment?
2. On what basis does the university select its environment?
3. How do you describe the relation between the university and its environment and the mechanism which bound this relation?
4. How do other actors within your environment affect your university's ability to co-evolve (or to achieve its objectives and strategies)?

Section (2): External Environment Factors

5. What environmental factors affect the ability of the university to co-evolve?
6. How does the extra-institutional environment affect your university's ability to co-evolve with your environment?

Section (3): Internal Environment Factors

7. What organizational factors affect your university's ability to co-evolve with its environment?

Section (4): Management Role and Capabilities Factors

8. What is the role of the university management (or managerial capabilities) in managing the relation between the university and its environment?

9. What factors affect the universities management actions in response to the university environment?
10. What is the role of the management search behavior in building the university's capabilities?
11. What are the factors which affect the ability for environmental sensing?

Section (5): Competition Factors

12. What are the factors which affect the ability of the universe to compete in its environment?

Section (6): Capability Building Process

13. What factors affect the university's capability building process?
14. Does the university capability building process include selection, retention, and variation steps?

Section (7): Organizational Outcome

15. What factors affect achieving a varied organizational outcome (Variations)?

Section (8): Additional Questions

16. Regarding the location of your university, does this affect the ability of your university to co-evolve with its environment?
17. If compared to the university's historical events (compared to previous periods) do you consider that your university has co-evolved? In what aspect?
18. If the university has co-evolved, what is this co-evolution compared to? Is it compared to your university's local, regional, or international environment?

Section (9): Mediating Factors

19. Is there anything you would like to add regarding other factors that can affect the ability of the university to co-evolve with its environment?

Appendix B

Interview Transcript Sample

Research Title: Investigating the Challenges Affecting the Co-Evolution of Universities in a Competitive Environment: The Case of Lebanese Universities

Date: 30th June 2020

Time: 17:00

Location: Beirut, Lebanon

Participant Number: Respondent 24

- **Can you please, describe the university's environment?**

The whole higher education is our environment. I mean the international environment, while Lebanon and Lebanese higher education are our local environment. What this means this means that we are already as we offer higher education and are part of the Lebanese higher education system that recognizes us as higher education institutions we belong to international higher education. As you already know, Lebanese higher education is recognized internationally as a well-developed field, and the recognition of the Lebanese higher education field by any higher education institution or educational provider gives it legitimacy and international recognition. You know, it takes time and effort to become a Lebanese higher education institution or be recognized as a Lebanese university.

- **On what basis does the university select its environment?**

The advantage offered by the Lebanese higher education ministry allowed us to operate in Lebanon, develop new programs, and be recognized internationally. Our main campuses are located in Lebanon, and our efforts are divided between Lebanese higher education and international higher education. Lately, in the past years, our effort has been focused more on Lebanon. We were not able to cope with other international higher education institutions altogether. Another factor is that we cannot compete with them since we do not own the required ability to do so. Let us return to Lebanon, because also lately we were faced with increased competition in Lebanon. We were pushed to focus our efforts in Lebanon to secure our place and ensure that we continue to offer what is expected from us. We believe that we always need, no matter what is the circumstances, to offer our best and ensure that our programs satisfy high standards. We at least start with our local landscape, and then when we are fully prepared, we can increase international interaction.

The focus on Lebanon allowed us to develop our programs and build our strength locally and will help us internationally. The university was founded in Lebanon; maybe if we were established in another country, our focus would be in that country, and our environment will also be focused on that country, and programs customized to the preferences of the students of that country. Also, Lebanese higher education ministry provides better support and facilitates our operations. So, Lebanon is our main landscape and environment, while we are linked to international higher education. Choosing to operate in a different landscape is somehow difficult and needs more time and effort. I have mentioned that we are not able to do so. We need many steps to reach this goal, face many external challenges, and need a new workshop for our university processes and abilities. It needs additional resources, methods, and strategies to go outside Lebanon. We do not have all

these, right now and our focus lately has been on the local landscape. Our resources and strategies are customized to the local environment. We may go international afterward.

- **How do you describe the relationship between the university and its environment? What is the mechanism that bound this relation?**

If you are asking about the local environment. We are having increased competition and rivalry between universities. We have always had a rivalry, and in this way, it is unprecedented. The changes happening to the stable environment are tremendous. It is our first time confronted with these changes and instability. It did not start now or yesterday day; it has been like this for the last four years. Whatever happens in our surrounding or environment, as you name it, affect us directly and indirectly. How is that so that when new developments and programs, projects, or teaching methods are introduced, we start to be benchmarked based on them? Changes in environmental characteristics are reflected in our operations and performance; they may have positive or negative consequences. We have more negative than positive effects, and environmental influences are increasing. We were able to adapt to a few influences.

The intensity of environmental influences is limiting our abilities and actions. It is a fact that our surrounding is affecting us and affecting other universities in Lebanon. The new influences limited several universes to start new projects and programs last year. We wanted to increase the number of our campuses, and it was delayed because of what was happening. Maybe in the next year, we will be able to do it. We also needed to upgrade our labs, but we postponed it to the next year or more, so we used our financial resources to help us in different areas. Our environment affects our abilities to develop, continue our operations, and limit our responses. Our response is linked to what is happening outside our campuses and what new characteristics are being developed out there that affect us here. This method will affect many univariates' development, and if it stays for

a long time, it will result in inertia in many areas. The upper hand is for the environment to determine where we will be, and we will do our best.

When I was talking about competition, I was referring to local and international competitors inside Lebanon. Local competitors compete on the number of students, number of programs, advancement of our research facilities, our international rank, and number of campuses. These factors are the usual competition areas we compete on with our rivals. International competitors are a new rival in the field, imposed on us from outside. New competitors were able to penetrate the Lebanese higher education and started positioning themselves as better international universities that can compete with universities that have been offering higher education for over 30 years. Lebanese landscape is witnessing new kinds of competitors. Yes, they have affected our operations and competitive abilities. The entrance of new external universities to the Lebanese market allowed international universities with advanced learning models to compete with local Lebanese universities. What has happened lately has disrupted the Lebanese education field and restrained several universities' competitive advantages. The new models include integrating new advanced technologies and flexible methods, which Lebanese universities lack. For example, a university based in the US or UK offers online or distance learning degrees for Lebanese students with fewer tuition fees and feasible and flexible models for learning. Affects the attractiveness of our university. Students liked the idea that I could pay less, have a higher-ranked degree, and get higher education with more flexibility and mobility than sitting in the classroom and coming to the university every day and for a long time. The degrees offered by these universities are the number one factor affecting our ability to offer new programs. International universities are offering the same degrees that we offer under the title of high-ranking universities outside

Lebanon. Because of that, we are trying our best to develop our programs, internal processes, and abilities to provide higher education in Lebanon.

- **What environmental factors affect the ability of the university to co-evolve?**

Technology is becoming number one that is affecting universities in Lebanon. The degree to which we can access new technologies greatly impacts our abilities. We are not able to acquire new technologies. Every day new technical tools, methods, and innovations merge in the market. We are not even able to know that it exists. The speed that technology development is characterized by is challenging. As we are talking about technology, the internet and communication tools, and infrastructure, another should be fixed to overcome telecommunication issues and benefit from these technologies. In Lebanon, poor communication infrastructure exists, preventing us from exploiting the advantages of the internet and combining communication tools with our process to produce new services. We have mentioned before that new competitors from outside Lebanon are influencing our abilities.

- **What other extra-institutional environment factors affect your university's ability to co-evolve with your environment?**

I will re-mention this; the changing preferences of students previously to have a typical learning experience and start their journey on our campuses, and preferring online methods for learning is a major factor influencing universities outside Lebanon. All of that, we did not talk about the influence of the ranks given to universities by different ranking providers. Ranking Lebanese universities reveals weakness more than it reveals strength because those who are on the top are always perceived as the best, and the lower are lower-ranking universities. That has led to lower

foreign student numbers on our campuses because students decide by the first 100 or maybe 200 ranking universities, and we are in the 400 leagues.

- **What organizational factors affect your university's ability to co-evolve with its environment?**

Internal, you mean, what is inside the organization. Some factors need to be discussed. Technology. Technology is affecting us more than other factors lately. Our ability to own new technologies is challenging. We need new ways to integrate new technologies into our university's system in our processes, teaching, and research activities. It will be one of the big challenges we will face in the future. Technological development is not static but dynamic. We will have in the future more difficulty acceding new tools, as they are rapidly developing. It is known that their development is exponential, and if we are back by a lot, it will be a big issue for us and our abilities. If we want to expand on this subject, technology also includes advanced software and programs that are not accessible easily and need a lot of training and experience to be implemented correctly, exerting additional constraints to develop our processes, process data, and create new knowledge. Knowledge is power. We are universities; the availability and absence of knowledge directly influence us. We should be making meaningful meaning of what is present and search for new ways to generate new knowledge or collaborate with other universities to reach this goal. Knowledge management, as I had mentioned when I was talking about software and programs. These programs can aid in data collection, analysis, and knowledge generation.

To return from the virtual world to the traditional campus-based resources. The number of classes, engineering labs, medic laboratories, PCs, and other tools we use to deliver education inside the university affects us. We have enough resources to offer higher education. That does not mean that they do not affect us. They do. The existing resources determine our abilities and put constraints

on performing new or more advanced processes and projects. To have a table design for the university, we need additional resources; I mean additional highly advanced tangible resources to integrate them with our system. Yet, it demands additional costs and financial abilities that we do not have. Our finances are diverted into the operation overheads of all our campuses in Lebanon. We need to operate successfully on all our campuses and satisfy the average level of operation. Because we have several campuses in Lebanon, it will be better if we can re-configure our university's design, to perform better, faster, effectively, and affectionally. Before, we did not have all these campuses in Lebanon; we designed our university's structure with respect to old circumstances. Now, we are working to re-configure our structure with the university's management team.

We will try to use new technologies to do that. We need a more flexible and faster structure, so we may integrate virtual platforms to achieve that. As we were speaking, we mentioned the number of campuses we have in Lebanon. It is like several nodes inside a circuit. What connects them determines their collaborations, share of knowledge, and connectedness. I mean the processes that link the tasks, data management, administration and staff and students, our facility members, projects, and research. Management of universities' processes and development is an important factor in essential to have a faster and more flexible system and ensure its continuity and synergy between different units. We do not have a process management unit or team focused on this task. Managers determine processes inside the campuses, and the processes between universities are updated annually. We may not have enough research teams to study these factors inside our university. Our research department is being developed. The same as other departments like IT department. Maybe if we had a developed research department and IT department equipped with the tools and methods, they could help us in many areas of process development.

- **What is the role of the university management (or managerial capabilities) in managing the relation between the university and its environment?**

Managers work with and through others; we all know it. The focus of each manager differs between managers. Managers' strategies, methods, and how to do things. Here, our university's managers are expected to perform daily tasks and connect with university staff members, faculty members, and students. Managers focus on assigning tasks, monitoring tasks, executing tasks, and taking necessary actions if something happens outside the university campus. In addition, university managers can perform external activities, like attending seminars, external visits, and participating in external social activities. External factors do not limit the role of the management team. It is mainly up to each manager and based on what he or she holds inside of perceived ideas and beliefs about the external environment of the university and what management can do against external changes. Management volunteerism may be a leading factor affecting management actions at the university. Instead of letting things happen, the management team does not take the initiative to take action if nothing is required from them.

- **You mentioned strategic volunteerism; what other factors do you suggest, other than that, affect the universities management actions in response to the university environment?**

My reality is different from your and other campus managers' perceptions of reality; there is a different understanding of the external variables that constitute the external environment and the influencing factors that affect the university. The same variables exist inside the university. How a manager perceives these variables, acknowledges their influences, determines how to respond to

them, and makes suitable decisions is essential to evaluating management capabilities and factors that impact their abilities and actions.

- **What is the role of the management search behavior in building the university's capabilities?**

Management is mainly in charge of searching for new processes or capabilities. The result of the research may be a new advanced way to do things inside the university or a whole new capability that we can use to perform past or new tasks. Management capabilities can allow for both. University's management team tends to search for new ways to develop our existing processes, and rarely are new capabilities integrated into our system. It may happen annually or sometimes at the start of the semesters. In the face of increasing competition and development happening in our surroundings, and limits our abilities, flexibility, and agility. Certain factors can affect management designs, but there are no restrictions on actions he can take to develop the university's capabilities. In our university, management tends to focus its search for new methods to use a capability more effectively. Doing so is putting restrictions on building our capabilities.

- **What are the factors that affect the ability of environmental sensing at your university?**

Information is everywhere, and let us talk deeper about it; it is inside and outside the university. Of course, outside is the broader medium. I told you that because I want to note that sensing our environment is based on the processes and tools, we use to figure out what is real around us. In addition to that, even if we have the best processes and enough data. Data is not ready to be collected or analyzed. Even this needs a much deeper process to distinguish overlapping data and solve complex problems. We lack many tools and processes to do so. We depend primarily on the

management team's abilities to scan, make sense and make decisions about external events. Maybe, that is why our abilities in this area are pretty limited.

- **What are the factors that affect the ability of the universe to compete in its environment?**

In Lebanon, certain factors distinguish universities. Starting from the classroom to lab logistics to the number of programs to the international rank. To stay local, Lebanese universities compete with their tangible resources. You enter the websites of several Lebanese universities and see how they market themselves in terms of their programs, student lifestyle, and mainly what is inside the campus. Rarely will you find universities that market their selves in terms of offered knowledge or research. We all can provide knowledge, and we do our research, and this will not give us a competitive advantage over other universities. We keep doing our research and provide knowledge to our students and environment in terms of publication, internships, and collaboration with other research centers in the country; our focus stays on the university campus and what it constitutes. We were talking about this before. We mainly depend on our resources and faculties and campus logistics and the outcome created by their assembly. We do not focus much on other types of resources. Focusing on a single type of advantage limits our capabilities. Other resources like knowledge assets and big databases are linked to knowledge acquisition and creation. Knowledge assets can help us acquire new competitive areas within our landscape. Knowledge can assist us in developing our university's resources and provide new methods to utilize them. Competition in higher education requires us to renew our abilities and ensure that we own better resources than our competitors. We can provide better value if we use our resources in the right way and market them correctly. Marketing campaigns helped us attract new students and show what we can offer. Marketing helped us to compete with other universities. Because many universities have limited budgets, they could not benefit from it. You cannot work all year and not show what you have

done to your surroundings. The inability to develop good marketing campaigns may have let others lose some of their market share in Lebanon.

- **What are the factors that affect that university's capability building process?**

It is the way we do things. I mean the methods used to perform certain tasks or how we achieve our goals. The steps, resources, tools, and human capital we use dictate the output of the processes. Although it is simple to define the process, its application remains challenging to be implemented. Regarding the steps, we have definite steps for all our processes, processes that we do. These steps cannot always be the same; their sequences should not be rigid. The steps we have is for our existing processes. Focusing on this point, we need new and updated steps for what already exists and new processes to do what we do. Change is not simple, and how-to knowledge is not free. I am talking about complex processes in research. Regarding the resources, we have enough resources and tools to perform our tasks not to develop new capabilities. Add this to the difficulties regarding capability building process.

And regarding human capital, we need knowledgeable and skilled staff to perform processes like this, or we do train for our staff. Each capability building requires a combination of what I have mentioned. Universities here in Lebanon do not differ in their development processes. They share a lot of similar processes and output. There are many universities where we can build new capabilities and take advantage of them. What we have in our hands lets us improve our capabilities and upgrade some features, let us say not transformative, innovative results. The result of similar processes is having a similar output, which is different from other universities.

- **Does the university capability building process include selection, retention, and variation steps?**

We do not have definite ways to in our development process. And I will tell another thing, development or capability building process name it what you were not, is done to few things in the university and across a period of time. So, no definite steps, time, or specific target. As a result of our processes, we acquire new methods and tools from outside the university like every 3 months or more. Our retention period is long. It takes a great deal of time to change pre-existed process. It can be updated; it will not be new, even if there is a better way because change needs time. With the delayed selection and retention steps, what do you think is the result of having new variations? Delayed output, similar services, and programs. So, fewer variations.

- **What factors affect the ability to achieve a varied organizational outcome (Variations)?**

The offering of new programs and services for students and the community. We need to develop new programs in science, technology, and research. Also, new services and activities within our local community or the whole country, like social outreach programs, social activities, seminars, and awareness campaigns. We can have varied outcomes by increasing our list of what we can offer. And if we can, it is possible after the pandemic to begin working on e-learning programs and offer them to local and international students as a new teaching method.

- **Regarding the location of your university, does this affect the ability of your university to co-evolve with its environment?**

No, not at all. Lebanon is a well-known country of higher education located in the center of the Middle East, its environment is attractive, and Lebanese higher education is recognized internationally. It is not where we are; it is about what we do.

- **If compared to the university's historical events (or previous periods) do you consider that your university has co-evolved? In what aspect?**

We were able to overcome many challenges in the last 12 years and adapt to changing circumstances, but not co-evolved. We need more to co-evolve and another adopted approach in the last years to co-evolve with our environment. We adapted to our environment. Environmental influences affected us and let slowed down our development process. We have made many improvements on our road to this point. We increased the number of our campuses, logistics, and increased our programs and schools. We are known better internationally and attracted more students.

- **If the university has co-evolved, what is this co-evolution compared to? Is it compared to your university's local, regional, or international environment?**

I mentioned to you that the university has adapted to its environment. Our effort was focused mainly to Lebanon and some regional countries. Our focus was to respond to local needs and requirements and then what other regional countries require. On the international landscape, we were following the Lebanese higher education system that demands us to satisfy international standards. As priority Lebanon, second is regional, and third comes international landscape.

- **Is there anything you would like to add regarding other factors that can affect the ability of the university to co-evolve with its environment?**

To focus more on adopting new technologies and utilizing them with our operations. There are many new technologies out there, machine learning, artificial intelligence, blockchain, and others. Integrating them will help us digitalize our processes and develop our capabilities. We can increase our programs and services in this way. We need to increase our publications abilities concerning academic papers and research in different fields.

Being able to have joint activities between our university and local and international higher education institutions will help expand our activities and partnerships. We need to increase partnerships and joint processes and have a good public relations team and communication channels, using traditional approaches or using social media platforms, to achieve that goal. There are many new ways we can co-evolve with our environment, from offering dual degrees, certificates like Cisco, or partnerships with international universities for joint programs; we have partnerships with American and German universities. It will be better if we can have more; maybe mini-campus strategy is not well-known. A highly recognized international university can use our local campuses to offer its programs to local and international students, with less tuition fees, no re-location for students, and a more customized experience. And especially, we hope to get over the pandemic and not have new ones in the future. We had enough; instead of going onward, we are going backward in developing and initiating new projects.

Appendix C

Informed Consent Form

Research Title: Investigating the Challenges that are Affecting the Co-Evolution of Universities in a Competitive Environment: The Case of Lebanese Universities

You are invited to take part in this research for the purpose of collecting data on the co-evolution of Lebanese universities and interrelation with their environment.

Before you decide to take part, you must read the accompanying **Participant Information Sheet**.

Please do not hesitate to ask questions if anything is unclear or if you would like more information about any aspect of this research. It is important that you feel able to take the necessary time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

If you agree to participate, please confirm your consent by signing the form as a participant.

- I agree to participate in this research, and I understand that my taking part in the research is voluntary.
- I have read the information sheet related to this research and I understand the aims of the it.
- I am aware that the in-depth interview is used in this research as qualitative data collection method.
- I don't expect to receive any payment or expenses for my participation.
- I understand that all the information I provide will be held securely and treated confidentially.
- I understand that the results of this study may be published.
- I agree that the information I provide will be used anonymously, in academic papers and other formal research outputs.

Participant's Name

Date

Signature

Appendix D

Participant Information Sheet

Title: Investigating the Challenges that are Affecting the Co-Evolution of Universities in a Competitive Environment: The Case of Lebanese Universities

I would like to invite you to take part in my research. Before you decide I would like you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear.

What is the purpose of the study?

The research aims to identify why Lebanese universities are unable to co-evolve with their environments, maintain competitiveness and adapt to changes. Also, the research aims to identify the main practices or processes which must be changed. Moreover, this research will provide practical guidelines for Lebanese universities to improve their adaptability and success in competitive environment.

Why am I being invited to participate?

You are being invited to participate in this research due to your position and role in the management, and shaping the university strategy and processes. Your knowledge and experiences, in past, present and what future changes could happen at this university or higher education sector in Lebanon.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet, and you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you agree to participate, you are free to withdraw, or if you have any concern, reason must be given, so as to be resolved.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You are invited to be interviewed about the university, its environment, as well as their interrelation between each other. Interviews will be conducted through skype. You will be asked a set of questions common to all interviewees, as well as tailored questions depending on your involvement. Any

information you give will transcribed, processed and analysed through thematic analysis software, which then will be used to reach the outcome of the research.

How much time will the project take?

The length of the interview might vary from participant to participant. It is generally expected to last between 90 to 180 minutes, but can be shorter or longer on occasion.

Is there any expense and payment from the participants?

There is no expense or payment from any participant.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no risks associated with participating in this research. Any potential risk would be related to your identification or your anonymity. To ensure your anonymity, your participation in this study is confidential. The data of this research, will be kept in a secure storage. No information that could potentially identify you will be published.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You will participate in a research, which is connected directly to your field and career. The research will have positive impact on your university and other universities. This will be, on the way they operate, processes, strategies, path and other. So as, to maintain its competitiveness, and ability to offer higher value, which is mainly education. This will reflect on the higher education system in Lebanon. Therefore, this will have positive and transformative effect on the education of the upcoming generation in Lebanon, and the role of the universities in its environments.

What will happen to the results of the research?

The results of this research may be used in articles, journals, books or other publications